

**BUNDESMINISTERIUM
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Report 2010

**Trends and Sources of
Zoonoses and Zoonotic Agents
in Humans, Foodstuffs, Animals and
Feedingstuffs**

Austria

**Including information on foodborne outbreaks,
antimicrobial resistance in zoonotic agents and some
pathogenic microbiological agents**

AUSTRIA

The Report referred to in Article 9 of Directive 2003/99/EC

**TRENDS AND SOURCES OF ZONOSSES AND ZONOTIC AGENTS
IN HUMANS, FOODSTUFFS, ANIMALS AND FEEDINGSTUFFS**

**Including information on foodborne outbreaks, antimicrobial
resistance in zoonotic agents and some pathogenic microbiological
agents**

IN 2010

1. Information on the Reporting and Monitoring System

Country: Austria

Reporting Year: 2010

This report was prepared by the Zoonoses-Group of the Competence Centre for Infectious Disease Epidemiology (CC-Infe) of the AGES. Following Institutions and laboratories were involved:

Institutions and laboratories involved in monitoring

Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
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Authorities

Central Veterinary Services	Federal Ministry of Health	Data concerning notifiable zoonoses in animals; Revision of the draft of the Trend Report; Approval of the Trend Report for Submission
Food Office	Federal Ministry of Health	Revision of the draft of the Trend Report
DG Public Health	Federal Ministry of Health	Validation of data concerning notifiable zoonoses in humans and food borne outbreaks; revision of the draft of the Trend Report
Feed Office	Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, the Environment and Watermanagement	Revision of the draft of the Trend Report
Provincial Veterinary Services	9 provinces, one Veterinary Service per province	Data concerning notifiable zoonoses in animals
Local/District health authorities	Part of each local administration authority ("Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde"), one physician per district	Collection and entry of the data concerning notifiable zoonoses in humans and food borne outbreaks

Institutes

Zoonoses-Group of the Competence Centre for Infectious Disease Epidemiology (CC-INFE)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Compilation, validation, preparation, data entry and submission of the Zoonoses Trend Report (Reporting officer, national reporter)
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Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Analysis of laboratory results for antimicrobial resistance of Salmonella spp., Campylobacter spp. Enterococcus faecalis/faecium and E. coli; Mapping of food data; Creation of xml-files
Statistics Austria	The independent and non-profit-making federal institution, Statistics Austria, provides data on the economy, demography, environment and social and cultural situation in Austria to federal bodies. Federal agencies can then implement controlling measures in the scientific community, business and public institutions.	Demographic and livestock census data

Human Medicine

National Reference Centre for Salmonella Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans and antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Laboratory for Campylobacter, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning campylobacteriosis in humans, speciation of Campylobacter from food and animals, antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Laboratory for Antimicrobial resistance, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Testing for antimicrobial resistance of E. coli and enterococci from animals; data concerning MRSA
National Reference Centre for Tuberculosis, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning tuberculosis in humans
National Reference Center for E. coli including VTEC Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Typing of VTEC from humans, food and animals

Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
National Reference Centre for Listeria Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning listeriosis in humans
National Reference Laboratory for Yersinia, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning yersiniosis in humans
National Reference Laboratory for Toxoplasmosis, Echinococcosis, Toxocarosis and other Parasitic Diseases; Department of Medical Parasitology; Institute of Specific Prophylaxis and Tropical Medicine; Center for Physiology, Pathophysiology and Immunology	Medical University of Vienna	Laboratory data concerning parasitic diseases in humans
National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, (IVET), Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning brucellosis in humans and animals
National Reference Laboratory for Clostridium difficile Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Analysis and Typing of Clostridium difficile from animals (and humans; not part of the report)

Food Control Institutes

Official Food Control Laboratories (ILMU)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES; Laboratories in Graz, Innsbruck, Linz, Salzburg and Vienna	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Food Safety Department of the City of Vienna	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Institute for Environment and Food Safety of the State of Vorarlberg	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Carinthian Institute for Food Analysis and Quality Control	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs

Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
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Veterinary Medicine

National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning tuberculosis in animals
National Reference Laboratory for Trichinellosis in Animals, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, (IVET), Innsbruck	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning trichinellosis in animals
Institutes for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES; Laboratories in Graz, Innsbruck, Linz and Moedling	Data concerning investigations in animals; bacteriological investigation in slaughtered animals
National Reference Laboratory for Rabies, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning rabies in animals
Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Klagenfurt	Regional Veterinary Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in animals
Austrian Poultry Health Service (QGV)	Association installed by law, running different programs e.g. salmonella control and hygiene programs, Control of veterinarians and poultry farmers	Data concerning the Austrian poultry industry

Feed Control Institute

Institute for Agricultural Analysis, Linz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning feeding stuff
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PREFACE

This report is submitted to the European Commission in accordance with Article 9 of Council Directive 2003/99/EC1. The information has also been forwarded to the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).

The report contains information on trends and sources of zoonoses and zoonotic agents in Austria during the year 2010. The information covers the occurrence of these diseases and agents in humans, animals, foodstuffs and in some cases also in feedingstuffs. In addition the report includes data on antimicrobial resistance in some zoonotic agents and commensal bacteria as well as information on epidemiological investigations of foodborne outbreaks. Complementary data on susceptible animal populations in the country is also given.

The information given covers zoonoses that are important for public health in the whole European Community as well as zoonoses which are relevant on the basis of the national epidemiological situation.

The report describes the monitoring systems in place and the prevention and control strategies applied in the country. For some zoonoses this monitoring is based on legal requirements laid down by the Community Legislation, while for the other zoonoses national approaches are applied.

The report presents the results of the examinations carried out in the reporting year. A national evaluation of the epidemiological situation, with special reference to trends and sources of zoonotic infections, is given. Whenever possible, the relevance of findings in foodstuffs and animals to zoonoses cases in humans is evaluated.

The information covered by this report is used in the annual Community Summary Report on zoonoses that is published each year by EFSA.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AGES	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety
BMG	Federal Ministry of Health
BMSK	Federal Ministry for Social Security, Generations and Consumer Protection
CC-INFE	Competence Centre for Infectious Disease Epidemiology
EHEC	Enterohemorrhagic E. coli
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EMS	Epidemiological Notification System for human notifiable diseases ("epidemiologisches Meldesystem")
ILMU	Official Food Control Laboratories, AGES
IMED	Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, AGES
IVET	Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, AGES
MOH	Ministry of Health
NRC	National Reference Centre
NRL	National Reference Laboratory
OIE	World organisation for animal health
TESSy	the European Surveillance System
VIS	Veterinary Information System
VTEC	Verotoxin producing E. coli

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3. Animal Populations

3.1. Information on susceptible animal population

Sources of information

The independent and non-profit-making federal institution, Statistics Austria, provides data on the economy, demography, environment and social and cultural situation in Austria to federal bodies. Federal agencies can then implement controlling measures in the scientific community, business and public institutions. The data for this report are available from an online database established by Statistics Austria.

Herds, flocks, holdings, stocks

Cattle: The number of holdings and animals is based on the official database for cattle.

Equids, Pigs, Sheep, Goats and Farmed Deer: The number of holdings and animals is based on the yearly full survey for pig, sheep and goats of the Veterinary Information System (VIS).

Poultry: The number of holdings and animals is based on a random sample survey performed by Statistics Austria (farm structure survey). The last random sample survey was performed 2007.

Slaughters

Cattle, Equids: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly statistic of all examined slaughters (reported by veterinarians), performed by Statistics Austria.

Pigs: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly statistic of all examined slaughters (reported by veterinarians), combined with not-examined slaughters (out of pig-random-sample-surveys) performed by Statistics Austria.

Sheep & Goats: The number of slaughters is based on an expert-model carried out by Statistics Austria.

Poultry: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly full survey in poultry-slaughterhouses (only) performed by Statistics Austria.

Dates the figures relate to and the content of the figures

Data are received from Statistics Austria, only poultry data from QGV.

Definitions used for different types of animals, herds, flocks and holdings as well as the types covered by the information

Cattle: BGBl. II Nr. 147/2009 (Statistiken über den Viehbestand)

Swine, Sheep and Goats: BGBl. II Nr. 291/2009 (Tierkennzeichnungs- und Registrierungsverordnung 2009)

Poultry: BGBl. II Nr. 310/2007 (Erstellung der Statistik über die Agrarstruktur und den Viehbestand im Jahr 2007); BGBl. II Nr. 356/2003 (Erhebung der Geflügelschlachtungen in Betrieben mit min. 5000 Vorjahres-Geflügelschlachtungen)

Geographical distribution and size distribution of the herds, flocks and holdings

Pigs: 97.02 % of all pigs are kept in 84.27 % of the holdings that are located in the 4 provinces Carinthia, Lower Austria, Upper Austria and Styria;

Sheep: 73.07 % of the sheep holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 74.81 % of the sheep are kept there.

Goats: 71.65 % of the goat holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 78.33 % of the goats are kept there.

Additional information

Nil

Table 1 Susceptible animal populations: number of herds and holdings rearing animals, 2010

Animal species	Category of animals	Number of herds or flocks		Number of holdings		Livestock numbers (live animals)		Number of slaughtered animals	
			Year*		Year*		Year*		Year*
Bovine animals	In total			71,563	01.12.2010	2,013,281	01.12.2010	624,859	2010
	LS: cattle under one year (incl. calves for slaughter) (slaughterings: calves only)					634,052	01.12.2010		
	Cows and heifers not for slaughtering purposes					1,083,719	01.12.2010		
	(mostly) Meat production animals (not incl. calves for slaughter)					295,510	01.12.2010		
	Mixed herds								
Sheep	In total			16,182	01.04.2010	414,876	01.04.2010	265,568	2010
	Milk ewes			916	01.04.2010	21,902	01.04.2010		
	Meat production animals								
	Animals over 1 year (slaughtered as: sheep)			15,735	01.04.2010	241,973	01.04.2010	64,691	2010
	Animals under 1 year (slaughtered as: lambs)			13,283	01.04.2010	172,903	01.04.2010	200,877	2010
	Mixed herds								
Goats	In total			11,026	01.04.2010	88,798	01.04.2010	45,159	2010
	Milk goats			2,895	01.04.2010	28,596	01.04.2010		
	Meat production animals								
	Animals over 1 year (slaughtered as: goats)			10,719	01.04.2010	61,463	01.04.2010	11,219	2010
	Animals under 1 year (slaughtered as: kids)			4,706	01.04.2010	27,335	01.04.2010	33,940	2010
	Mixed herds								
Pigs	In total			34,211	01.04.2010	3,164,898	01.04.2010	5,632,643	2010
	Sows and gilts (slaughterings: sows only)			8,092	01.04.2010	285,908	01.04.2010	99,771	2010
	Fattening pigs			26,092	01.04.2010	1,149,279	01.04.2010	5,532,872	2010
	Breeding animals								
	Multiplication animals								
	Mixed herds								
Gallus gallus	In total (slaughterings: in major slaughterhouses only)	6334		2287		65392095		72,310,000	
	Breeding animals in total	124		85		1,021,287			

Animal Populations

Animal species	Category of animals	Number of herds or flocks		Number of holdings		Livestock numbers (live animals)		Number of slaughtered animals	
			Year*		Year*		Year*		Year*
	Breeding animals for egg production line in total	27		n.a.		244,750			
	Breeding animals for meat production line in total	97		n.a.		776,537			
	Elite birds in total	0		0		0		0	
	Elite birds for egg production line								
	Elite birds for meat production line								
	Grandparent birds in total	0		0		0		0	
	Grandparent birds for egg production line								
	Grandparent birds for meat production line								
	Parent birds in total	124		85		1,021,287		n.a.	
	Parent birds for egg production line	27		n.a.		244,750		n.a.	
	Parent birds for meat production line	97		n.a.		776,537		n.a.	
	Laying hens	2,808		1,733		8,034,315		n.a.	
	Broilers	3,402		469		56,336,493			
	Mixed flocks/ holdings								
Turkey	In total (slaughters: in slaughterhouses only)							protected	
	Breeding animals in total							0	
	Elite birds							0	
	Grandparent birds							0	
	Parent birds							0	
	Meat production birds	355		145		2,280,878			
	Mixed flocks/ holdings								
Geese	In total (slaughters: in slaughterhouses only; incl. ducks)							protected	
	Breeding animals in total								
	Elite birds			0		0		0	
	Grandparent birds			0		0		0	
	Parent birds			0		0		0	
	Meat production animals								
	Mixed flocks/ holdings	n.a.		n.a.		n.a.		n.a.	

Animal Populations

Animal species	Category of animals	Number of herds or flocks		Number of holdings		Livestock numbers (live animals)		Number of slaughtered animals	
			Year*		Year*		Year*		Year*
Ducks	In total (slaughters: part of geese)							protected	2009
	Breeding animals in total								
	Elite birds			0		0		0	
	Grandparent birds			0		0		0	
	Parent birds			0		0		0	
	Meat production animals								
	Mixed flocks/ holdings								
Equids				15,287	01.04.2010	72,269	01.04.2010	947	2010
Farmed deer				1,570	01.04.2010	35,099	01.04.2010		
Farmed reindeers									
Farmed wild boars									

4. Information on Specific Zoonoses and Zoonotic Agents

The World Health Organization defines zoonoses as “those diseases and infections which are naturally transmitted between vertebrate animals and man.” Foodstuffs often serve as vehicles of zoonotic infections. Zoonotic agents include viruses, bacteria, fungi, parasites or other biological entities that are likely to cause zoonoses.

Collection of human cases

Starting with January 1st 2009 a new reporting system, the **epidemiological reporting system** (epidemiologisches Meldesystem, EMS) has been put in operation. The physicians report all notifiable diseases (case based) to the local health authorities which are part of the local administration authorities (“Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde”). The physicians working at the local health authorities (public health officers) have to enter the data of the human cases of all notifiable diseases in the data base EMS including all relevant variables and laboratory results (case based). In the near future all laboratories will enter the results of their laboratory work in EMS via a gateway to streamline the process. Beginning with 2011 the national reference laboratories dealing with zoonotic diseases already enter their laboratory data in EMS.

EMS is the one and only database for notifiable diseases in the human sector in Austria. In the near future this system is also the standard gateway for reporting to ECDC. Currently a trial is running for automated reporting to TESSy. A short report is also extracted and compiled using EMS which is published nationwide monthly and once a year by the Federal Ministry of Health online on the BMG-homepage:

http://bmg.gv.at/home/Schwerpunkte/Krankheiten/Uebertragbare_Krankheiten/Statistiken/Monatliche_Statistik_meldepflichtiger_Infektionskrankheiten_ab_2010).

Additionally data of primary isolates from patients typed in the national reference centres are available. The responsible reference centres for zoonotic diseases published the numbers of microbiologically typed primary isolates from humans; due to the fact that more than one bacterial strain could be isolated from single patients these figures may differ from the case numbers notified to the Federal Ministry. As mentioned above, with 2011 these laboratory data are also available in the EMS.

In this report it is indicated which data source has been used for the reporting of human cases for each respective zoonosis.

General Information about the Food Sampling Strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the decree „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2010 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2008“ (BMGFJ – 75500/0332-IV/B/7/2008) of the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2007-2010) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every food business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection

can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes, etc.

In 2010, approximately 35,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 75 % of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production. In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a given period of time. In 2010, seven food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2010 BMG-75500/0246-II/B/7/2009). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

4.1. Salmonellosis

4.1.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Human salmonellosis remains a major health problem in Austria. In 2010, the number of notified salmonellosis cases was the second highest reported pathogen after campylobacteriosis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The incidence of human salmonellosis has significantly declined since the peak in 1998/1999. The salmonella-contamination of raw poultry meat has declined from 30% in 1999 to less than 5.5% in 2010. The consumption of eggs and egg products that are contaminated with Salmonella is presumably the main cause of human infection.

The number of salmonellosis cases presented in this report (table 2) reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases sent to the National Reference Centre for Salmonella, n = 2,209. This number shows again a reduction compared to the previous year and reflects the success of interventions aimed at combating salmonella.

As compared to the number of notified cases of campylobacteriosis (see chapter campylobacteriosis), salmonella is the second most important cause for enteric diseases in Austria.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

In 2010, data from feedingstuffs (n = 244; only feedingstuffs for food producing animals, exclusive pet feed) indicate that the prevalence of salmonella (< 1%) remains very low. None of the tested table eggs (57 samples, between 25 g and 900 g tested) were positive for salmonella, although infected eggs pose the main vehicle for human infections.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

There were EU programs implemented to control the contamination of Salmonella in poultry, most programs involved meat and egg production. The effort of the intervention is directed toward improving the sanitation of breeding flocks and laying flocks, broiler flocks and turkey flocks according to EU legislation.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Continue the efforts already started, especially to improve harmonization of monitoring and control programs along the food chain.

Additional information

If zoonotic agents, which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obligated to send these strains to the respective national reference laboratory for typing and comparative analysis.

4.1.2. Salmonellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of salmonellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory cases confirmed in the National Reference Centre for Salmonella.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following four symptoms:

- Diarrhoea
- Fever
- Abdominal pain
- Vomiting

Laboratory criteria

- Isolation of Salmonella (other than *S. Typhi* and *S. Paratyphi*) from stool or blood

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriology: Sample material is processed as described in „Richtlinien für die Diagnostik von Salmonellen (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123-126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 11-12)“.

At the National Reference Centre for Salmonella (NRC Salmonella), all isolates are serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. And further all *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso typed according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK. Additionally the antimicrobial resistance testing by disk diffusion method is performed with each isolate.

Notification system in place

Notification of salmonellosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 1989 and 1990, human infections with salmonella increased markedly in Austria. After a peak in 1992, the incidence of salmonella illness decreased, but the number of infections has remained at a high level until 2002. Since that year the number of laboratory confirmed cases of human Salmonella infections has decreased by 73% (2010: 2,209 laboratory confirmed cases by the National Reference Centre for Salmonella).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2010, the number of laboratory confirmed cases of human Salmonella infections decreased compared to the year before (2,209 cases in 2010; 2,775 cases in 2009).

The proportion of *S. Enteritidis*, out of all Salmonella isolates, decreased in 2010 to 55% (compared to 65% in 2009). The most frequently identified phage types in 2010 were: PT8 (29%), PT4 (23%) and PT6 (13%). The reduction of salmonellosis cases is only due to *S. Enteritidis*, all other serotypes remained more or less constant between 1,200 and 950 cases (2002 to 2010).

The number of *S. Typhimurium* cases reported decreased in absolute numbers (2010: 248 cases; 2009: 482) and in relative numbers: 11.2% compared to 17.4% in 2009. Additionally 65 cases were caused by *S. Typhimurium* monophasic strain; according to the new classification those strains also have to be added to *S. Typhimurium*, therefore the overall number of cases caused by *S. Typhimurium* is 313.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In 2010, the number of notified human cases of campylobacteriosis again exceeded the number of salmonellosis cases. The reduction in the number of human salmonellosis cases is due to EU wide control programs and establishment of goals for the reduction of prevalences of salmonella in laying hen flocks, broilers and turkeys.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria.

Annual report of the National Reference Center for Salmonella:

http://bmg.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/0/9/7/CH1305/CMS1299590600940/jb_salmonellen_2010_04_032011.pdf (as of 9.05.2011).

Provisionally yearly report published on the Website of the MOH

Table 2 Salmonellosis cases and primary isolates in humans - serotype distribution, 2010

	Cases			
	N	Incidence/100,000 population	Imported cases	Unknown status
Salmonellosis	2,209	26.38	65	2144
S. Enteritidis	1,212	14.47	25	1187
S. Typhimurium	248	2.96	6	242
monophasic S. Group B (1,4,5,12 : i : -)	65	0.78	4	61
S. Mbandaka	186	2.22	1	185
S. Infantis	72	0.86	2	70
S. Saintpaul	29	0.35	1	28
S. Hadar	10	0.12	1	9
S. Agona	16	0.19	1	15
S. Newport	16	0.19	-	16
S. Thompson	10	0.12	-	10
S. Abony	6	0.07	2	4
S. Napoli	3	0.04	-	3
S. Virchow	19	0.23	3	16
S. Paratyphi B var. Java	18	0.21	2	16
S. Montevideo	13	0.16	1	12
S. Oranienburg	15	0.18	-	15
S. Kentucky	24	0.29	1	23
S. Muenchen	3	0.04	-	3
S. Rissen	4	0.05	-	4
S. Senftenberg	4	0.05	-	4
other Serotypes	236	2.82	15	221

Data source: National Reference Centre for Salmonella as 31.05.2011

Table 3 Salmonellosis cases in humans - age distribution, 2010

age group	<i>Salmonella</i> spp.			<i>S. Enteritidis</i>			<i>S. Typhimurium</i> **			<i>S. Mbandaka</i>			other serotypes*		
	all	male	female	all	male	female	all	male	female	all	male	female	all	male	female
< 1 year	20	9	11	11	2	9	2	2		1	1		6	4	2
1 to 4 years	322	148	172	182	87	94	48	17	31	26	16	10	66	28	37
5 to 14 years	419	202	215	270	130	140	70	35	35	27	12	15	52	25	25
15 to 24 years	305	166	138	166	84	81	32	17	15	26	15	11	81	50	31
25 to 44 years	402	196	203	187	85	99	63	31	32	35	14	21	117	66	51
45 to 64 years	375	175	198	202	87	114	49	26	23	18	8	10	106	54	51
> 65 years	350	168	180	187	80	105	47	28	19	52	31	21	64	29	35
unknown	16	6	8	7	4	3	2		1	1		1	6	2	3
	2,209	1,070	1,125	1,212	559	645	313	156	156	186	97	89	498	258	235

* excluding SE, ST, S. Mbandaka

** including S. Typhimurium monophasic strain

Note: "all" includes "male" + "female" + "sex unknown" cases;

Data source: National Reference Centre for Salmonella as 31.05.2011

Table 4 Salmonellosis cases in humans – seasonal distribution, 2010

Month	<i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	<i>S. Typhimurium</i> **	<i>S. Mbandaka</i>	other serotypes*
January	116	75	21	0	20
February	69	38	12	0	19
March	87	30	14	10	33
April	115	38	22	23	32
May	148	76	18	35	19
June	123	60	22	21	20
July	174	97	26	22	29
August	183	103	27	3	50
September	208	131	28	3	46
October	155	107	19	4	25
November	121	80	11	5	25
December	64	32	11	2	19
unknown	646	345	82	58	161
Total	2,209	1,212	313	186	498

* excluding SE, ST, S.Mbandaka;

** including S. Typhimurium monophasic strain

Data source: National Reference Centre for Salmonella as 31.05.2011

4.1.3. *Salmonella* spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2009 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2008“ (BMGFJ – 75500/0332-IV/B/7/2008) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2007-2010) according to the Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2010, approximately 35,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 75 % of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2010, seven food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2010 BMG-75500/0246-II/B/7/2009). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to ISO 6579: 1999, with modifications: After preenrichment, selective enrichment in modified semisolid Rappaport-Vassiliadis or Diasalm, 18-24 hours at 42°C. Subsequently plating on XLD agar, Brilliant green-Phenolred-Lactose-Saccharose agar (BPLS), Salmonella Detection and Identification Medium (SMID) or Rambach agar.

25 g of raw material for egg products or 25 g of pooled content of 5 table eggs are either incubated directly or preenriched in peptone water. Further steps are performed as described above.

All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are phage-typed according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

Salmonella spp. was detected in fresh single broiler meat samples in 5.5% (23 out of 415), in 11% of fresh turkey meat samples (6 out of 56), and in 5 out of 225 samples (2 %) of meat preparation from broilers, intended to be eaten cooked. None of the tested bovine meat samples (0/69) were tested positive. In all the pig meat samples (fresh and cooked), 20 of the 1,836 tested single samples (1.1%) were found positive. No positive samples were found in meat from farmed game, land mammals fresh chilled (campaign A-803-10) out of 30 samples; in mixed meat products cooked, ready-to-eat chilled (campaign A-801-10) none out of the 99 samples tested positive; out of the 66 samples of mixed meat products, fermented sausages (campaign A-802-10) none of them tested positive for *Salmonella*. In 2010, 860 samples from milk, milk products and cheeses (all from cows', sheeps' or goats' milk) were tested for *Salmonella* spp. and no sample was found positive as in the years 2007 -

2009. Out of the 57 sample units, each containing 25g of table eggs that were sampled and examined at packing centres or at retail level, no sample was tested positive for salmonella.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-802-10: Salmonella spp. in food – Meat - mixed meat – meat products – fermented sausages - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: November – December

Type of specimen taken

Mixed meat products – fermented sausages

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Salmonella spp. in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

66 samples tested, 0-time positive for Salmonella spp.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for VTEC and Listeria monocytogenes

Campaign A-801-10: Salmonella spp. in food – Meat - mixed meat products cooked – ready-to-eat chilled - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: August - October

Type of specimen taken

Mixed meat products cooked – ready-to-eat chilled

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Salmonella spp. in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

99 samples tested, 0-time positive for Salmonella spp.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Listeria monocytogenes

Campaign A-803-10: Salmonella spp. in food - Meat from farmed game – land mammals fresh chilled - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: September - November

Type of specimen taken

Meat from farmed game – land mammals fresh chilled

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Salmonella spp. in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

30 samples tested for Salmonella spp.: 0-times positive

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Campylobacter, VTEC and Clostridium difficile

Table 5 Salmonella spp. in poultry meat and meat products, 2010

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.														
							<i>S.</i> Abony	<i>S.</i> Bredeney	<i>S.</i> Kottbus	<i>S.</i> Infantis	<i>S.</i> Indiana	<i>S.</i> Newport	<i>S.</i> Give	<i>S.</i> Saintpaul	<i>S.</i> Kentucky	<i>S.</i> Typhimurium	Group-C1 monophasic strain 6,7 :-: 1,5			
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	6	3														
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	16	0														
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	366	18		2		12					2					2
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	17	2				1	1									
	at slaughterhouse	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	10	0														
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0														
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	225	5		1		1		1		2						
Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	7	0														
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0														
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0														
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	8	0														
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	12	0														
	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0														
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	10g	5	1														1
		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	65	2				1							1			
		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	50g	1	0														
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	10g	2	0														
	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	9	0															
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0														
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0														
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0														
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	9	0														
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0														
		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0														
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0														
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	5	0														
Meat from turkey	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	1														1
Meat from turkey - fresh	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	4	2				1										1
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	8	0														
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	37	4		1						2	1					
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	7	0														
Meat from geese - fresh	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	1								1						
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	13	3	1		1										1	
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0														
Meat from ducks		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0														

Table 6 Salmonella spp. in red meat and products thereof, 2010

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Cont	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>S. Infantis</i>	<i>S. Bredeney</i>	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	<i>S. Derby</i>	<i>S. Give</i>	<i>S. Saintpaul</i>	<i>S. Enteritidis</i>
Meat from bovine animals - fresh	at catering	Surveillance o	single	10g	2	0							
		Surveillance o	single	25g	1	0							
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	10g	4	0							
		Surveillance o	single	25g	13	0							
Meat from bovine animals - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat chilled	at catering	Surveillance o	single	25g	1	0							
Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at catering	Surveillance o	single	25g	2	0							
		Surveillance o	single	10g	1	0							
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	10g	15	0							
		Surveillance o	single	10g	4	0							
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	10g	3	0							
		Surveillance o	single	10g	20	0							
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	25g	2	0							
		Surveillance o	single	10g	1	0							
Meat from deer (venison) - fresh	at retail - imported	Surveillance o	single	25g	1	0							
Meat from deer (venison) - meat preparation	at catering	Surveillance o	single	25g	1	0							
		Surveillance o	single	25g	1	0							
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	25g	2	0							
Meat from deer (venison) - meat products	at catering	Surveillance o	single	25g	1	0							
		Surveillance o	single	25g	3	0							
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	25g	3	0							
		Surveillance o	single	25g	3	0							
Meat from other animal species or not specified	at catering	Surveillance o	single	10g	3	0							
		Surveillance o	single	25g	2	0							
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	10g	12	0							
		Surveillance o	single	25g	2	0							
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at catering	Surveillance o	single	25g	1	0							
Meat from pig - fresh	at catering	Surveillance o	single	25g	2	0							
		Surveillance o	single	25g	1	0							
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	10g	972	12			11			1	
		Surveillance o	single	25g	27	0							
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at catering	Surveillance o	single	10g	8	1				1			
		Surveillance o	single	10g	10	1	1						
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	25g	4	0							

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Cont	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i>								
						Spp.	S. Infantis	S. Bredeney	S. Typhimurium	S. Derby	S. Give	S. Saintpaul	S. Enteritidis	
	at retail	Surveillance o	single	10g	5	0								
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	10g	491	5	1		3				1	
		Surveillance o	single	25g	5	0								
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at catering	Surveillance o	single	25g	5	0								
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	25g	2	0								
	at retail	Surveillance o	single	25g	270	1	1							
Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at catering	Surveillance o	single	25g	2	0								
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	25g	6	0								
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	25g	13	0								
	at retail - imported	Surveillance o	single	25g	3	0								
Meat from pig - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	at catering	Surveillance o	single	25g	2	0								
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	25g	1	0								
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	25g	1	0								
Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at catering	Surveillance o	single	10g	1	0								
	at retail	Surveillance o	single	10g	1	0								
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	10g	3	0								
Meat from pig - offal	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	25g	1	0								
Meat from sheep - fresh	at retail - imported	Surveillance o	single	25g	1	0								
Meat from sheep - meat preparation	at catering	Surveillance o	single	10g	1	0								
		Surveillance o	single	50g	1	0								
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	10g	1	0								
	at retail - imported	Surveillance o	single	10g	1	0								
Meat from farmed game - land mammals fresh chilled (campaign A-803-10)	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	25g	30	0								
Meat from wild game - birds - fresh	at retail - imported	Surveillance o	single	25g	1	0								
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at catering	Surveillance o	single	10g	2	0								
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	10g	8	0								
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	10g	80	1						1		
		Surveillance o	single	25g	2	0								
	at retail - imported	Surveillance o	single	10g	1	0								
Meat, mixed meat - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked chilled	at catering	Surveillance o	single	25g	1	0								
Meat, mixed meat meat products cooked, ready-to-eat chilled	at catering	Surveillance o	single	25g	1	0								
Meat, mixed meat products cooked - ready-to-eat chilled (campaign A-801-10)	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	25g	99	0								
Meat, mixed meat - meat products fermented sausages	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	25g	1	0								
Meat, mixed meat - meat products - fermented sausages (campaign A-802-10)	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance o	single	25g	66	0								

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Cont	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i>								
						Spp.	S. Infantis	S. Bredeney	S. Typhimurium	S. Derby	S. Give	S. Saintpaul	S. Enteritidis	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at catering	Surveillance	o single	25g	8	0								
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance	o single	10g	8	0								
		Surveillance	o single	25g	12	0								
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance	o single	10g	10	0								
		Surveillance	o single	25g	35	0								
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages		Surveillance	o single	50g	3	0								
	at catering	Surveillance	o single	25g	2	0								
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance	o single	25g	19	0								
	at retail	Surveillance	o single	25g	4	0								
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance	o single	25g	32	0								
		Surveillance	o single	50g	1	0								
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at retail - imported	Surveillance	o single	25g	8	0								
		Surveillance	o single	50g	1	0								
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance	o single	25g	1	0								
	at retail	Surveillance	o single	25g	3	0								
	at catering	Surveillance	o single	10g	7	2			1		1			
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance	o single	10g	1	0								
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance	o single	10g	25	0								
		Surveillance	o single	25g	19	0								
	at retail - imported	Surveillance	o single	10g	1	0								

Table 7 Salmonella spp. in milk and dairy products, 2010

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.
Cheeses from cows' milk - curd	at farm	single	25g	2	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	9	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	4	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	7	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	2	0
		single	50g	2	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at farm	single	25g	1	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	3	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at catering	single	25g	1	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	20	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	4	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	at catering	single	25g	2	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	50	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	12	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	3	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low-heat treated milk	at catering	single	25g	1	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	14	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	31	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	2	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified	at catering	single	25g	1	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	2	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	2	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - madre from pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - madre from raw or low-heat treated milk	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - madre from raw or low-heat treated milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	2	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - unspecified - madre from pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	6	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - unspecified - madre from raw or low-heat treated milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	10	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	4	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - madre from pasteurised	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - madre from raw or low-heat treated milk	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail - imported	single	25g	1	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	5	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	6	0
Cheeses made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0
Cheeses made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0
Cheeses made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0
Cheeses made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	2	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0
Cheeses made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	5	0
Cheeses made from unspecified milk or other animal milk	at farm	single	25g	1	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0
Cheeses made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - curd	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	0
Cheeses made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter	at catering	single	25g	2	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	10	0
	at retail	single	25g	2	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	24	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter made from raw or low-heat treated milk	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified	at catering	single	25g	1	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	25	0
	at retail	single	25g	4	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	1	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream	at catering	single	25g	121	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream made from pasteurised milk	at catering	single	25g	41	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	51	0
	at retail	single	25g	5	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	227	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	8	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0
Milk from other animal species or unspecified	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	2	0
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - pasteurised	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - raw	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0
Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	25	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	16	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	1	0
Milk, cows' - raw	at catering	single	25g	3	0
	at farm	single	25g	8	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	2	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0
Milk, cows' - raw - intended for direct human consumption	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	at catering	single	25g	1	0
	at farm	single	25g	1	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	8	0
	at retail	single	25g	1	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	0
Milk, goats' - raw	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0
Milk, sheep's - raw	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0

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Table 8 Salmonella spp. in other food, 2010

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	S. Montevideo
Bakery products	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	7	0	
	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	3	0	
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	
Bakery products - cakes	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	14	0	
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	7	0	
	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	43	0	
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	5	0	
Bakery products - desserts containing raw eggs and cream	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	
Bakery products - desserts containing low-heat treated cream	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	5	0	
Bakery products - pastry	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	17	0	
		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	50g	2	0	
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	16	0	
	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	3	0	
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	61	0	
Cereals and meals		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	50g	1	0	
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	
	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	3	0	
Chocolate	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	6	0	
	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	17	0	
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	
	Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	14	0
at retail		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	8	0	
at retail - domestic production		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	25	0	
at retail - imported		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	14	0	
Crustaceans		at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	5	0
	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	22	0	
	Egg products	at packing centre	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	7	0
at processing plant - domestic production		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	
at retail		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	
at retail - domestic production		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	19	0	
at retail - imported		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	6	0	
Egg products - dried	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
Egg products - liquid	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	11	0	
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	4	0	
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	
	Eggs - table eggs	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0
		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	>25g	1	0	
at farm		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	>25g	1	0	
at packing centre		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	7	0	

Salmonellosis

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	S. Montevideo
		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	>25g	7	0	
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	>25g	1	0	
	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	4	0	
		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	>25g	12	0	
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	8	0	
		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	>25g	13	0	
		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	in the shell	1	0	
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
Fish - raw	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
Fish - raw chilled	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	3	0	
Fishery products - unspecified	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
Fishery products - unspecified - seafood pate	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
Fishery products - unspecified - ready-to-eat chilled	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	3	0	
Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	
Fruits	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
Fruits - products - fruit puree	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	3	0	
Fruits and vegetables - non pre-cut	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
Fruits and vegetables - pre-cut, ready-to-eat	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
Fruits - products	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
Infant formula	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	4	0	
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	17	0	
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	5	0	
Juice - fruit juice	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	4	0	
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	4	0	
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
Juice - fruit juice - unpasteurised	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	
	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	10	0	
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	
Juice - mixed juice	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	
Mushrooms	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	4	0	
Nuts and nut products	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	4	0	
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	11	0	
Other food	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	6	0	
	at farm	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	
	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	20	0	
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	8	0	
Other food of non-animal origin	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	7	0	
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
Other processed food products and prepared dishes	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	329	0	
		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	50g	181	0	
	at processing plant	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	14	0	

Salmonellosis

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>S.</i> Montevideo
	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	4	0	0
		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	50g	5	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	34	0	0
		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	50g	15	0	0
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	13	0	0
		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	50g	2	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified non-ready-to-eat foods chilled	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - sandwiches containing meat	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	3	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - noodles	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	6	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - containing raw egg - pasta	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	9	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	13	0	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	44	0	0
	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	4	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	41	0	0
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	19	0	0
Ready-to-eat salads	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	24	0	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	14	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	37	0	0
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	5	0	0
Ready-to-eat salads containing mayonnaise	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	28	0	0
Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	11	0	0
	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	4	0	0
Sauces and dressings	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	4	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	0
Seeds, dried	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	0
	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	3	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	7	0	0
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	0
Spices and herbs	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	3	0	0
	at processing plant	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	35	0	0
	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	9	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	45	0	0
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	67	1	1
Spices and herbs - dried non-irradiated	at packing centre	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	23	0	0
Sweets	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	0
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	0
Vegetables	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	4	0	0
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	5	0	0
Vegetables - pre-cut, ready-to-eat	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	10	0	0
Vegetables - products	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	4	0	0
Live bivalve mollusc	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0	0

4.1.4. Salmonella spp. in animals

A. Salmonella spp. in Gallus gallus - breeding flocks

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are only parent flocks in Austria. The permanent monitoring plan performed by a national program takes place at hatcheries; each flock is tested regularly as well by the farmer as by the Veterinary Authorities.

If *S. Enteritidis*, *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Infantis*, *S. Hadar* and *S. Virchow* or *S. Pullorum Gallinarum* is isolated from breeding flocks at the hatchery the flock is banned. For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and up to inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

If a parent flock tests positive for other salmonella serotypes, official veterinarians are required to investigate the source of infection to optimise biosecurity.

Frequency of the sampling

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Every flock is tested at day one

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

1. Routine testing: Every flock is tested at the age of 4 and 12 weeks and 2 weeks before the laying period starts.

2. Confirmation: If routine testing reveals positive Salmonella test results then follow-up test must be performed from the identical flock.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Monitoring by national program, takes place at hatchery, each flock is tested every two weeks at hatch by the farmer, and every 16 weeks by the Veterinary Authorities; additionally each flock is tested every 4 weeks by the farmer by boot swabs.

Type of specimen taken

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: drag swabs, pooled faeces.

For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and up to inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)**Production period**

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: Drag swabs, pooled faeces and dust in the hatchery, meconium, broken eggshells and hatched eggs.

For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and up to inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)**Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)****Day-old chicks**

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)**Rearing period**

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: 60 pooled droppings a 1 gram per flock, collection of dust.

For confirmation: For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and up to inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Breeding flocks: Production period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: 1 drag swab, pooled faeces, collection of dust.

For confirmation: For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and up to inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Case definition**Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)****Day-old chicks**

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: Salmonella spp. isolated from hatcher basket liners

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)**Rearing period**

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Salmonella spp. isolated from 5 pairs of boot swaps or 300 faeces samples.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)**Production period**

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Salmonella spp. isolated from 5 pairs of boot swaps or 300 faeces samples.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used**Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)****Day-old chicks**

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5+/- 1°C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like xld or sm2. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

Other: See day old chicks

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

Other: See day old chicks

Vaccination policy

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! The national program for parent flocks made vaccination against Salmonella Enteritidis mandatory for all flocks

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. I Nr. 6/2007, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). The Austrian program for monitoring and eradication of Salmonella in breeding flocks of poultry was again (already since 2000) approved for the year 2006 by Commission Decision 2005/887/EG of 12 December 2005.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Measures according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation:

- Banning of the incriminated sector of the holding
- Culling of the infected flock
- Disposal of the hatched eggs
- Abolishing of the restriction after cleaning and disinfection
- If necessary prescriptions of GMP to prevent re-infection

Notification system in place

All positive results from parent flocks must be reported to the local authorities and via the Austrian Poultry Health Service to the Federal Ministry of Health (BMG).

Results of the investigation

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2010, Salmonella spp. was not detected in any parent flock in Austria.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

B. Salmonella spp. in Gallus gallus - flocks of laying hens

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Laying hens flocks

At the earliest 3 weeks prior to slaughter, two pairs of boot swabs must be taken from each flock. Since May 2007, every flock has been tested in accordance to regulation 1168/2006.

Frequency of the sampling

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Other: No legal requirements, e.g. at day one of each flock

Laying hens: Rearing period

3 times at day one, week 8 to 12 and 2 weeks before the laying period starts

Laying hens: Production period

Each flock is tested every 15 weeks with two pairs of boot swabs; an official veterinarian is testing every flock once a year according to regulation 1168/2006.

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

3 weeks before slaughter at farm with two pairs of boot swabs

Laying hens: At slaughter

Other: Not applicable. No sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Other: according to the program of the cooperatives voluntary surface swabs (e.g. every eight weeks)

Type of specimen taken

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Laying hens: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. pooled feces

Laying hens: Production period

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. pooled feces or drag swabs

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Other: two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: At slaughter

Other: no sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Other: Voluntary e.g. surface swabs

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Laying hens: Rearing period

2 pair of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: Production period

Industry sampling: 2 pair of boot swabs per flock

Official sampling: 2 pair of boot swabs per flock, 25 g of dust and 60 pooled faeces samples

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: At slaughter

No sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

No legal requirements, e.g. surface swabs

Case definition

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements, e.g. Salmonella spp. isolated from hatcher basket liners

Laying hens: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Laying hens: Production period

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs or dust or detection of antimicrobials or bacterial growth inhibitory effect in feces samples

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Laying hens: At slaughter

No sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Salmonella spp. isolated from surface swabs

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Other: Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5 +/- 1 °C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like xld or sm2. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All S. Enteritidis and S. Typhimurium isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

Laying hens: Rearing period

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Laying hens: Production period

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Laying hens: At slaughter

Other: no testing

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Vaccination policy

Laying hens flocks

The national program made vaccination against Salmonella Enteritidis mandatory for all flocks

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Laying hens flocks

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Laying hens flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. I Nr. 6/2007, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

All actions according to EU- and national legislation

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Laying hens flocks

No class A eggs or culling in case of association with a food borne outbreak

EU regulation 1237/2007 is in force

Notification system in place

All positive results from parent flocks must be reported to the local authorities and via the Austrian Poultry Health Service to the Federal Ministry of Health (BMG).

Results of the investigation

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2010, 2,811 laying hen flocks were in production and have been tested. S. Enteritidis and S. Typhimurium were detected in 37 flocks (1.3 %). The EU-target was achieved in 2010.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

C. *Salmonella* spp. in *Gallus gallus* - broiler flocks

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Broiler flocks

Earliest 3 weeks prior to slaughter boot swabs have to be taken. Other programs are not foreseen, only voluntary sampling by the farmer or sampling according to private cooperatives is performed.

Frequency of the sampling

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. at day one each flock

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: 3 weeks before slaughter at farm 2 pairs of boot swabs 10 % of the flocks by competent authority, Regulation EU 646/2007 is in force since 01.01.2009

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: No sampling

Type of specimen taken

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. pooled feces

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: two pairs of boot swabs per flock; 10 % of the flocks sampled by competent authority, Regulation EU 646/2007 is in force since 01.01.2009

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: No sampling

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. pooled faeces

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: two pairs of boot swabs per flock; 10 % of the flocks sampled by competent authority, Regulation EU 646/2007 is in force since 01.01.2009

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Case definition

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

Other: Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5 +/- 1 °C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like xld or sm2. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All S. Enteritidis and S. Typhimurium isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Other: See day-old chicks

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: See day-old chicks

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: no testing

Vaccination policy

Broiler flocks

Neither legal requirements nor recommendations

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Broiler flocks

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Broiler flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. I Nr. 6/2007, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

Competitive exclusion strategies takes place.

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Competitive exclusion strategies takes place.

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Competitive exclusion strategies takes place. Logistic Slaughtering is permitted for Salmonella spp. positive flocks

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No testing

Notification system in place

All positive findings in parent flocks had to be notified to the local authority and via the Austrian Poultry Health Service to the Federal Ministry of Health.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2010, 3,402 broiler flocks were in production and have been tested. S. Enteritidis or S. Typhimurium was detected in 21 flocks (0.6 %). The EU-target was achieved in 2010.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

D. Salmonella spp. in turkey - meat production flocks

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Meat production flocks

Earliest 3 weeks prior to slaughter boot swabs have to be taken. Other programs are not foreseen, only voluntary sampling by the farmer or sampling according to private cooperatives is performed.

Frequency of the sampling

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. at day one each flock

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: 3 weeks before slaughter at farm

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: No sampling

Type of specimen taken

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. pooled feces

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: no sampling

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

No sampling

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Case definition

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

Other: Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5 +/- 1 °C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like xld or sm2. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

Other: see day-old chicks

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: see day-old chicks

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: see day-old chicks

Vaccination policy

Meat production flocks

Neither legal requirements nor recommendations

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Meat production flocks

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Meat production flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. I Nr. 6/2007, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Notification not mandatory

Notification system in place

Notification not mandatory

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Low prevalence of *S. Enteritidis* or *S. Typhimurium* (0%) in met production turkey flocks

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

In 2010, 355 turkey meat production flocks existed in Austria. *S. Enteritidis* or *S. Typhimurium* was detected in 1 (0.3%) turkey flock. The EU-targeted was achieved in 2010.

Table 9 *Salmonella* spp. in poultry breeding flocks (*Gallus gallus*), 2010

	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details				Number of existing flocks	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	<i>S. Hadar</i>	<i>S. Infantis</i>	<i>S. Virchow</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> spp., unspecified
			Source of information	Sampling unit											
Gallus gallus (fowl), Parent breeding flocks for egg production line															
day-old chicks				QGV	flock	9	9	0							
during rearing period	at farm - animal sample - faeces	control or eradication programmes - cofinanced by Community - official and industry sampling		QGV	flock	9	9	0							
adult	at farm - animal sample - faeces	control or eradication programmes - cofinanced by Community - official and industry sampling		QGV	flock	27	27	0							
unspecified				QGV	flock	0									
Gallus gallus (fowl), Parent breeding flocks for broiler production line															
day-old chicks				QGV	flock	19	19	0							
during rearing period	at farm - animal sample - faeces	control or eradication programmes - cofinanced by Community - official and industry sampling		QGV	flock	43	43	0							
adult	at farm - animal sample - faeces	control or eradication programmes - cofinanced by Community - official and industry sampling		QGV	flock	97	97	0							
unspecified				QGV	flock	0									

Table 10 Salmonella spp. in other commercial poultry, 2010

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Number of existing flocks	Units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.	Enteritidis	Typhimurium	Abony	Adelaide	Bovismorbificans	Braenderup	Bredeney	Dublin	Heidelberg	Indiana	Infantis	Johannisburg	Kedougou	Kentucky	Kottbus	Livingstone	London	Mbandaka	group B, monophasic strain	group C2, monophasic strain	Montevideo	Panama	S. IIb (Salmonella enterica subsp. diarizonae)	Saintpaul	Serftenberg	Stanleyville	Tennessee	Thompson	Veneziana	Worthington	not typed			
Gallus gallus (fowl)																																										
Laying hens																																										
Day-old chicks							498	8	2	0							1	1																								
Rearing period			QGV	flock	498																																					
Adult							2808	60	23	10	2	1		4		3	1		3																							
Adult:	at farm	control or eradication programme - official and industrial sampling	QGV	flock	2808		2808	33	11	6		1		4		1	1		3																							
Adult:	at farm	control or eradication programme - sampling by industry	QGV	flock	2808		2499	37*	18	5	2			0		2	1		2																							
Adult:	at farm	control or eradication programme - official sampling - objective sampling	QGV	flock	2808		1669	34	14	14	0	0																														
Adult:	at farm	control or eradication programme - official sampling - suspect sampling	QGV	flock	2808																																					
Gallus gallus (fowl)																																										
Broilers																																										
Day-old chicks																																										
Before slaughter	at farm	control or eradication programme - official and industrial sampling	QGV	flock	3402		3402	100	15	6			2	1					19																							
Turkeys																																										
Breeding flocks, unspecified																																										
Day-old chicks	at farm	control or eradication programme - official and industrial sampling																																								
During rearing period	at farm	control or eradication programme - official and industrial sampling																																								
adult	at farm	control or eradication programme - official and industrial sampling																																								
Turkeys																																										
Fattening flocks, unspecified																																										
Before slaughter	at farm	control or eradication programme - official and industrial sampling	QGV	flock	355		355	30*	1						1				2																							
Ducks																																										
Breeding flocks, unspecified																																										
Meat production flocks																																										
Geese																																										
Breeding flocks, unspecified																																										
Meat production flocks																																										

More than one serotype found in a few samples

Table 11 Salmonella in other animals, 2010

Animal Sample	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Source of Information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive	S. Enteritidis	S. Typhimurium	S. Dublin	S. Hadar	S. Infantis	S. Kedougou	S. Kottbus	S. Regent	S. Saintpaul
Capercaillie	at farm - animal sample - faeces	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	1	0									
	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	2	0									
Fallow	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	2	0									
Throttle	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	1	1		1							
Lizard	at farm - animal sample - faeces	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	1	0									
Duck	at farm - animal sample - faeces	clinical investigation	AGES VET	flock	1	0									
	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	flock	4	2	2								
	at farm - environmental sample - boot swabs	clinical investigation	AGES VET	flock	3	1		1							
Donkey	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	1	0									
Owl	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	1	0									
Falcon	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	2	0									
Pheasant	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	1	0									
Hare	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	1	0									
Chamois	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	2	0									
Goose	at farm - animal sample - faeces	clinical investigation	AGES VET	flock	7	3	1	2							
	at farm - animal sample - foetus/stillbirth	clinical investigation	AGES VET	flock	3	0									
	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	flock	12	4		3						1	
	at farm - environmental sample - boot swabs	clinical investigation	AGES VET	flock	23	10		5		4	1				
Domestic rabbit	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	1	0									
Dog	at farm - animal sample - faeces	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	5	1		1							
	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	5	0									
Canary	at farm - animal sample - faeces	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	1	0									
Cat	at farm - animal sample - faeces	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	7	1	1								
	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	14	0									
Crane	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	2	0									
Mouse	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	1	0									

Salmonellosis

Animal Sample	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Source of Information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive	S. Enteritidis	S. Typhimurium	S. Dublin	S. Hadar	S. Infantis	S. Kedougou	S. Kottbus	S. Regent	S. Saintpaul
Guinea pigs	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	1	0									
Parrot	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	1	0									
Peacock	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	3	0									
Horse	at farm - animal sample - faeces	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	1	0									
	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	2	1			1						
	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - meat	Surveillance - official controls - suspect sampling	AGES VET	animals	1	0									
Deer	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	3	1		1							
Beef	at farm - animal sample - faeces	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	80	23			23						
	at farm - animal sample - foetus/stillbirth	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	5	1			1						
	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	41	2			2						
	at farm - environmental sample	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	2	0									
	at farm - environmental sample - boot swabs	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	9	0									
	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - carcass swabs	Surveillance - official controls - selective sampling	AGES VET	animals	6	0									
	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - meat	Monitoring - industry sampling - selective sampling	AGES VET	animals	6	2									2
Sheep	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - meat	Surveillance - official controls - suspect sampling	AGES VET	animals	1373	0									
	at farm - animal sample - foetus/stillbirth	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	4	0									
	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	13	0									
	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - meat	Monitoring - industry sampling - selective sampling	AGES VET	animals	1	0									
Pig	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - meat	Surveillance - official controls - suspect sampling	AGES VET	animals	2	0									
	at farm - animal sample - faeces	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	13	4		3				1			
	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	60	12		12							
	at farm - environmental sample	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	3	0									
	at farm - environmental sample - boot swabs	clinical investigation	AGES VET	herd	23	0									

Salmonellosis

Animal Sample	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Source of Information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive	S. Enteritidis	S. Typhimurium	S. Dublin	S. Hadar	S. Infantis	S. Kedougou	S. Kottbus	S. Regent	S. Saintpaul
	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - carcass swabs	Surveillance - official controls - selective sampling	AGES VET	animals	36	0									
	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - meat	Surveillance - official controls - suspect sampling	AGES VET	animals	53	0									
Ostrich	at farm - environmental sample - boot swabs	clinical investigation	AGES VET	flock	3	2							2		
Dove	at farm - animal sample - faeces	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	11	1		1							
	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	4	1		1							
Tiger	at zoo	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	2	0									
Quail	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	2	0									
Parakeet	at farm - animal sample - faeces	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	2	0									
	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	3	0									
Wild rabbits	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	1	0									
Boar	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	2	0									
Goat	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES VET	animals	6	0									
	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - meat	Surveillance - official controls - suspect sampling	AGES VET	animals	2	0									

4.1.5. Salmonella spp. in feedstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Official monitoring based on risk assessment, own check programme by the industry based on HACCP.

Frequency of the sampling

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Assigned sampling plan, random samples are collected based on an official surveillance programme.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Other: See above

Imported feed material of plant origin

Other: See above

Imported feed material of animal origin

Other: See above

Process control in feed mills

Other: See above

Compound feeding stuffs

Other: See above

Type of specimen taken

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Feed material of cereal grain and oil seed or fruit origin

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Fish meal, dried animal by-products for pets

Imported feed material of plant origin

Oil seed meals and cakes

Imported feed material of animal origin

Fish meal, dried animal by-products for pets

Process control in feed mills

Not applicable (n. a.)

Compound feeding stuffs

Feed for poultry

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Sampling is performed according EC-Directive 76/371/EEC applying special hygiene requirements or sampling of original packaged products.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

See above

Imported feed material of plant origin

See above

Imported feed material of animal origin

See above

Process control in feed mills

See above

Compound feeding stuffs

See above

Definition of positive finding

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Imported feed material of plant origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Imported feed material of animal origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Process control in feed mills

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Compound feeding stuffs

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Bacteriological method: ISO 6579:2002; sample weight: 25 g; all isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and are serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Other: as above

Imported feed material of plant animal

Other: as above

Imported feed material of animal origin

Other: as above

Process control in feed mills

Other: as above

Compound feeding stuffs

Other: as above

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

National legislation: BGBl. Nr. 139/1999 (Futtermittelgesetz 1999, § 3) and BGBl. Nr. 93/2000 (Futtermittelverordnung 2000, as amended) containing general requirements for feedingstuffs and BGBl. II Nr. 243/2000 (Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2000).

EC: VO (EG) 183/2005 (Futtermittelhygieneverordnung) and VO (EG) 882/2004 (Kontrollverordnung) with regard to salmonella monitoring, general requirements for feed material and compound feed, coordinated annual control program

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings

Domestic feed material of plant origin

In the event of a positive result, the notification results in the confiscation of the infected feedingstuffs according to official measures. This includes the withdrawal of the feedingstuffs from the market, the recall of feed, decontamination of the feed, disposal or other use of the feed, exploration and elimination of the sources of contamination and operational measures to prevent future contaminations.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

See above

Imported feed material of plant origin

See above

Imported feed material of animal origin

See above

Process control in feed mills

See above

Compound feeding stuffs

See above

Notification system in place

The Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) notifies the local authorities and the system has been in place since 1979. The legal basis of the RASFF is Regulation EC/178/2002.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In the last 20 years, the quality of feed has improved due to the increase of numbers of farms, processing plants and retailer using HACCP concepts, traceability of contaminated feed/components of feed and palletizing feed/contaminated feed. In 2010, data from feedingstuffs (n = 244; only feedingstuffs for food producing animals, exclusive pet feed) indicate that the prevalence of salmonella (< 1%) remains very low. Although in pet feed Salmonella was detected in 11% (10 out of 91) of analysed samples.

Additional information

Nil

Table 12 Salmonella spp. in feed material of animal origin, 2010

Feed	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sample unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	S. Agona
Feed material of land animal origin	at processing plant - domestic production	*	batch	25g	2	1	1
Feed material of marine animal origin - fish meal	at feed mill - domestic production	*	batch	25g	1	0	
	at processing plant	*	batch	25g	7	0	
	at retail - domestic production	*	batch	25g	15	0	
Feed material of marine animal origin - fish oil	at processing plant	*	batch	25g	2	0	
	at retail - domestic production	*	batch	25g	1	0	

*Surveillance - official control - objective sampling

Table 13 *Salmonella* spp. in compound feeding stuff, 2010

Feed	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sample unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	monoph. Stamm der B-Gruppe	<i>S.</i> Agona	<i>S.</i> Anatum	<i>S.</i> Goldcoast	<i>S.</i> Newport	<i>S.</i> Reading	<i>S.</i> Saintpaul	<i>S.</i> Typhimurium
Compound feedingstuffs for cattle - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm - feed sample	*	batch	25g	1	0								
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm - feed sample	*	batch	25g	3	0								
	at retail - domestic production	*	batch	25g	20	0								
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs - final product - pelleted	at retail - domestic production	*	batch	25g	2	0								
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs - process control - non-pelleted/meal	at feed mill - domestic production	*	batch	25g	8	0								
	at processing plant	*	batch	25g	13	0								
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs - process control - pelleted	at processing plant - domestic production	*	batch	25g	2	0								
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - broilers - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm - feed sample	*	batch	25g	8	0								
	at retail - domestic production	*	batch	25g	3	0								
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - broilers - final product - pelleted	at farm - feed sample	*	batch	25g	3	0								
	at retail - domestic production	*	batch	25g	1	0								
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - broilers - process control - non-pelleted/meal	at processing plant - domestic production	*	batch	25g	1	0								
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - broilers - process control - pelleted	at processing plant - domestic production	*	batch	25g	1	0								
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm - feed sample	*	batch	25g	29	0								
	at retail - domestic production	*	batch	25g	16	0								
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens - final product - pelleted	at farm - feed sample	*	batch	25g	1	0								
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens - process control - non-pelleted/meal	at feed mill - domestic production	*	batch	25g	3	0								
	at processing plant - domestic production	*	batch	25g	4	0								
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm - feed sample	*	batch	25g	12	0								
	at retail - domestic production	*	batch	25g	11	0								
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) - final product - pelleted	at farm - feed sample	*	batch	25g	3	0								
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) - process control - non-pelleted/meal	at processing plant - domestic production	*	batch	25g	1	0								
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm - feed sample	*	batch	25g	1	0								
	at retail - domestic production	*	batch	25g	2	0								
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys - final product - pelleted	at farm - feed sample	*	batch	25g	2	0								
	at retail - domestic production	*	batch	25g	1	0								
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys - process control - non-pelleted/meal	at processing plant - domestic production	*	batch	25g	1	0								
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys - process control - pelleted	at processing plant - domestic production	*	batch	25g	1	0								
Compound feedingstuffs, not specified - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm - feed sample	*	batch	25g	2	0								
Pet food	at retail - domestic production	*	batch	25g	3	0								
Pet food - dog snacks (pig ears, chewing bones)	at farm - feed sample	*	batch	25g	1	0								
	at processing plant	*	batch	25g	10	0								
	at retail - domestic production	*	batch	25g	53	8	1	2		1	1	1	1	1
	at retail - imported	*	batch	25g	24	2			1		1			

*Surveillance - official control - objective sampling

Table 14 *Salmonella* spp. in other feed matter, 2010

Feed	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sample unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	S. group C1, H-
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - linseed derived	at retail - domestic production	*	batch	25g	2	0	
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - other oil seeds derived	at feed mill - domestic production	*	batch	25g	1	0	
	at processing plant - domestic production	*	batch	25g	1	0	
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - rape seed derived	at farm - feed sample	*	batch	25g	1	0	
	at processing plant - domestic production	*	batch	25g	1	0	
	at retail - domestic production	*	batch	25g	4	0	
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - soya (bean) derived	at farm - feed sample	*	batch	25g	3	0	
	at feed mill - domestic production	*	batch	25g	3	1	1
	at processing plant	*	batch	25g	8	0	
	at retail	*	batch	25g	28	0	
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - sunflower seed derived	at processing plant - domestic production	*	batch	25g	1	0	
	at retail	*	batch	25g	6	0	
Other feed material - tubers, roots and similar products	at retail - domestic production	*	batch	25g	1	0	

*Surveillance - official control - objective sampling

4.1.6. Salmonella serovars and phage type distribution

The methods of collecting, isolating and testing of the Salmonella isolates are described in the chapters above respectively for each animal species, foodstuffs and in humans. The serotype and phage type distributions can be used to investigate the sources of the Salmonella infections in humans. Findings of same serovars and phagetypes in human cases and in foodstuffs or animals may indicate that the food category or animal species in question serves as a source of human infections. However, as information of the potential source of infection is not available, conclusions have to be made with caution.

Table 15 Salmonella serovars in humans, food and animals, 2010

Serovars	Humans	Bovine meat		Pig meat		Broiler meat (Gallus gallus)		Turkey meat		Cattle		Pigs		Gallus gallus, fowl		Turkey	
		monitor.	surveillance	monitor.	surveillance	monitor.	surveillance	monitor.	surveillance	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical
Number of isolates in the laboratory	N= 2210	2		7		36		35		43		31		279		139	
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped	N= 2210	2		7		36		35		43		31		279		139	
Number of isolates per serovar																	
S. Enteritidis	1226	-	-	1	-	1	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	114	-	1	-
S. Typhimurium	253	-	-	3	-	1	-	3	-	5	-	23	-	28	-	9	-
monophasic S. Group B - 1,4,5,12 : i :-	66	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Mbandaka	199	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9	-	-	-
S. Infantis	75	-	-	-	-	27	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	30	-	7	-
S. Saintpaul	29	-	-	-	-	-	-	14	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	64	-
S. Kentucky	25	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	1	-	5	-	-	-
S. Virchow	20	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Paratyphi B var. Java	18	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
S. Bredeney	17	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	2	-
S. Agona	16	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1	-
S. Newport	16	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8	-
S. Oranienburg	15	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Montevideo	13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	23	-	7	-
S. Braenderup	11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7	-	-	-
S. Coeln	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	-
S. Hadar	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
S. Thompson	10	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7	-	-	-
S. Corvallis	9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Kottbus	9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8	-	20	-
S. Stanley	9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Heidelberg	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	5	-	-	-
S. Brandenburg	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-
S. Abony	6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	1	-
S. Bovismorbificans	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-
S. Indiana	5	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
S. Livingstone	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
S. Panama	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
S. Schwarzengrund	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-

Serovars	Humans		Bovine meat		Pig meat		Broiler meat (Gallus gallus)		Turkey meat		Cattle		Pigs		Gallus gallus, fowl		Turkey	
	monitor.	surveillance	monitor.	surveillance	monitor.	surveillance	monitor.	surveillance	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical
Number of isolates in the laboratory	N=	2210	2	7	36	35	43	31	279	139								
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped	N=	2210	2	7	36	35	43	31	279	139								
Number of isolates per serovar																		
S. Tennessee		5	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	-
S. Senftenberg		4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	3	-	-
S. London		4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-
monophasic S. Group B - 4,12 : - : 1,7		2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-
S. Choleraesuis*		2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. IIIb - 61 : k : 1,5,(7)		2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-
S. Stanleyville		2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-
S. Dublin		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	38	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-
monophasic S. Group C2 - 6,8 : e,h : -		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-
S. Derby		1	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Adelaide		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-
S. Isangi		1	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Ohio		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-
S. IIIb - 38 : r : z		0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-
S. Worthington		0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	-	-	-	-
S. Muenster		0	2	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Group B H-		0	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Kedougou		0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1	-	-	-	-
S. Regent		0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-
monophasic S. Group I - 16 : d : -		0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-
other serotypes		81	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

S. Choleraesuis* - 6 x wild boar

Data source: NRC Salmonella as of March 11th, 2011 (primary isolates in the NRC, exclusive S. Typhi and S. Paratyphi)

Table 16 S. Enteritidis phage types in humans, food and animals, 2010

Phagetypes S.Enteritidis	Humans	Bovine meat		Pig meat		Broiler meat (Gallus gallus)		Turkey meat		Cattle		Pigs		Gallus gallus (fowl)		Turkey	
		monitor.	surveillance	monitor.	surveillance	monitor.	surveillance	monitor.	surveillance	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical
Number of isolates in the laboratory	N=	1226	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	114	1		
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped	N=	1226	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	114	1		
Number of isolates per type																	
8	351	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	43	-	-	-
4	283	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	18	-	1	-
6	164	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	11	-	-	-
21	77	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	11	-	-	-
14b	61	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-
1	51	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
RDNC	40	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7	-	-	-
13a	30	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
13	23	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2	21	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5	13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8	-	-	-
22	12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
14c	12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6a	12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15a	11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
U	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
12	9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6c	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
23	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	-
1d	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	-	-	-
19	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	-	-	-
4b	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
11	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
29	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
35	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
51	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1e	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
21c	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
19a	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1a	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1b	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7a	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Data source: NRC Salmonella as of March 11th, 2011 2011 (primary isolates in the NRC)

Table 17 S. Typhimurium definitive types in humans, food and animals, 2010

Lysotypes S.Typhimurium	Humans	Bovine meat		Pig meat		Broiler meat (Gallus gallus)		Turkey meat		Cattle		Pigs		Gallus gallus (fowl)		Turkey	
		monitor.	surveillance	monitor.	surveillance	monitor.	surveillance	monitor.	surveillance	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical
Number of isolates in the laboratory	N= 319	0	3	1	3	5	23	28	9								
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped	N= 319	0	3	1	3	5	23	28	9								
Number of isolates per type																	
monophasic	66	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT193	41	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
U	13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
U311	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT120	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT RDNC	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 104L	33	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	20	-	1	-	2	-
DT 193	36	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	3	-	5	-
DT 120	41	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
U277	14	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 1	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	2	-
U311	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
DT U	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 41	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	-
DT 104H	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	-
DT 3	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	-	-	-
DT 8	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 24	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 99	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 46A	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 17	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 46	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
U310	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 2	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 27	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 141	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
U302	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 15a	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 10	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 64	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 66	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 85	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 92	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 110	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 125	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 135	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 208	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 193A	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Lysotypes <i>S.Typhimurium</i>		Humans		Bovine meat		Pig meat		Broiler meat (<i>Gallus gallus</i>)		Turkey meat		Cattle		Pigs		Gallus gallus (fowl)		Turkey	
		monitor.	surveillance	monitor.	surveillance	monitor.	surveillance	monitor.	surveillance	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical		
Number of isolates in the laboratory	N=	319	0	3	1	3	5	23	28	9									
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped	N=	319	0	3	1	3	5	23	28	9									
Number of isolates per type																			
U287		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
U291		0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-
DT RDNC		50	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	10	-	-	-	-

Data source: NRC Salmonella as of March 11th, 2011 2011 (primary isolates in the NRC)

4.1.7. Antimicrobial resistance in *Salmonella* spp. isolates

Antimicrobial resistance is the ability of certain microorganisms to survive or grow in the presence of a given concentration of antimicrobial agent that usually would kill or inhibit the microorganism species in question. Antimicrobial resistant *Salmonella* strains may be transferred from animals or foodstuffs to humans.

A. Antimicrobial resistance of *Salmonella* spp. in humans

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The overall resistance-rates against antibiotics remained stable over the past years.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The resistance rates remained stable. High level resistances against ciprofloxacin and third generation cephalosporins (cefotaxime) were still extremely rare in comparison to rates reported within the EU.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

Annual publication of the results in the NRL-S Report and the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES)

B. Antimicrobial resistance of *Salmonella* spp. in animals and food

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

All *Salmonella* spp. isolated in veterinary and food laboratories, as well as all primary isolates from humans were sent to the NRC-S where the susceptibility testing was performed using the disk diffusion method. *Salmonella* isolates from the control programmes in laying hens, broilers and turkeys although were subjected to MIC-testing; all unique strains isolated from one epidemiological unit in the course of the control programmes.

Type of specimen taken

Monitoring samples and samples obtained in the control programs from humans; for animals and food see chapters *Salmonella* spp. in animal species and *Salmonella* spp. in food.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Clinical samples from humans; for animals and food see chapters *Salmonella* spp. in animal species and *Salmonella* spp. in food.

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

All *Salmonella* spp. isolated in veterinary and food laboratories, as well as all primary isolates from humans were sent to the NRC-S where the susceptibility testing was performed using the disk diffusion method. All unique strains isolated in the course of the control program (identical strains from one epidemiological unit only once) were subjected to microdilution susceptibility testing.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

See chapter salmonellosis in humans; for the MIC testing CLSI standards are used, applying EU-RL (European Reference Laboratory) cut-off values.

Laboratory used for detection of resistance

National Reference Centre for *Salmonella*, AGES Graz

Antimicrobials included in monitoring

All *Salmonella* isolates were susceptibility tested (disc diffusion) according to CLSI. Isolates obtained in course of the control programs were tested according CD Nr. 2007/407/EC. See corresponding tables! Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For *Salmonella* this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazole.

Control program/mechanisms

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

An EU standardized antimicrobial resistance monitoring system would be highly welcome.

Additional information

Nil

Table 18 Breakpoints for antibiotic resistance of *Salmonella* spp., 2010**Test method used**

Disc diffusion	x
E-test	
Agar dilution	
Broth dilution	x

Standards used for testing

NCCLS	
Other	
EN ISO 20776-1	x

The methods are used for investigation of isolates from

Feedingstuff	
Animals	x
Food	x
Humans	x

<i>Salmonella</i>	Dilution method		Diffusion method	
	Standard for cut-off	Resistant > concentration (µg/ml)	Standard for breakpoint	Resistant ≤ zone diameter (mm)
Tetracyclines				
	Tetracycline	EU-RL	8	CLSI 11
Amphenicols				
	Chloramphenicol	EU-RL	16	CLSI 12
	Floramphenicol	EU-RL	16	
Penicillins				
	Ampicillin	EU-RL	4	CLSI 13
Cephalosporins				
	Cefotaxim	EU-RL	0.5	CLSI 14
	Ceftazidime	EU-RL	2	
Fluoroquinolones				
	Ciprofloxacin	EU-RL	0.06	CLSI 15
Sulfonamides				
	Sulfamethoxazol	EU-RL	256	CLSI 12
Aminoglycosides				
	Streptomycin	EU-RL	32	CLSI 11
	Gentamicin	EU-RL	2	CLSI 12
	Kanamycin		4	CLSI 13
Quinolones				
	Nalidixic acid	EU-RL	16	CLSI 13
Polymyxine				
	Colistin	EU-RL	2	
Trimethoprim				
		EU-RL	2	CLSI 10

EU-RL = European Reference Laboratory

Table 19 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* in humans, animals and food (diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2010

	Humans			Broiler meat			Turkey meat			Bovine meat			Pig meat			Laying hens			Broiler			Turkeys			Cattle			Pigs		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	no																													
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	1226			1			1			0			1			96			18			1			0			0		
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n
Tetracyclines																														
Tetracycline	1226	2,4	30	1	0	0	1	100	1				1	0	0	96	7,3	7	18	5,6	1	1	0	0						
Amphenicols																														
Chloramphenicol	1226	0,1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0				1	0	0	96	0	0	18	0	0	1	0	0						
Penicillins																														
Ampicillin	1226	3,5	43	1	0	0	1	100	1				1	0	0	96	0	0	18	5,6	1	1	0	0						
Cephalosporins																														
Cefotaxim	1226	0,2	2	1	0	0	1	0	0				1	0	0	96	0	0	18	0	0	1	0	0						
Fluoroquinolones																														
Ciprofloxacin	1226	0,0		1	0	0	1	0	0				1	0	0	96	0	0	18	0	0	1	0	0						
Sulfonamides																														
Sulfamethoxazol	1226	0,3	4	1	0	0	1	0	0				1	0	0	96	0	0	18	5,6	1	1	0	0						
Aminoglycosides																														
Streptomycin	1226	0,4	5	1	0	0	1	100	1				1	0	0	96	0	0	18	0	0	1	0	0						
Gentamicin	1226	0,0	0	1	0	0	1						1	0	0	96	0	0	18	0	0	1	0	0						
Kanamycin	1226	0,0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0				1	0	0	96	0	0	18	0	0	1	0	0						
Quinolones																														
Nalidixic acid	1226	8,2	100	1	0	0	1	0	0				1	0	0	96	0	0	18	0	0	1	0	0						
Trimethoprim	1226	0,2	2	1	0	0	1	0	0				1	0	0	96	0	0	18	5,6	1	1	0	0						
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	1226	86,7	1062	1	100	1	1	0,0	0				1	100	1	96	92,7	89	18	94,4	17	1	100	1						
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	1226	12,2	150	1	0,0	0	1	0,0	0				1	0,0	0	96	7,3	7	18	0,0	0	1	0,0	0						
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	1226	0,7	9	1	0,0	0	1	0,0	0				1	0,0	0	96	0,0	0	18	0,0	0	1	0,0	0						
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	1226	0,2	3	1	0,0	0	1	100	1				1	0,0	0	96	0,0	0	18	0,0	0	1	0,0	0						
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	1226	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	1	0,0	0				1	0,0	0	96	0,0	0	18	5,6	1	1	0,0	0						
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	1226	0,2	2	1	0,0	0	1	0,0	0				1	0,0	0	96	0,0	0	18	0,0	0	1	0,0	0						

Table 20 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2010

	Humans			Broiler meat			Turkey meat			Bovine meat			Pig meat			Laying hens			Broiler			Turkeys			Cattle			Pigs		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	no																													
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	253			1			3			0			3			21			7			9			5			23		
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n
Tetracyclines																														
Tetracycline	253	47,4	120	1	0,0	0	3	33,3	1				3	100,0	3	21	14,3	3	7	0,0	0	9	77,8	7	5	40,0	2	23	91,3	21
Amphenicols																														
Chloramphenicol	253	18,2	46	1	0,0	0	3	33,3	1				3	0,0	0	21	4,8	1	7	0,0	0	9	33,3	3	5	60,0	3	23	82,6	19
Penicillins																														
Ampicillin	253	51,0	129	1	0,0	0	3	33,3	1				3	66,7	2	21	14,3	3	7	14,3	1	9	77,8	7	5	88,0	4	23	95,7	22
Cephalosporins																														
Cefotaxim	253	0,8	2	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0				3	0,0	0	21	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	9	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	23	13,0	3
Fluoroquinolones																														
Ciprofloxacin	253	0,0	0	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0				3	0,0	0	21	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	9	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	23	0,0	0
Sulfonamides																														
Sulfamethoxazol	253	51,4	130	1	0,0	0	3	33,3	1				3	66,7	2	21	14,3	3	7	0,0	0	9	77,8	7	5	80,0	4	23	100,0	23
Aminoglycosides																														
Streptomycin	253	42,7	108	1	0,0	0	3	33,3	1				3	66,7	2	21	14,3	3	7	0,0	0	9	77,8	7	5	80,0	4	23	100,0	23
Gentamicin	253	0,4	1	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0				3	0,0	0	21	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	9	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	23	0,0	0
Kanamycin	253	2,0	5	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0				3	0,0	0	21	4,8	1	7	0,0	0	9	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	23	13,0	3
Quinolones																														
Nalidixic acid	253	6,3	16	1	0,0	0	3	33,3	1				3	0,0	0	21	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	9	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	23	17,4	4
Trimethoprim	253	13,4	34	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0				3	0,0	0	21	4,8	1	7	0,0	0	9	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	23	30,4	7
Number of multiresistant isolates*	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	253	42,3	107	1	100	1	3	66,7	2				3	33,3	1	21	85,7	18	7	85,7	6	9	22,2	2	5	20,0	1	23	0,0	0
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	253	5,5	14	1	0,0	0	3	33,3	1				3	0,0	0	21	0,0	0	7	14,3	1	9	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	23	0,0	0
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	253	1,6	4	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0				3	0,0	0	21	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	9	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	23	4,3	1
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	253	6,3	16	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0				3	0,0	0	21	0,0	0	7	0,0	0	9	0,0	0	5	0,0	0	23	0,0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	253	24,5	62	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0				2	66,6	2	21	4,8	1	7	0,0	0	9	44,4	4	5	60,0	3	23	4,3	1
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	253	19,8	50	1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0				3	0,0	0	21	9,5	2	7	0,0	0	9	33,3	3	5	20,0	1	23	91,3	21

Table 21 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium*, monophasic strain, 2010

	Humans			Broiler meat			Turkey meat			Bovine meat			Pig meat			Laying hens			Broiler			Turkeys			Cattle			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	no																											
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	66			0			0			0			0			0			0			0			0			
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	
Tetracyclines																												
Tetracycline	66	92,4	61																									
Amphenicols																												
Chloramphenicol	66	3,0	2																									
Penicillins																												
Ampicillin	66	92,4	61																									
Cephalosporins																												
Cefotaxim	66	1,5	1																									
Fluoroquinolones																												
Ciprofloxacin	66	0,0	0																									
Sulfonamides																												
Sulfamethoxazol	66	83,3	55																									
Aminoglycosides																												
Streptomycin	66	83,3	55																									
Gentamicin	66	1,5	1																									
Kanamycin	66	1,5	1																									
Quinolones																												
Nalidixic acid	66	3,0	2																									
Trimethoprim	66	4,5	3																									
Number of multiresistant isolates*	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	
fully sensitive	66	0,0	0																									
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	66	6,1	4																									
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	66	9,1	6																									
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	66	7,6	5																									
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	66	71,2	47																									
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	66	6,0	4																									

Table 22 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than Enteritidis and Typhimurium in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2010

	Humans			Broiler meat			Turkey meat			Bovine meat			Pig meat			Laying hens			Broiler			Turkeys			Cattle			Pigs					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	no																																
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	665			34			31			2			3			51			86			129			38			8					
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n			
Tetracyclines																																	
Tetracycline	665	17,7	118	34	76,5	26	31	48,4	15	2	0,0	0	3	33,3	1	51	17,6	9	86	26,7	23	129	45,7	59	38	0,0	0	8	0,0	0	8	0,0	0
Amphenicols																																	
Chloramphenicol	665	1,8	12	34	0,0	0	31	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	51	0,0	0	86	0,0	0	129	0,0	0	38	0,0	0	8	0,0	0	8	0,0	0
Penicillins																																	
Ampicillin	665	11,0	73	34	8,8	3	31	48,4	15	2	0,0	0	3	66,7	2	51	5,9	3	86	3,5	3	129	48,8	63	38	0,0	0	8	0,0	0	8	0,0	0
Cephalosporins																																	
Cefotaxim	665	0,6	4	34	0,0	0	31	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	3	33,3	1	51	0,0	0	86	0,0	0	129	0,0	0	38	0,0	0	8	0,0	0	8	0,0	0
Fluoroquinolones																																	
Ciprofloxacin	665	3,0	20	34	0,0	0	31	9,7	3	2	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	51	0,0	0	86	0,0	0	129	0,0	0	38	0,0	0	8	0,0	0	8	0,0	0
Sulfonamides																																	
Sulfamethoxazol	665	16,2	108	34	76,5	26	31	41,9	13	2	0,0	0	3	66,7	2	51	3,9	2	86	25,6	22	129	44,2	57	38	0,0	0	8	25,0	2			
Aminoglycosides																																	
Streptomycin	665	16,1	107	34	73,5	25	31	38,7	12	2	0,0	0	3	33,3	1	51	11,8	6	86	26,7	23	129	41,9	54	38	81,6	31	8	0,0	0	8	0,0	0
Gentamicin	665	4,1	27	34	0,0	0	31	9,7	3	2	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	51	0,0	0	86	0,0	0	129	0,8	1	38	0,0	0	8	0,0	0	8	0,0	0
Kanamycin	665	1,5	10	34	2,9	1	31	9,7	3	2	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	51	0,0	0	86	0,0	0	129	9,3	12	38	0,0	0	8	0,0	0	8	0,0	0
Quinolones																																	
Nalidixic acid	665	16,7	111	34	79,4	27	31	58,1	18	2	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	51	3,9	2	86	32,6	28	129	54,3	70	38	0,0	0	8	0,0	0	8	0,0	0
Trimethoprim	665	5,4	36	34	2,9	1	31	12,9	4	2	0,0	0	3	33,3	1	51	3,9	2	86	0,0	0	129	35,7	46	38	0,0	0	8	0,0	0	8	0,0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates*	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n
fully sensitive	665	57,9	385	34	17,6	6	31	22,6	7	2	100	2	3	33,3	1	51	70,6	36	86	62,8	54	129	27,1	35	38	18,4	7	8	75,0	6			
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	665	20,9	139	34	2,9	1	31	22,6	7	2	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	51	21,6	11	86	10,5	9	129	17,8	23	38	81,6	31	8	25,0	2			
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	665	2,7	18	34	0,0	0	31	3,2	1	2	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	51	3,9	2	86	0,0	0	129	10,1	13	38	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	665	3,6	24	34	5,9	2	31	16,1	5	2	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	51	0,0	0	86	2,3	2	129	0,8	1	38	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	665	6,9	46	34	67,6	23	31	0,0	0	2	0,0	0	3	66,7	2	51	0,0	0	86	24,4	21	129	8,5	11	38	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	665	8,0	53	34	5,9	2	31	35,5	11	2	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	51	3,9	2	86	0,0	0	129	35,7	46	38	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			

Table 23 Qualitative table: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Salmonella serotypes derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method, cut-off values), 2010

Gallus gallus laying hens, control program										
	S. Enteritidis			S. Typhimurium			S. other than S. Enteritidis and S. Typhimurium			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	37			10			41			
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	
Aminoglykosid AB										
Gentamicin	37	0	0	10	0	0	41	0	0	
Kanamycin	37	0	0	10	10	1	41	0	0	
Streptomycin	37	0	0	10	20	2	41	7,3	3	
Cephalosporine										
Cefotaxim	37	0	0	10	0	0	41	4,9	2	
Ceftazidime	37	0	0	10	0	0	41	4,9	2	
Folsäureinhibitoren										
Sulfamethoxazol	37	0	0	10	20	2	41	7,3	3	
Trimethoprim	37	0	0	10	10	1	41	7,3	3	
Penicilline										
Ampicillin	37	0	0	10	20	2	41	9,8	4	
Phenicole										
Chloramphenicol	37	0	0	10	0	0	41	0	0	
Florfenicol	37	0	0	10	0	0	41	0	0	
Polymyxine										
Colistine	37	30	11	10	0	0	41	0	0	
Quinolone and Quinoxalin										
Ciprofloxacin	37	0	0	10	0	0	41	7,3	3	
Nalidixinsäure	37	0	0	10	0	0	41	7,3	3	
Tetracycline										
Tetracycline	37	2,7	1	10	20	2	41	12	5	
Number of multiresistant isolates										
fully sensitive	37	97	36	10	80	8	41	83	34	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	37	2,7	1	10	0	0	41	7,3	3	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	37	0	0	10	0	0	41	2,4	1	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	37	0	0	10	0	0	41	0	0	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	37	0	0	10	10	1	41	0	0	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	37	0	0	10	10	1	41	7,3	3	

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For Salmonella this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, Nalidixic acid, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazole

Table 24 Qualitative table: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Salmonella serotypes derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method, cut-off values), 2010

	Gallus gallus broiler, control program														
	S. Montevideo			S. Infantis			S. Enteritidis			S. Typhimurium			S. other than S. Montevideo, S. Infantis, S. Enteritidis, S. Typhimurium		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	30			22			15			6			31		
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n
Aminoglykosid AB															
Gentamicin	30	0	0	22	0	0	15	0	0	6	0	0	31	0	0
Kanamycin	30	0	0	22	0	0	15	0	0	6	0	0	31	0	0
Streptomycin	30	0	0	22	14	3	15	0	0	6	0	0	31	0	0
Cephalosporine															
Cefotaxim	30	0	0	22	0	0	15	0	0	6	0	0	31	0	0
Ceftazidime	30	0	0	22	0	0	15	0	0	6	0	0	31	0	0
Folsäureinhibitoren															
Sulfamethoxazol	30	0	0	22	86	19	15	0	0	6	0	0	31	0	0
Trimethoprim	30	0	0	22	0	0	15	0	0	6	0	0	31	0	0
Penicilline															
Ampicillin	30	0	0	22	4,5	1	15	0	0	6	17	1	31	6,5	2
Phenicole															
Chloramphenicol	30	0	0	22	0	0	15	0	0	6	0	0	31	0	0
Florfenicol	30	0	0	22	0	0	15	0	0	6	0	0	31	0	0
Polymyxine															
Colistine	30	0	0	22	4,5	1	15	6,7	1	6	0	0	31	6,5	2
Quinolone and Quinoxalin															
Ciprofloxacin	30	0	0	22	86	19	15	0	0	6	0	0	31	13	4
Nalidixinsäure	30	0	0	22	86	19	15	0	0	6	0	0	31	13	4
Tetracycline															
Tetracycline	30	0	0	22	86	19	15	0	0	6	0	0	31	0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates															
fully sensitive	30	100	30	22	14	3	15	100	15	6	83	5	31	84	26
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	30	0	0	22	0	0	15	0	0	6	17	1	31	3,2	1
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	30	0	0	22	0	0	15	0	0	6	0	0	31	9,7	3
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	30	0	0	22	0	0	15	0	0	6	0	0	31	3,2	1
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	30	0	0	22	68	15	15	0	0	6	0	0	31	0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	30	0	0	22	18	4	15	0	0	6	0	0	31	0	0

Table 25 Qualitative table: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Salmonella serotypes derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method, cut-off values), 2010

	turkey, control program								
	S. Kottbus			S. Saintpaul			S. other than S. Kottbus and S. Saintpaul		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	13			11			8		
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n
Aminoglykosid AB									
Gentamicin	13	0	0	11	0	0	8	0	0
Kanamycin	13	0	0	11	0	0	8	13	1
Streptomycin	13	0	0	11	64	7	8	13	1
Cephalosporine									
Cefotaxim	13	0	0	11	0	0	8	0	0
Ceftazidime	13	0	0	11	0	0	8	0	0
Folsäureinhibitoren									
Sulfamethoxazol	13	0	0	11	73	8	8	38	3
Trimethoprim	13	0	0	11	73	8	8	0	0
Penicilline									
Ampicillin	13	0	0	11	73	8	8	0	0
Phenicol									
Chloramphenicol	13	0	0	11	0	0	8	0	0
Florfenicol	13	0	0	11	0	0	8	0	0
Polymyxine									
Colistine	13	0	0	11	0	0	8	25	2
Quinolone and Quinoxalin									
Ciprofloxacin	13	0	0	11	82	9	8	25	2
Nalidixinsäure	13	0	0	11	82	9	8	25	2
Tetracycline									
Tetracycline	13	0	0	11	73	8	8	38	3
Number of multiresistant isolates									
fully sensitive	13	100	13	11	9,1	1	8	63	5
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	13	0	0	11	0	0	8	0	0
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	13	0	0	11	18	2	8	0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	13	0	0	11	0	0	8	13	1
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	13	0	0	11	9,1	1	8	25	2
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	13	0	0	11	64	7	8	0	0

Table 26 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2010

		<i>S. Enteritidis</i> laying hens, control program																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory																						
		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:		=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
		N	%R	n																		
Aminoglykosid AB																						
	Gentamicin	37	0	0			33	4														
	Kanamycin	37	0	0							37											
	Streptomycin	37	0	0						24	13											
Cephalosporine																						
	Cefotaxim	37	0	0																		
	Ceftazidime	37	0	0																		
Folsäureinhibitoren																						
	Sulfamethoxazol	37	0	0											11	26						
	Trimethoprim	37	0	0																		
Penicilline																						
	Ampicillin	37	0	0						13	24											
Phenicol																						
	Chloramphenicol	37	0	0							34	3										
	Florfenicol	37	0	0							36	1										
Polymyxine																						
	Colistine	37	29,73	11							26	9	2									
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																						
	Ciprofloxacin	37	0	0																		
	Nalidixinsäure	37	0	0							36	1										
Tetracycline																						
	Tetracyclin	37	2,7027	1						3	33										1	

Table 27 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2010

				<i>S. Typhimurium</i> laying hens, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:				=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																							
	Gentamicin	10	0	0					7	3													
	Kanamycin	10	10	1									9						1				
	Streptomycin	10	20	2									1	6	1				2				
Cephalosporine																							
	Cefotaxim	10	0	0				3	5	2													
	Ceftazidime	10	0	0					6	4													
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
	Sulfamethoxazol	10	20	2													8					2	
	Trimethoprim	10	10	1						9							1						
Penicilline																							
	Ampicillin	10	20	2							2	5	1				2						
Phenicole																							
	Chloramphenicol	10	0	0									3	7									
	Florfenicol	10	0	0									10										
Polymyxine																							
	Colistine	10	0	0								10											
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
	Ciprofloxacin	10	0	0																			
	Nalidixinsäure	10	0	0									10										
Tetracycline																							
	Tetracyclin	10	20	2								8						2					

Table 28 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than Enteritidis and Typhimurium derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2010

				<i>Salmonella</i> other than <i>S. Enteritidis</i> and <i>S. Typhimurium</i> laying hens, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:				=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																							
Gentamicin	41	0	0						30	11													
Kanamycin	41	0	0										41										
Streptomycin	41	7,3171	3										3	30	5				2	1			
Cephalosporine																							
Cefotaxim	41	4,878	2				23	16						2									
Ceftazidime	41	4,878	2						27	12						2							
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
Sulfamethoxazol	41	7,3171	3												2	2	8	24	2				3
Trimethoprim	41	7,3171	3								38							3					
Penicilline																							
Ampicillin	41	9,7561	4								4	25	8								4		
Phenicole																							
Chloramphenicol	41	0	0										1	14	26								
Florfenicol	41	0	0										1	32	8								
Polymyxine																							
Colistine	41	0	0									41											
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
Ciprofloxacin	41	7,3171	3	1	18	19			3														
Nalidixinsäure	41	7,3171	3											37	1					3			
Tetracycline																							
Tetracyclin	41	12,195	5								6	30								1	4		

Table 29 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2010

				<i>S. Enteritidis</i> broiler, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:				≤< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																							
	Gentamicin	15	0	0																			
	Kanamycin	15	0	0																			
	Streptomycin	15	0	0																			
Cephalosporine																							
	Cefotaxim	15	0	0																			
	Ceftazidime	15	0	0																			
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
	Sulfamethoxazol	15	0	0																			
	Trimethoprim	15	0	0																			
Penicilline																							
	Ampicillin	15	0	0																			
Phenicol																							
	Chloramphenicol	15	0	0																			
	Florfenicol	15	0	0																			
Polymyxine																							
	Colistine	15	6,6667	1																			
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
	Ciprofloxacin	15	0	0																			
	Nalidixinsäure	15	0	0																			
Tetracycline																							
	Tetracyclin	15	0	0																			

Table 30 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2010

		<i>S. Typhimurium</i> broiler, control program																					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
Antimicrobials:		=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048		
		n																					
	N	%R	n																				
Aminoglykosid AB																							
	Gentamicin	6	0	0																			
	Kanamycin	6	0	0																			
	Streptomycin	6	0	0																			
Cephalosporine																							
	Cefotaxim	6	0	0																			
	Ceftazidime	6	0	0																			
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
	Sulfamethoxazol	6	0	0																			
	Trimethoprim	6	0	0																			
Penicilline																							
	Ampicillin	6	16,667	1																			
Phenicole																							
	Chloramphenicol	6	0	0																			
	Florfenicol	6	0	0																			
Polymyxine																							
	Colistine	6	0	0																			
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
	Ciprofloxacin	6	0	0																			
	Nalidixinsäure	6	0	0																			
Tetracycline																							
	Tetracyclin	6	0	0																			

Table 31 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Montevideo* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2010

				<i>S. Montevideo</i> broiler, control program																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:				≤< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
Aminoglykosid AB																								
	Gentamicin	30	0	0					21	9														
	Kanamycin	30	0	0									30											
	Streptomycin	30	0	0									5	25										
Cephalosporine																								
	Cefotaxim	30	0	0			15	14	1															
	Ceftazidime	30	0	0					26	4														
Folsäureinhibitoren																								
	Sulfamethoxazol	30	0	0												1	28	1						
	Trimethoprim	30	0	0						30														
Penicilline																								
	Ampicillin	30	0	0						1	13	16												
Phenicol																								
	Chloramphenicol	30	0	0									8	22										
	Florfenicol	30	0	0									29	1										
Polymyxine																								
	Colistine	30	0	0								30												
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																								
	Ciprofloxacin	30	0	0	1	11	18																	
	Nalidixinsäure	30	0	0									29	1										
Tetracycline																								
	Tetracyclin	30	0	0							2	28												

Table 32 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Infantis* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2010

				<i>S. Infantis</i> broiler, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:				≦ 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		N	%R	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																							
	Gentamicin	22	0	0					21	1													
	Kanamycin	22	0	0								22											
	Streptomycin	22	13,636	3								1	2	8	8	3							
Cephalosporine																							
	Cefotaxim	22	0	0			6	14	2														
	Ceftazidime	22	0	0				1	11	10													
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
	Sulfamethoxazol	22	86,364	19												1	2					19	
	Trimethoprim	22	0	0						22													
Penicilline																							
	Ampicillin	22	4,5455	1							3	9	9	1									
Phenicol																							
	Chloramphenicol	22	0	0									1	12	9								
	Florfenicol	22	0	0									8	5	9								
Polymyxine																							
	Colistine	22	4,5455	1								21	1										
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
	Ciprofloxacin	22	86,364	19			2	1	2	11	6												
	Nalidixinsäure	22	86,364	19									3					19					
Tetracycline																							
	Tetracyclin	22	86,364	19								3					2	17					

Table 33 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than S. Enteritidis and S. Typhimurium S. Montevideo and S. Infantis derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2010

				<i>Salmonella</i> other than <i>S. Enteritidis</i> , <i>S. Typhimurium</i> , <i>S. Montevideo</i> and <i>S. Infantis</i> broiler, control program																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:				=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
	N	%R	n	n																				
Aminoglykosid AB																								
Gentamicin	31	0	0						17	14														
Kanamycin	31	0	0										31											
Streptomycin	31	0	0										1	25	5									
Cephalosporine																								
Cefotaxim	31	0	0				18	12	1															
Ceftazidime	31	0	0						19	10	2													
Folsäureinhibitoren																								
Sulfamethoxazol	31	0	0												4	9	13	5						
Trimethoprim	31	0	0								31													
Penicilline																								
Ampicillin	31	6,4516	2								1	25	3				2							
Phenicole																								
Chloramphenicol	31	0	0									2	14	15										
Florfenicol	31	0	0									2	23	6										
Polymyxine																								
Colistine	31	6,4516	2									29	2											
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																								
Ciprofloxacin	31	12,903	4		1	19	7		4															
Nalidixinsäure	31	12,903	4										25	2				4						
Tetracycline																								
Tetracyclin	31	0	0								4	27												

Table 34 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Kottbus* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2010

				<i>S. Kottbus</i> turkey, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:				=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																							
	Gentamicin	13	0	0																			
	Kanamycin	13	0	0																			
	Streptomycin	13	0	0																			
Cephalosporine																							
	Cefotaxim	13	0	0																			
	Ceftazidime	13	0	0																			
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
	Sulfamethoxazol	13	0	0																			
	Trimethoprim	13	0	0																			
Penicilline																							
	Ampicillin	13	0	0																			
Phenicol																							
	Chloramphenicol	13	0	0																			
	Florfenicol	13	0	0																			
Polymyxine																							
	Colistine	13	0	0																			
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
	Ciprofloxacin	13	0	0																			
	Nalidixinsäure	13	0	0																			
Tetracycline																							
	Tetracyclin	13	0	0																			

Table 35 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Saintpaul* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2010

				<i>S. Saintpaul</i> turkey control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:				=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		N	%R	n	n																		
Aminoglykosid AB																							
	Gentamicin	11	0	0					9	2													
	Kanamycin	11	0	0								11											
	Streptomycin	11	63,636	7									3		1		4	3					
Cephalosporine																							
	Cefotaxim	11	0	0			9	2															
	Ceftazidime	11	0	0					9	2													
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
	Sulfamethoxazol	11	72,727	8													3					8	
	Trimethoprim	11	72,727	8						3							8						
Penicilline																							
	Ampicillin	11	72,727	8							3						8						
Phenicol																							
	Chloramphenicol	11	0	0									5	6									
	Florfenicol	11	0	0									10	1									
Polymyxine																							
	Colistine	11	0	0								11											
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
	Ciprofloxacin	11	81,818	9			2	2	7														
	Nalidixinsäure	11	81,818	9									2					9					
Tetracycline																							
	Tetracyclin	11	72,727	8								3					1	7					

Table 36 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than S. Kottbus and S. Saintpaul derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2010

				<i>Salmonella</i> other than S. Kottbus and S. Saintpaul turkey, control program																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:				=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
	N	%R	n	n																				
Aminoglykosid AB																								
Gentamicin	8	0	0						6	2														
Kanamycin	8	12,5	1										7							1				
Streptomycin	8	12,5	1								1				2	2	2	1						
Cephalosporine																								
Cefotaxim	8	0	0				5	2		1														
Ceftazidime	8	0	0						5	2	1													
Folsäureinhibitoren																								
Sulfamethoxazol	8	37,5	3												1	2	2						3	
Trimethoprim	8	0	0							8														
Penicilline																								
Ampicillin	8	0	0								5	3												
Phenicole																								
Chloramphenicol	8	0	0										5	2	1									
Florfenicol	8	0	0										7	1										
Polymyxine																								
Colistine	8	25	2									6	1	1										
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																								
Ciprofloxacin	8	25	2			3	3			1	1													
Nalidixinsäure	8	25	2										6						2					
Tetracycline																								
Tetracyclin	8	37,5	3									5						1	2					

4.2. Campylobacteriosis

4.2.1. General evaluation of the national situation

A. Thermotolerant Campylobacter general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2006, the number of notified human campylobacteriosis cases exceeded for the first time the number of notified salmonellosis cases in Austria. Since then, the gap between the number of human campylobacter cases and salmonella cases has been widening.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In recent years, the number of notified cases of campylobacteriosis – with the exception of 2003 – steadily increased, reaching a new peak of 6,077 cases in 2007. The number of Campylobacter cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases $n = 4,405$.

The sources of infection are still unclear. The few published outbreaks in Austria were due to contaminated cow's raw milk or chicken meat. Pets may be considered another possible source.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Feedings stuff has no obvious relevance. Animals are diversly infected: broiler flocks around 50%, cattle approx. 25%. The actual source of infection is unknown in human cases, chicken meat may account for approx. 40% of human infections.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

On January 1st, 2006, the Federal Zoonoses Act (128. Bundesgesetz: Zoonosengesetz, published on 18th November 2005) was implemented. The subject of this Act is to ensure that zoonoses, zoonotic agents and related antimicrobial resistance are properly monitored, that food-borne outbreaks receive proper epidemiological investigation to enable the collection of the information necessary in the EU. According to this Zoonoses Act, to survey and combat the zoonoses in Austria, a Federal Commission for Zoonoses (Zoonoses Commission) has been founded to advise the Federal Minister. The first meeting took place on May 3rd, 2006. The tasks of this Zoonoses Commission are

- Securing of effective and continuous teamwork of special fields concerned
- Cooperation based on free exchange of general information and where necessary, of specific data
- Determination of measures in case of Austrian-wide food borne outbreaks (concerning several provinces by one outbreak)
- Issues the annually report on trends and sources of zoonoses in Austria
- Preparation of risk based, integrated monitoring and surveillance programmes

The Austria-wide monitoring program on the trends of campylobacter prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of campylobacter in broiler and cattle was continued for the fifth year according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council and the Federal Zoonoses Act. The sampling was carried out from January to December 2010, and follow up programs will be implemented in the forthcoming years. In 2010, the monitoring program was suspended in pigs due to low relevance for human infections.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Continue to work for harmonization of monitoring programs

Additional information

If zoonotic agents, which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.2.2. Campylobacteriosis in humans

A. Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of *Campylobacter* cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory cases confirmed of the National Reference Centre for *Campylobacter*.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following three symptoms:

- Diarrhoea
- Abdominal pain
- Fever

Laboratory criteria

- Isolation of *Campylobacter* spp. from stool or blood
- Differentiation of *Campylobacter* spp. should be performed if possible

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Stool samples are plated on selective media and incubated in microaerobic atmosphere at 37 - 42 °C for a minimum of 36 hours (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123-126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 13). *Campylobacter* is confirmed by observing the typical colony morphology and characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope. For typing and differentiation of isolates to species level the production of catalase and oxidase, the reaction in hippurate and indoxylacetate-hydrolysis is performed. The differentiation to species-level is not performed in each laboratory.

Notification system in place

Notification of *Campylobacteriosis* according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2006, the number of notified human *campylobacteriosis* cases in Austria exceeded the number of notified salmonellosis cases for the first time. Since that year *campylobacteriosis* has remained the most frequently reported bacterial enteritis in humans in Austria.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2010 campylobacteriosis (n = 4,405) was the most frequently notified foodborne enteric disease. It seems that the main sources of infection are chicken meat and raw milk (Feierl G. 2007. Jahresbericht 2006 der Nationalen Referenzzentrale für Campylobacter. Mitteilungen der Sanitätsverwaltung 4/2007).

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In 2010, campylobacteriosis remained the most frequently notified food borne disease in Austria.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. Annual report of the National Reference Centre

http://bmg.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/5/4/2/CH1305/CMS1299587296083/jb_campylobacter_2010_re_v.pdf (as of 9.05.2011).

Provisionally yearly report published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 37 Campylobacteriosis in humans - species/serotype distribution, 2010

	Cases			
	N	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases
Campylobacteriosis	4,405	52.60	n.a.	n.a.
Campylobacter spp., typed	2,735	32.66	n.a.	n.a.
<i>C. jejuni</i>	2,555	30.51	n.a.	n.a.
<i>C. coli</i>	167	1.99	n.a.	n.a.
<i>other Campylobacter spp.</i>	13	0.16	n.a.	n.a.

Data source: EMS as 31.05.2011

Table 38 Campylobacteriosis in humans - age distribution, 2010

Age group	<i>Campylobacter spp.</i>			<i>C. jejuni</i>			<i>C. coli</i>		
	all	male	female	all	male	female	all	male	female
< 1 year	48	34	14	25	17	8	2	2	-
1 to 4 years	387	219	168	209	111	98	6	2	4
5 to 14 years	819	430	389	487	250	237	12	7	5
15 to 24 years	1,275	702	573	747	416	331	25	13	12
25 to 44 years	753	416	337	440	247	193	45	23	22
45 to 64 years	489	296	193	294	189	105	36	19	17
65 years and older	634	290	344	353	166	187	41	19	22
All age groups	4,405	2,387	2,018	2,555	1,396	1,159	167	85	82

Data source: EMS as 31.05.2011

Table 39 Campylobacteriosis in humans - seasonal distribution, 2010

Month	<i>Campylobacteriosis</i>
	Cases
January	311
February	162
March	235
April	234
May	344
June	492
July	501
August	607
September	433
October	391
November	401
December	294
Total	4405

Data source: EMS as 31.05.2011

4.2.3. Campylobacter in foodstuffs

A. Campylobacter, thermotolerant in food - all foodstuffs - official food

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2009 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2008“ (BMGFJ – 75500/0332-IV/B/7/2008) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2007-2010) according to Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes, etc.

In 2010, approximately 35,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 75 % of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-dept information. In 2010, seven food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2010 BMG-75500/0246-II/B/7/2009). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Samples are cultured either according to ISO 10272: 1995 or preenriched in Bolton bouillon at 42 °C for 48 hours and subsequent plated on CCDA- or modified CCDA agar at 42 °C for 48 hours microaerophilic. Campylobacter-like colonies were identified serologically, observing their characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope and the production of catalase and oxidase. Not all isolates of Campylobacter spp. are differentiated.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

357 single samples of fresh broiler meat were tested and in 10% (= 37 samples) thermotolerant Campylobacter was found (2009: in 26%). In 11 samples of pasteurised cows' milk, no sample was found positive as well as in 36 samples of raw cows' milk.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-803-10: Campylobacter in food - Meat from farmed game – land mammals fresh chilled - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: September - November

Type of specimen taken

Meat from farmed game – land mammals fresh chilled

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Campylobacter in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

30 samples tested for Campylobacter: 0-times positive

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Salmonella spp., VTEC and Clostridium difficile

Table 40 Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* spp. in poultry meat, 2010

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for thermophilic <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<i>Campylobacter coli</i>	<i>Campylobacter jejuni</i>	<i>Campylobacter</i> spp., unspecified
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	324	10		1	9
	at retail - imported	single	25g	3	0			
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	30	27	17	10	
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0			
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		single	25g	225	2			2
Meat from turkey - fresh	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	7	3			3
Meat from ducks - unspecified		single	25g	2	1			1
Meat from geese - unspecified	at retail - imported	single	25g	12	5			5
Meat from poultry - unspecified - fresh	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	3	3	2	1	
Meat from poultry - unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at catering	single	25g	1	0			
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	1	1		
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	1			1

Table 41 Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* spp. in food, 2010

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for thermophilic <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<i>Campylobacter jejuni</i>
Milk cows' - pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	11	0	
Milk, cows' - raw	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	0	
	at catering	single	25g	3	0	
	at farm	single	25g	8	0	
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacturing of raw or low heat-treated products	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	10	0	
	at catering	single	25g	1	0	
	at farm	single	25g	1	0	
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	8	0	
Milk sheep's - raw	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	
Milk goats' - raw	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	
Milk from other animal species or unspecified	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - raw	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	0	
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - not specified	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	14	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	
	at retail - imported	single	25g	1	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	0	
Meat from sheep - meat preparation	at catering	single	25g	1	0	
Meat from farmed game - land mammals fresh chilled (campaign A-803-10)	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	30	0	
Other processed food products and prepared dishes	at catering	single	25g	5	1	1
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	
Fishery products - unspecified	at retail - imported	single	25g	1	0	

4.2.4. Campylobacter in animals

A. *Campylobacter* spp. in animal - Cattle (bovine animals) - at slaughterhouse - animal sample - faeces - Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Since 2004 monitoring plans on the prevalence of selected zoonotic agents and their antimicrobial resistance have been performed annually. Based on the prevalence of thermotolerant *Campylobacter* in cattle in 2008 the number of caecum samples was calculated (N = 671) to obtain 170 thermotolerant *Campylobacter* for antimicrobial susceptibility testing. Caecal contents of slaughtered cattle of Austrian origin were sampled in slaughter houses where at least 80% of all cattle were slaughtered in 2009. The sampling had been stratified on the number of slaughtered animals by abattoirs all over Austria. The date of sampling was randomized over the period of the study.

Frequency of the sampling

Animals at slaughter:

The sampling was distributed by randomization over the whole year 2010.

Type of specimen taken

Animals at slaughter: Caecum containing a minimum of 50 to 100 grams of content.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The sampling was performed by official veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration a part of the colon was ligated and wrapped in a sterile plastic bag. After cooling down to 4 °C the sample was sent in a hobbox or polystyrene box after adding cooling units to the Institute of Veterinary Diseases Control (IVET) in Graz. In the laboratory some content of each colon was inoculated in selective bouillon suitable for *Campylobacter jejuni/coli*.

Case definition

A bovine animal is considered to be infected with thermotolerant *Campylobacter* following isolation of *Campylobacter jejuni* or *C. coli* from its caecum.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Approximately 1 gram of content of the colon was enriched in Preston bouillon in microaerophilic atmosphere for 24 hours at 42 °C. Subsequently the preenrichment was plated on modified CCD agar (mCCDA) and incubated in microaerophilic atmosphere at 42 ± 1 °C for 48 hours. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were identified by observing their characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope and the production of catalase and oxidase.

For typing and differentiating of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates, hippurate reaction and indoxylacetate-hydrolysis was performed. All *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates were frozen in proteose pepton solution containing 10% glycerol or thioglycolate-broth at -70 °C.

For quality control *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 and internal control isolates of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli*.

Statistical analysis was performed with EpiInfo version 3.3.5.

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not performed in Austria

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Emphasis should be placed on education of the people for a better care in kitchen hygiene.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None

Notification system in place

Findings of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* in animals must not be reported to authorities in Austria.

Results of the investigation

See respective tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 184 out of 671 (27.4%) caecum samples from slaughtered bovine animals thermotolerant *Campylobacter* were detected. There was no significant change in the prevalence compared to the previous years (28.5% in 2008). Due to the 47% (184/394) prevalence of positive broiler slaughter batches for thermotolerant *Campylobacter*, there may be a higher risk for humans to get infected from poultry meat than from the consumption of beef or veal.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

Nil

B. *Campylobacter* spp. in animal – broiler - at slaughterhouse –official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In 2010 the monitoring on the prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of *Campylobacter* spp. was continued in broiler flocks. The period of sampling was randomized over the whole year. Sampling was performed in the 5 broiler slaughter facilities with slaughter batches consisting of >2000 animals in Austria in 2009.

Frequency of the sampling

Rearing period: no program

Before slaughter at farm: no program

At slaughter: according to the randomized sampling plan

Type of specimen taken

Intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Rearing period: no program

Before slaughter at farm: no program

At slaughter: The sampling was performed by official veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration the whole intestines of 10 animals were taken and wrapped in a sterile plastic bag. Additionally a carcass from the same slaughter batch was sampled. After cooling down to 4 °C the sample was sent in a hobbox or polystyrene box after adding cooling units to the Institute of Veterinary Diseases Control (IVET) in Graz. In the laboratory a caecum of each intestinal convolute was identified, some content of each caecum pooled and plated on selective medium suitable for *Campylobacter jejuni/coli*.

Case definition

At slaughter: A slaughter batch is considered to be infected with thermotolerant *Campylobacter* following isolation of *Campylobacter jejuni* or *C. coli* from the pooled caecal content.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

At slaughter: The pooled samples were examined by direct inoculation on modified CCD agar (mCCDA) that was incubated in microaerophilic atmosphere at 42 ± 1 °C for 48 hours. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were identified by observing their characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope and the production of catalase and oxidase. For typing and differentiating of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates, hippurate reaction and indoxylacetate-hydrolysis was performed. All *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates were frozen in proteose peptone solution containing 10 % glycerol or thioglycolat-broth at -70 °C. For quality control *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 and internal control isolates *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* were used. Statistical analysis was performed with EpiInfo version 3.3.2.

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not performed in Austria.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Different strategies are in discussion, e.g. a quick test for identification of *campylobacter* infected flocks at farm.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Emphasis should be placed on education of the people for a better care in kitchen hygiene.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None.

Notification system in place

Findings of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* in animals must not be reported to authorities in Austria.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In the course of this monitoring thermotolerant *Campylobacter* were detected in 184 out of 394 (46.7%) of the tested slaughter batches. Due to the fact that poultry is the animal species with the highest

prevalence of *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli*, poultry meat seem to be the most risky food combined with mistakes in kitchen hygiene for humans acquiring an infection with *C. jejuni/coli*.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

C. *Campylobacter* spp. in animal - Pigs - at slaughterhouse – monitoring programme – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

No monitoring in 2010 due to the presumably low relevance of pigs for infections in humans (up to 99% of campylobacter in pigs are *C. coli*).

Table 42 Thermophilic *Campylobacter* spp. in animals, 2010

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit				
						Units tested	Total units positive	Campylobacter jejuni	Campylobacter coli
Broiler flocks	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	10 intestines per slaughter batch	IVET Graz	slaughter batch	394	184	122	62
Cattle (bovine animals) - meat production animals - calves (under 1 year)	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling		IVET Graz	animal	14	0	0	0
Cattle (bovine animals) - meat production animals - young cattle (1-2 years)	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling		IVET Graz	animal	194	79	62	17
Cattle (bovine animals) - adult cattle over 2 years	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling		IVET Graz	animal	463	105	83	22

IVET Graz: AGES Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Graz

4.2.5. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter* spp.

A. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli* in humans

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

A sentinel surveillance program for *Campylobacter* isolates from human infections was installed in October 2006. On a monthly basis, the first 10 isolates collected at each of four designated diagnostic laboratories serving different provinces in Austria are sent to the National Reference Laboratory for *Campylobacter* for speciation analysis and antimicrobial resistance testing.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Stool specimens were plated on *Campylobacter* blood-free selective media at 37°C or 42°C for 48 hours under micro aerobic conditions, and organisms were identified as *Campylobacter* spp. by oxidase testing and cell morphology. Isolates were speciated by hippurate hydrolysis, indoxyl acetate hydrolysis, katalase production, and species-specific real-time PCR.

Broth micro dilution susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter* spp. isolates was done using customised Sensititre® susceptibility micro titre plates (TREK Diagnostic Systems, Ltd., East Grinstead, West Sussex, and England). Briefly, *Campylobacter* spp. strains were subcultivated on Columbia blood agar and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerophilic atmosphere. Inocula from fresh cultures were prepared by suspension in physiological saline to obtain a turbidity equivalent to that of a McFarland standard 0.5. The suspension was added to Mueller Hinton bouillon for a final concentration of approximately 500,000 cfu/ml and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerophilic atmosphere. *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560 was used as control.

The number of isolates that are fully sensitive and the number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 and > 4 antimicrobials for *Campylobacter* includes only resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin, gentamicin, and streptomycin!

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Again, a further increase in resistance to fluoroquinolones was observed, the actual prevalence of antimicrobial resistance to ciprofloxacin in *Campylobacter jejuni* is 62.9 % throughout Austria. Resistance to tetracycline decreased to 24.0 %, and resistance to macrolides was not present (0 %).

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

The newly established sentinel surveillance system will be continued. The results are published annually in the NRL-C Report and the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

B. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli* in broiler meat

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

Isolates from broiler meat isolated in the course of the national food surveillance programs that were sent to the national reference centre for *Campylobacter* were tested for antimicrobial susceptibility.

Type of specimen taken

Food surveillance programs

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* in food

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

Testing of all isolates will be performed in the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene in Graz. All 2010 *Campylobacter* isolates from broiler meat were tested.

Methods used for collecting data

All informations concerning the tested food and results of the antimicrobial testing were entered and analysed in a Microsoft® Excel tables.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Described in chapter thermotolerant *Campylobacter* in broilers.

Broth micro dilution susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter* spp. isolates was done using customised Sensititre® susceptibility micro titre plates (TREK Diagnostic Systems, Ltd., East Grinstead, West Sussex, and England). Briefly, *Campylobacter* spp. strains were subcultivated on Columbia blood agar and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerophilic atmosphere. Inocula from fresh cultures were prepared by suspension in physiological saline to obtain a turbidity equivalent to that of a McFarland standard 0.5. The suspension was added to Mueller Hinton bouillon for a final concentration of approximately 500,000 cfu/ml and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerophilic atmosphere. *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560 was used as control.

MIC values have been entered in a Microsoft® Excel datasheet.

The number of isolates that are fully sensitive and the number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 and > 4 antimicrobials for *Campylobacter* includes only resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin, gentamicin, and streptomycin.

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Samples from food animals were monitored for antimicrobial residues according to a randomized sampling scheme (BMGF-74320/0003-IV/B/7/2010, Rückstandsuntersuchung-Durchführungserlass 2007).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A project has been started to assess the appropriate method for collecting data on antimicrobial usage in animals. Results of this study are expected in 2011.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Nil

Notification system in place

No notification system for resistant isolates in place.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2010, 69 % (n = 16) *C. jejuni* isolated from broiler meat showed resistance to ciprofloxacin and 31 % to tetracycline; no resistance was found against erythromycin. In *C. coli* even higher resistance rates were observed (ciprofloxacin 79 %, tetracycline 67 %).

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)**Additional information**

C. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli* in animals

Sampling strategy used in monitoring**Frequency of the sampling**

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant campylobacter in broilers and cattle.

Type of specimen taken

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant campylobacter in broilers

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant campylobacter in broilers

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

Testing of all isolates will be performed in the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene in Graz. The randomized sampling plan was calculated to obtain approximately 170 thermotolerant *Campylobacter* isolates per animal species. If less than 170 isolates were obtained, all isolates were tested. If more than 170 thermotolerant *Campylobacter* were isolated 170 were randomly chosen.

Methods used for collecting data

All information concerning the tested animals, sampled slaughterhouses and results of the antimicrobial testing were entered and analysed in a Microsoft® Excel tables.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Described in chapter thermotolerant campylobacter in broilers.

Broth micro dilution susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter* spp. isolates was done using customised Sensititre® susceptibility micro titre plates (TREK Diagnostic Systems, Ltd., East Grinstead, West Sussex, and England). Briefly, *Campylobacter* spp. strains were subcultivated on Columbia blood agar and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerophilic atmosphere. Inocula from fresh cultures were prepared by suspension in physiological saline to obtain a turbidity equivalent to that of a McFarland standard 0.5. The suspension was added to Mueller Hinton bouillon for a final concentration of approximately 500,000 cfu/ml and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerophilic atmosphere. *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560 was used as control.

MIC values have been entered in a Microsoft® Excel datasheet.

The number of isolates that are fully sensitive and the number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 and > 4 antimicrobials for Campylobacter includes only resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin, gentamicin, and streptomycin.

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Samples from food animals were monitored for antimicrobial residues according to a randomized sampling scheme (BMGF-74320/0003-IV/B/7/2010, Rückstandsuntersuchung-Durchführungserlass 2007).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A project has been started to assess the appropriate method for collecting data on antimicrobial usage in animals. Results of this study are expected in 2011.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Nil

Notification system in place

No notification system for resistant isolates in place.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2010, *C. jejuni* isolated from broiler with the highest level of resistance remained for ciprofloxacin (49% in 2008 to 59% in 2009) at 56%. For tetracycline the resistance rates did not differ significantly in the last years (2008: 26%; 2009: 30%; 2010: 25%); similar trends could also be seen in isolates from humans; all isolates were sensitive for erythromycin as in 2008 and 2009.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Additional information

Table 43 Breakpoints used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni*, 2010

Test method used	Number of reporting laboratory	1
Disc diffusion		
E-test		
Agar dilution		
Broth dilution	x	

Standards used for testing	The methods are used for investigation of isolates from
CLSI	Feedingstuff
other	Animals x
EN ISO 20776-1	Food
	Humans x

<i>Campylobacter jejuni</i>	Standard for breakpoint (NCCLS,...)	Dilution method		
		Breakpoint Resistant >	Range tested concentration (µg/ml)	
			lowest	highest
Aminoglykosid AB				
Gentamicin	EFSA	> 1	0,125	16
Neomycin	EUCAST	> 1	0,125	8
Streptomycin	EFSA	> 2	0,5	32
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination				
Amoxicillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	CLSI	> 16	1	64
Quinolone und Quinoxalin				
Ciprofloxacin	EFSA	> 1	0,06	32
Nalidixinsäure	EUCAST	> 16	2	256
Makrolide				
Erythromycin	EFSA	> 4	0,25	128
Penicilline				
Ampicillin	EUCAST	> 8	0,5	64
Phenicole				
Chloramphenicol	EUCAST	> 16	2	64
Polymyxine				
Colistin	DANMAP	> 32	4	128
Tetracycline				
Tetracyclin	EFSA	> 2	0,125	64

Table 44 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in humans, quantitative data, 2010

<i>C. jejuni</i> human																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory																						
Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																						
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0,007	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512	
Aminoglykosid AB				n																		
Gentamicin	375	0	0						271	102	2											
Neomycin	375	0,27	1						23	209	139	3				1						
Streptomycin	375	1,33	5								323	45	2			4		1				
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																						
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	375	0	0									223	135	16	1							
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	375	62,9	236					38	86	11	2	2	1	4	91	93	25	22				
Nalidixinsäure	375	62,9	236										29	89	20	1	2	8	55	156	15	
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	375	0	0							31	133	165	40	6								
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	375	25,6	96								1	10	56	155	57	23	20	33	20			
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	375	0,27	1										245	87	28	14	1					
Polymyxine																						
Colistin	375	0	0											314	58	3						
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	375	24	90						78	136	42	20	9	2	1	2	13	19	53			

Table 45 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in broiler meat, quantitative data, 2010

<i>C. jejuni</i> broiler meat				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory																						
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0,007	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512	
Aminoglykosid AB				n																		
Gentamicin	16	0	0						7	8	1											
Neomycin	16	0	0							6	10											
Streptomycin	16	6,25	1								13	2						1				
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																						
Amoxicillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	16	0	0									14	1	1								
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	16	68,75	11				3	2							7	4						
Nalidixinsäure	16	43,75	7										6	3						5	2	
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	16	0	0							1	12	3										
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	16	50	8										3	5		1	3	3	1			
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	16	0	0										13	3								
Polymyxine																						
Colistin	16	0	0											15		1						
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	16	31,25	5					3	7	1									2	3		

Table 46 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in broiler flocks - at slaughter - quantitative data, 2010

<i>C. jejuni</i> Gallus gallus																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory																						
Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																						
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0,007	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512	
				n																		
Aminoglykosid AB																						
Gentamicin	134	0	0						79	53	2											
Neomycin	134	0	0						4	59	65	6										
Streptomycin	134	0	0								113	21										
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																						
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	134	0	0									84	47	3								
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	134	55,97	75					18	38	2	1			2	31	27	10	5				
Nalidixinsäure	134	52,99	71										19	35	8	1		1	21	42	7	
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	134	0	0								14	57	55	8								
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	134	26,12	35										3	28	53	15	5	9	18	3		
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	134	0	0											82	34	12	6					
Polymyxine																						
Colistin	134	0	0												118	14	2					
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	134	25,37	34						25	44	12	14	5		2		6	13	13			

Table 47 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in cattle, quantitative data, 2010

<i>C. jejuni</i> cattle																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0,007	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512	
Aminoglykosid AB				n																		
Gentamicin	159	0	0						111	48												
Neomycin	159	0	0						6	82	69	2										
Streptomycin	159	0,6289	1								136	22							1			
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																						
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	159	0	0									110	46	3								
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	159	38,994	62					34	54	7	1	1		1	27	22	8	4				
Nalidixinsäure	159	39,623	63										27	48	21			1	19	40	3	
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	159	0	0							14	54	73	17	1								
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	159	15,723	25								13	4	31	62	24	5	7	11	2			
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	159	0	0										102	42	12	3						
Polymyxine																						
Colistin	159	0	0											134	23	1	1					
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	159	13,208	21						40	63	24	8	3			1	3	3	14			

Table 48 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in humans, broiler meat, broiler slaughter batches and cattle (qualitative data), 2010

	<i>C. jejuni</i>											
	human	broiler meat	Gallus gallus	cattle								
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes	yes	yes	yes								
Number of isolates available in the laboratory												
Antimicrobials:	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%R	n
Aminoglykosid AB												
Gentamicin	375	0,0	0	16	0,0	0	134	0,0	0	159	0,0	0
Neomycin	375	0,3	1	16	0,0	0	134	0,0	0	159	0,0	0
Streptomycin	375	1,3	5	16	6,3	1	134	0,0	0	159	0,6	1
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination												
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	375	0,0	0	16	0,0	0	134	0,0	0	159	0,0	0
Quinolone und Quinoxalin												
Ciprofloxacin	375	62,9	236	16	68,8	11	134	56,0	75	159	39,0	62
Nalidixinsäure	375	62,9	236	16	43,8	7	134	53,0	71	159	39,6	63
Makrolide												
Erythromycin	375	0,0	0	16	0,0	0	134	0,0	0	159	0,0	0
Penicilline												
Ampicillin	375	25,6	96	16	50,0	8	134	26,1	35	159	15,7	25
Phenicole												
Chloramphenicol	375	0,3	1	16	0,0	0	134	0,0	0	159	0,0	0
Polymyxine												
Colistin	375	0,0	0	16	0,0	0	134	0,0	0	159	0,0	0
Tetracycline												
Tetracyclin	375	24,0	90	16	31,3	5	134	25,4	34	159	13,2	21
Number of multiresistant isolates												
fully sensitive	375	32,5	122	16	18,8	3	134	38,8	52	159	56,0	89
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	375	47,7	179	16	56,3	9	134	41,0	55	159	35,2	56
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	375	18,7	70	16	25,0	4	134	20,2	27	159	8,8	14
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	375	1,1	4	16	0,0	0	134	0,0	0	159	0,0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	375	0,0	0	16	0,0	0	134	0,0	0	159	0,0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	375	0,0	0	16	0,0	0	134	0,0	0	159	0,0	0

Number of multiresistant isolates: For *Campylobacter* this includes resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin, gentamicin, and streptomycin

Table 49 Breakpoints used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli*, 2010

Test method used	Number of reporting laboratory
Disc diffusion	1
E-test	
Agar dilution	
Broth dilution	

Standards used for testing	The methods are used for investigation of isolates from	
CLSI	Feedingstuff	
other	Animals	x
EN ISO 20776-1	Food	
	Humans	x

<i>Campylobacter coli</i>	Standard for breakpoint (NCCLS,...)	Dilution method		
		Breakpoint	Range tested	
			concentration (µg/ml)	
		Resistant >	lowest	highest
Aminoglykosid AB				
Gentamicin	EFSA	> 2	0,125	16
Neomycin	EUCAST	> 2	0,125	8
Streptomycin	EFSA	> 4	0,5	32
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination				
Amoxicillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	CLSI	> 16	1	64
Quinolone und Quinoxalin				
Ciprofloxacin	EFSA	> 1	0,06	32
Nalidixinsäure	EUCAST	> 32	2	256
Makrolide				
Erythromycin	EFSA	> 16	0,25	128
Penicilline				
Ampicillin	EUCAST	> 16	0,5	64
Phenicol				
Chloramphenicol	EUCAST	> 16	2	64
Polymyxine				
Colistin	DANMAP	> 32	4	128
Tetracycline				
Tetracyclin	EFSA	> 2	0,125	64

Table 50 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in humans quantitative data, 2010

<i>C. coli</i> human																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory																						
Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																						
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0,007	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512	
				n																		
Aminoglykosid AB																						
Gentamicin	53	0	0						6	43	4											
Neomycin	53	0	0							10	40	3										
Streptomycin	53	11,32	6								12	34		1	2	2	1	1				
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																						
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	53	0	0										10	32	10	1						
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	53	66,04	35				8	6	4					11	10	9	5					
Nalidixinsäure	53	66,04	35											9	7	2		1	26	8		
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	53	5,66	3							3	24	5	14	4								3
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	53	20,75	11											7	24	11	4	4	3			
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	53	0	0										10	29	14							
Polymyxine																						
Colistin	53	0	0											50	1	1	1					
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	53	37,74	20						8	15	4	5	1				2	4	14			

Table 51 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in broiler meat - quantitative data, 2010

<i>C. coli</i> broiler meat																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory																						
Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																						
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0,007	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512	
Aminoglykosid AB				n																		
Gentamicin	24	0	0						7	17												
Neomycin	24	0	0							10	12	2										
Streptomycin	24	33,33	8								8	8			1	5	2					
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																						
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	24	0	0									4	11	6	2	1						
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	24	79,17	19					3	2					4	11	3	1					
Nalidixinsäure	24	79,17	19											4	1					14	5	
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	24	0	0							2	7	6	8	1								
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	24	25	6										1	9	4	4	3	2	1			
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	24	0	0										10	12	2							
Polymyxine																						
Colistin	24	0	0											20	3	1						
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	24	66,67	16						5	2	1								1	15		

Table 52 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in broiler slaughter batches - quantitative data, 2010

<i>C. coli</i> <i>Gallus gallus</i>																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory																						
Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																						
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0,007	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512	
				n																		
Aminoglykosid AB																						
Gentamicin	46	0	0						9	34	3											
Neomycin	46	0	0						9	34	3											
Streptomycin	46	10,87	5							14	27				1	1	2	1				
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																						
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	46	0	0									7	20	14	3	2						
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	46	80,43	37					5	3	1			2	8	13	11	3					
Nalidixinsäure	46	80,43	37											7	2			1	25	11		
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	46	8,696	4							6	9	7	17	3							4	
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	46	10,87	5										2	19	17	3		2	3			
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	46	0	0										11	25	10							
Polymyxine																						
Colistin	46	0	0											46								
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	46	52,17	24						10	5	4	1	2			1		2	21			

Table 53 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in cattle - quantitative data, 2010

<i>C. coli</i> cattle																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0,007	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512	
Aminoglykosid AB				n																		
Gentamicin	10	0	0						2	6	2											
Neomycin	10	0	0							2	6	2										
Streptomycin	10	40	4								2	3	1			1	2	1				
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																						
Amoxicillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	10	0	0										4	6								
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	10	50	5					2	3					1	2	2						
Nalidixinsäure	10	50	5											1	4				1	4		
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	10	0	0								1	3	2	3	1							
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	10	0	0										1	2	4	3						
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	10	0	0										2	3	4	1						
Polymyxine																						
Colistin	10	0	0											10								
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	10	70	7							2		1								7		

Table 54 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in humans, broiler meat, broiler slaughter batches and cattle - qualitative data, 2010

	C. coli											
	human			broiler meat			Gallus gallus			cattle		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory												
Antimicrobials:	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%R	n
Aminoglykosid AB												
Gentamicin	53	0,0	0	24	0,0	0	46	0,0	0	10	0,0	0
Neomycin	53	0,0	0	24	0,0	0	46	0,0	0	10	0,0	0
Streptomycin	53	11,3	6	24	33,3	8	46	10,9	5	10	40,0	4
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination												
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	53	0,0	0	24	0,0	0	46	0,0	0	10	0,0	0
Quinolone und Quinoxalin												
Ciprofloxacin	53	66,0	35	24	79,2	19	46	80,4	37	10	50,0	5
Nalidixinsäure	53	66,0	35	24	79,2	19	46	80,4	37	10	50,0	5
Makrolide												
Erythromycin	53	5,7	3	24	0,0	0	46	8,7	4	10	0,0	0
Penicilline												
Ampicillin	53	20,8	11	24	25,0	6	46	10,9	5	10	0,0	0
Phenicol												
Chloramphenicol	53	0,0	0	24	0,0	0	46	0,0	0	10	0,0	0
Polymyxine												
Colistin	53	0,0	0	24	0,0	0	46	0,0	0	10	0,0	0
Tetracycline												
Tetracyclin	53	37,7	20	24	66,7	16	46	52,2	24	10	70,0	7
Number of multiresistant isolates												
fully sensitive	53	22,6	12	24	16,7	4	46	13,0	6	10	10,0	1
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	53	43,4	23	24	16,7	4	46	32,6	15	10	30,0	3
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	53	24,5	13	24	37,5	9	46	45,7	21	10	50,0	5
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	53	9,4	5	24	29,2	7	46	6,5	3	10	10,0	1
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	53	0,0	0	24	0,0	0	46	2,2	1	10	0,0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	53	0,0	0	24	0,0	0	46	0,0	0	10	0,0	0

Number of multiresistant isolates: For *Campylobacter* this includes resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin, gentamicin, and streptomycin

4.3. Listeriosis

4.3.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Listeriosis can be regarded as a relatively rare infectious disease in Austria with an annual incidence between 0.1 and 0.25 cases per 100,000 inhabitants in the years 1996 to 2007. In 2008 a total of 31 culturally verified human cases of listeriosis were recorded for Austria (incidence 0.38 per 100,000 inhabitants), four of them were associated with pregnancy. In 2009 a further increase had to be assessed, 46 cases what corresponds to an incidence of 0.6. Two cases were associated with pregnancy. In 2010, a reduction to 34 cases (incidence of 0.41) could be observed. The incidences are similar to those of most other western European countries (0.2-0.9). Lethality reduced in 2010 to 12% (4 cases) compared with 26% in 2009. This (usually) high rate and the sometimes severe permanent disabilities demand every effort to ascertain potential food-associated outbreaks as early as possible.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease.

The number of listeriosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of cases reported to the Epidemiological Reporting System and the National Reference Laboratory for Listeriosis, n = 34.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Listeriosis is a rare disease, but not a rare bacterium, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, including pregnancy and immunosuppression.

Although dairy products and salmon are likely candidates, the source of an infection often remains unclear. Ready-to-eat meat and meat products harbour listeria in 0–7 % and ready-to-eat smoked fish in approx. 10 - 17 %.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A monthly report is sent to the Ministry of Health by the National Reference Center, whereas outbreaks are reported immediately.

Restrictions tightened to sell unpasteurised milk in remote areas (Alps).

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

More widespread information for pregnant and immunocompromised persons should be provided.

Additional information

If zoonotic agents, which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.3.2. Listeriosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

A monthly report is sent to the Ministry of Health by the National Reference Center, whereas outbreaks are reported immediately.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following three symptoms:

- Listeriosis of newborns defined as Stillbirth or at least one of the following five in the first month of life:
 - Granulomatosis infantiseptica
 - Meningitis or meningoencephalitis
 - Septicaemia
 - Dyspnoea
 - Lesions on skin, mucosal membranes or conjunctivae
- Listeriosis in pregnancy defined as at least one of the following three:
 - Abortion, miscarriage, stillbirth or premature birth
 - Fever
 - Influenza-like symptoms
- Other form of listeriosis defined as at least one of the following four:
 - Fever
 - Meningitis or meningoencephalitis
 - Septicaemia
 - Localised infections such as arthritis, endocarditis, and abscesses

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following two:

- Isolation of *Listeria monocytogenes* from a normally sterile site
- Isolation of *Listeria monocytogenes* from a normally non-sterile site in a foetus, stillborn, newborn or the mother at or within 24 hours of birth

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the laboratory criteria
- or
- Any mother with a laboratory confirmed listeriosis infection in her foetus, stillborn or newborn

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriology: Smears of the samples are Gram stained. Specimen from normally sterile sites are inoculated in blood culture broth or thioglycollate broth and Columbia blood agar plates, vaginal swabs are plated only directly on Columbia blood and colistin-nalidixic acid (CNA) agar. *L. monocytogenes* is identified by catalase and Api Listeria test.

Stool samples were examined after cold enrichment in Fraser enrichment broth and streaked onto selective chromogenic agar plate and Columbia blood-agar. All isolates obtained in Austria are sent to the National Reference Center for confirmation, subtyping by PCR and PFGE and comparison.

Notification system in place

Notification of listeriosis according to the Federeal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

History of the disease in chapter general evaluation.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

History of the disease

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Listeriosis is a rare disease, but not a rare bacterium, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, including pregnancy and immunosuppression. Although dairy products and salmon are likely candidates, the source of an infection often remains unclear.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria.

Annual report of the National Reference Centre:

http://bmg.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/7/2/8/CH1305/CMS1299588312999/jb_listeriose_2010_final.pdf (as of 9.05.2011).

Provisionally yearly report published on the Website of the MOH

Table 55 Listeriosis in humans - species/serotype distribution, 2010

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population
Listeriosis	34	0.41
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2a</i>	19	0.23
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2b</i>	4	0.05
<i>L. monocytogenes 4b</i>	10	0.12
<i>L. monocytogenes 1/2c</i>	1	0.01
Deaths	4	0.05
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2a</i>	2	0.02
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2b</i>	2	0.02
Congenital cases	3	0.04

Data source: Epidemiological Reporting System, National Reference Laboratory as 13th May 2011

Table 56 Listeriosis in humans - age distribution, 2010

Age group	Listeriosis			L. monocytogenes 1,2a			L. monocytogenes 1,2b			L. monocytogenes 4b			L. monocytogenes 1/2c		
	all	male	female	all	male	female	all	male	female	all	male	female	all	male	female
< 1 year	3	1	2	1	-	1	-	-	-	2	1	1	-	-	-
1 to 4 years	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5 to 14 years	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15 to 24 years	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-
25 to 44 years *	1	-	1	1	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
45 to 64 years	3	2	1	1	1	-	1	1	-	1	-	1	-	-	-
65 years and older	26	18	8	16	11	5	3	3	-	6	3	3	1	1	-
Age unknown	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
All age groups	34	22	12	19	12	7	4	4	0	10	5	5	1	1	0

* Actually there were 2 patients, but according to mother-child definition for pregnant woman = 1 case

Data source: Epidemiological Reporting System, National Reference Laboratory as 13th May 2011

4.3.3. *Listeria* spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2009 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2008“ (BMGFJ – 75500/0332-IV/B/7/2008) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2007-2010) according to Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes, etc.

In 2010, approximately 35,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 75 % of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2010, seven food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2010 BMG-75500/0246-II/B/7/2009). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used at the production plant or at retail

Qualitative detection of *Listeria* spp. is performed according to ISO 11290: Part 1 (1996).

Quantification of *Listeria* spp. content in food is conducted either according to ISO 11290: Part 2 (1998) with following modifications: *Listeria monocytogenes* are confirmed on Ottaviani Agosti Agar, ALOA Agar, RapidLmono agar, using Gram stain, motility testing and catalase production or by the Api *Listeria* test or Vidas LMO II.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

Listeria monocytogenes was not detected in samples of pasteurised cows' milk (0/51). Within the 30 samples of raw cows' milk only 1 sample was found positive for *L. monocytogenes* (3%), 1-time *L. monocytogenes* presence in 25g. Also in 7 of 355 ready-to-eat pig meat product samples (2%) *L. monocytogenes* was found and 15 out of 256 samples (6%) of meat products from bovine animals, cooked, ready-to-eat chilled were found positive in 25g.

In 3 out of 66 samples (5%) of mixed meat products, fermented sausages (campaign A-802-10) *L. monocytogenes* was found (3-times <100 cfu/g), additionally one-time *L. innocua* and *L. welshimeri* respectively.

11.9 % of all samples from fishery products (54/454) revealed a contamination with *L. monocytogenes* (2 of them <100 cfu/g, 4 of them >100 cfu/g). 2 of 14 raw fish samples (14.3%) were positive for *L. monocytogenes*, both times *L. monocytogenes* was qualitatively found in 25g.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs; a folder was created by the AGES in cooperation with the Austrian Medical Chamber: Pregnancy – infections transmitted via food (Schwangerschaft – Infektionen

durch Nahrungsmittel, http://www.ages.at/uploads/media/AGES_Folder_Schwangerschaft_Web.pdf). This folder was distributed to all gynaecologists. The folder contains advices to prevent food-borne infections during pregnancy, including listeriosis, toxoplasmosis, campylobacteriosis and salmonellosis as well as mycotoxicosis.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-802-10: Listeria in food – Meat - mixed meat – meat products – fermented sausages - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: November – December

Type of specimen taken

Mixed meat products – fermented sausages

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Listeria in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

66 samples tested for Listeria monocytogenes: 3 samples positive in 25 g (all <10 CFU/g), 1 x L. innocua, 1 x L. welshimeri

Additional information

Samples were also tested for VTEC and Salmonella spp.

Campaign A-801-10: Listeria in food – Meat - mixed meat products cooked – ready-to-eat chilled - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: August - October

Type of specimen taken

Mixed meat products cooked – ready-to-eat chilled

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Listeria in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

99 samples tested for Listeria: 3 samples positive in 25 g (all <10 CFU/g), 1 x L. innocua

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Salmonella spp.

Table 57 *Listeria monocytogenes* in milk and milky products, 2010

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sampling weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in 25g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> ; > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g
Cheeses made from cows' milk - curd	at farm	single	25g	2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	17	0	16	0	11	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	10	0	10	0	2	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	11	0	11	0	4	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	6	0	6	0	4	0	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	2	0	2	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at farm	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	0	3	0	2	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	407	3	407	3	386	0	3
	at catering	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	16	0	16	0	7	0	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	at smpling stage	single	25g	11	0	11	0	3	0	0
	at catering	single	25g	3	1	3	1	3	1	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	102	1	102	1	44	0	0
	at retail	single	25g	75	0	73	0	43	0	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	39	0	38	0	33	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft - Survey - EU baseline survey (Campaign A 800-10)	at retail	single	25g	63	0	63	0	63	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	53	1	53	1	46	0	0
	at catering	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	18	0	18	0	3	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk	at smpling stage	single	25g	20	0	20	0	0	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	4	0	4	0	3	0	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	4	0	4	0	0	0	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified	at catering	single	25g	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
	at processing plant	single	25g	2	0	2	0	0	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	6	0	5	0	6	0	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	7	1	7	1	7	1	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at catering	single	25g	2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	7	0	7	0	2	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	17	0	16	0	16	0	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	5	0	5	0	5	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sampling weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method <i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in 25g	Units tested with enumeration method <i>L. monocytogenes</i> ; > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > 100 cfu/g
Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft milk	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft milk - made from pasteurised milk	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft milk - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	8	0	8	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	9	0	9	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	6	0	6	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	4	0	4	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail - imported	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - unspecified	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	6	0	6	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	6	0	6	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	at retail - imported	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	12	0	12	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	11	0	11	0	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	9	0	9	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk	at farm	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - curd	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	4	0	4	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - fresh	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	6	0	6	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	0	3	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses)	at retail	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sampling weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method <i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in 25g	Units tested with enumeration method <i>L. monocytogenes</i> ; > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > 100 cfu/g
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter	at catering	single	25g	2	1	2	1	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	11	0	11	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	31	0	31	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products	at farm	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	3	0	3	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	1	3	1	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	54	0	54	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	54	0	54	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	9	0	9	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - sour milk	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - probiotics drinks	at retail - imported	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy desserts chilled	at retail - imported	single	25g	23	0	23	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream	at catering - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	4	0	4	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	0	3	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified	at catering	single	25g	15	0	15	0	0
	at farm	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
	at processing plant	single	25g	23	0	23	0	0
	at retail	single	25g	12	0	12	0	0
Milk from other animal species or unspecified	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - pasteurised	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	0
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - raw	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	0
Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	28	0	28	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	22	0	22	0	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw	at catering	single	25g	3	0	3	0	0
	at farm	single	25g	8	0	8	0	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	at catering	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
	at farm	single	25g	1	1	1	1	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	8	0	8	0	0
	at retail	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw - intended for direct human consumption	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	0	3	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
Milk, goats' - raw	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
Milk, sheep's - raw	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0

Table 58 *Listeria monocytogenes* in other foods, 2010

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sampling weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in 25g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> ; > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g	<i>L. innocua</i>	<i>L. welshimeri</i>
Meat from pig - fresh	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0	0	0		
Meat from pig - fresh, chilled	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0	0	0		
Meat from pig - meat products - pate	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	0	0	0		
Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	4	0	4	0	4	0	0		
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	6	0	6	0	6	0	0		
	at retail - imported	single	25g	2	1	2	1	2	0	0		
Meat from pig - meat products - raw, ham	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	5	0	5	0	0	0	0		
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ham sliced	at catering	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0	0	0		
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	348	7	348	7	347	0	0		
	at catering	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	2	0	0		
	at retail - imported	single	25g	4	0	2	0	4	0	0		
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	2	0	0		
Meat from deer (venison) - meat preparation	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0	0	0		
Meat from deer (venison) - meat products	at catering	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
	at game handling establishment	single	25g	3	0	3	0	3	0	0		
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	4	0	4	0	2	0	0		
	at retail - imported	single	25g	4	0	2	0	4	0	0		
Meat from bovine animals - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat chilled	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	256	15	256	15	255	0	0		
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	7	0	5	0	6	0	0		
	at retail - imported	single	25g	4	0	4	0	1	0	0		
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	2	0	0		
	at retail - imported	single	25g	4	1	4	1	3	0	0		
Meat from turkey - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat chilled	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	0	0	0		
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	0	3	0	3	0	0		
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0	0	0		
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	3	0	3	0	0	0	0		
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	10	0	10	0	0	0	0		
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	3	0	3	0	0	0	0		
	at retail	single	25g	11	0	11	0	0	0	0		
	at retail - imported	single	25g	2	0	2	0	0	0	0		
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at catering	single	25g	8	1	8	1	8	0	0		
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	9	1	9	1	9	0	0		
	at retail	single	25g	25	1	23	1	25	0	0		
	at retail - imported	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages	at catering	single	25g	3	0	3	0	3	0	0		
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	20	3	20	3	16	0	0		

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sampling weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in 25g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> ; > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g	<i>L. innocua</i>	<i>L. welshimeri</i>
	at retail	single	25g	39	2	39	2	33	0	0		
	at retail - imported	single	25g	8	0	8	0	7	0	0		
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	2	0	0		
Meat from other animal species or not specified	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at catering	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	18	3	18	3	18	0	0		
Meat, mixed meat - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked chilled	at catering	single	25g	2	0	2	0	0	0	0		
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked chilled	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0	0	0		
Meat, mixed meat - meat products - fermented sausages	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	13	0	13	0	0	0	0		
Meat, mixed meat - meat products - fermented sausages (campaign A-802-10)	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	66	3	66	3	66	0	0	1	1
Meat, mixed meat products cooked - ready-to-eat chilled (campaign A-801-10)	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	99	3	99	3	99	1	0	1	
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - heat treated, ready to eat - Survey - EU baseline survey (campaign A-800-10)	at retail	single	25g	58	1	58	1	58	1	0		
Fishery products - unspecified - seafood pate	at catering	single	25g	2	0	2	0	0	0	0		
Fishery products - smoked fish	at retail - imported	single	25g	123	23	122	23	118	0	0		
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	20	1	20	1	20	0	0		
Fishery products - unspecified, ready-to-eat chilled	at catering	single	25g	17	1	17	1	1	0	0		
Fishery products, unspecified	at catering	single	25g	5	1	5	1	5	0	0		
	at processing plant	single	25g	4	0	4	0	4	0	0		
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	18	9	18	9	18	0	0		
	at retail	single	25g	14	2	14	2	14	1	1		
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	40	3	40	3	32	0	2		
	at retail - imported	single	25g	89	12	86	12	88	1	1		
Fishery products - unspecified, ready-to-eat - Survey - EU baseline survey - after sample collection at retail level (campaign A-800-10)	at retail	single	25g	61	2	61	2	61	0	0		
Fishery products - unspecified, ready-to-eat - Survey - EU baseline survey - at the end of shelf-life (campaign A-800-10)	at retail	single	25g	61	0	61	0	61	0	0		
Fish - raw	at catering	single	25g	2	1	2	1	2	0	0		
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
	at retail	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	1	3	1	3	0	0		
	at retail - imported	single	25g	3	0	3	0	3	0	0		
Fish raw chilled	at catering	single	25g	4	0	4	0	3	0	0		
Juice fruit juice - unpasteurised	at retail - imported	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0	0	0		
Fruits products - fruit purée	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	0	3	0	0	0	0		
Bakery products - cakes	at catering	single	25g	8	0	8	0	8	0	0		
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	4	0	4	0	4	0	0		
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	51	1	51	1	39	0	0		

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sampling weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in 25g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> ; > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g	<i>L. innocua</i>	<i>L. welshimeri</i>
	at retail - imported	single	25g	5	0	5	0	5	0	0		
Bakery products cakes containing heat-treated cream	at catering	single	25g	7	0	7	0	0	0	0		
Bakery products desserts containing raw eggs	at catering	single	25g	2	0	2	0	0	0	0		
Bakery products - pastry	at catering	single	25g	11	0	11	0	11	0	0		
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	14	0	14	0	13	0	0		
	at retail	single	25g	2	0	2	0	1	0	0		
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	64	0	64	0	50	0	0		
Bakery products pastry with egg filling	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
Sauce and dressings mayonnaise	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	6	0	5	0	2	0	0		
Crustaceans	at retail	single	25g	2	0	1	0	2	0	0		
	at retail - imported	single	25g	5	0	5	0	0	0	0		
Ready-to-eat salads	at catering	single	25g	21	0	21	0	21	0	0		
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	3	0	3	0	2	0	0		
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	5	0	5	0	3	0	0		
Ready-to-eat salads containing mayonnaise	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	11	0	11	0	0	0	0		
Vegetables	at catering	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	9	0	9	0	9	0	0		
	at retail - imported	single	25g	8	0	8	0	8	0	0		
Vegetables - products	at retail	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	2	0	0		
	at retail - imported	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
Vegetables pre-cut ready-to-eat	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	11	0	6	0	5	0	0		
Infant formula	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0	0	0		
Other food	at catering	single	25g	4	0	4	0	4	0	0		
	at farm	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	1	0	0		
	at retail	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	7	0	6	0	1	0	0		
	at retail - imported	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
Other food - products and prepared dishes - noodles	at catering	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0	0	0		
Other food - products and prepared dishes - unspecified - non-ready-to-eat foods - chilled	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	0	3	0	0	0	0		
Other processed food products and prepared dishes	at catering	single	25g	12	0	11	0	11	0	0		
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	5	0	5	0	5	0	0		
	at retail	single	25g	11	0	11	0	8	0	0		
	at retail - imported	single	25g	2	0	2	0	1	0	0		
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - ices and similar frozen desserts		single	25g	28	0	28	0	0	0	0		
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - sushi	at catering	single	25g	2	0	0	0	2	0	0		
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta	at catering	single	25g	5	0	5	0	0	0	0		

4.3.4. Listeria spp. in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

There is no active surveillance system and detection of cases is based on clinical observations.

Frequency of the sampling

When there is a suspected case of invasive listeriosis.

Case definition

A case may be defined with positive histopathology and/or positive bacteriology. The animal is the epidemiological unit.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The diagnostic methods used include histopathology and bacteriology.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None

Notification system in place

No notification system of listeriosis in animal species available at this time.

Results of the investigation

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

No relevance because products of sick animals are not used for human consumption.

Table 59 *Listeria* spp. in animals, 2010

animal species	sampling stage	sampling context	Source of information	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Listeria</i> spp.	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	<i>Listeria ivanovii</i>	<i>Listeria</i> sp., unspecified
hare	at farm - animal sample - organ	clinical investigation	AGES IVET	2	2	2		
deer	at farm - animal sample - organ	clinical investigation	AGES IVET	1	0			
cattle	at farm - animal sample - blood	clinical investigation	AGES IVET	1	0			
	at farm - animal sample - feces	clinical investigation	AGES IVET	2	1	1		
	at farm - animal sample - feed	clinical investigation	AGES IVET	1	0			
	at farm - animal sample - meat swab	clinical investigation	AGES IVET	3	0			
	at farm - animal sample - organ	clinical investigation	AGES IVET	22	18	17		1
sheep	at farm - animal sample - feed	clinical investigation	AGES IVET	1	0			
	at farm - animal sample - organ	clinical investigation	AGES IVET	19	11	9	1	1
pig	at farm - animal sample - meat swab	clinical investigation	AGES IVET	8	0			
goat	at farm - animal sample - organ	clinical investigation	AGES IVET	10	5	5		

AGES IVET: AGES Institutes for Veterinary Disease Control

4.4. Verotoxic Escherichia coli

4.4.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2010, 730 samples were investigated at the National Reference Centre for Escherichia coli including verotoxin producing E. coli. 456 human, 36 food 145 isolates from the National Zoonosis Monitoring in animals 2010 were analyzed. From the 36 food samples 30 isolates were gained. From the human samples 88 verotoxin producing isolates could be confirmed, including 31 verotoxin producing E. coli (VTEC) and 57 enterohemorrhagic E. coli (EHEC = VTEC plus eae-gene). The ratio of human EHEC O157 (11 isolates) to VTEC/EHEC non O157 (77 isolates) differed from that of previous years (e.g. in 2009: 30 EHEC O157 versus 63 VTEC/EHEC non O157). A clear shift towards VTEC/EHEC non O157 can be seen. In 2010 EHEC O26 was confirmed in 16 cases, and for the first time it was more prevalent than serotype O157. Eleven cases of hemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS) were diagnosed as post infectious complication. The incidence of HUS in children (< 14 years) due to VTEC/EHEC was 0.53 HUS cases per 100.000 children in 2010. There were eight smaller family outbreaks and one province-crossing foodborne outbreak, with seven cases due to VTEC O174:H2.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease

The number of VTEC cases presented in this report reflects the number of cases reported to the Epidemiological Reporting System and the National Reference Laboratory for VTEC, n = 87.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

The prevalence of verotoxin producing E. coli isolated from cattle increased to 29 % and from sheep to 65 %, but we hypothesize that this is due to a higher sensitivity of the new ELISA, the sampling material (rectum-anal swabs) and improvement in the VTEC isolation techniques (see chapter Pathogenic Escherichia coli in animals). Concerning the 5 most important VTEC serotypes for humans (O157, O26, O103, O111 and O145), only O157 (2 x) and O103 (2 x) were isolated from cattle.

According to the EFSA definition of VTEC (“a VTEC positive sample is considered to be any sample, from which at least one E. coli strain containing vtx and eae has been isolated. Both gene-groups must be present in the isolated E. coli strain, for a sample to be positive”) only in 8 samples VTEC were isolated from cattle (6 %) and none from sheep (0 %).

The relevance of findings of VTEC in faeces seems to be low because VTEC are found only in a very low prevalence on meat samples from bovines and sheep.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

An Austrian wide monitoring program on the trends of VTEC prevalence in bovine animals and sheep was implemented according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 17 November 2003 in the National Orders. The sampling was carried out throughout 2010 and follow up programs will be implemented in the forthcoming years. Also in food products of wild animals surveillance programs were conducted (see Campaign A-802-10 and A-803-10).

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Increased awareness and information should be made available for parents, paediatricians and general practitioners in regard to food safety and the prevention of infection.

Additional information

If zoonotic agents, which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.4.2. Verocytotoxic Escherichia coli in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The National Reference Center provides a quarterly report discussing recent outbreaks to the Ministry of Health.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

STEC/VTEC diarrhoea

Any person with at least one of the following two symptoms:

- Diarrhoea
- Abdominal pain

HUS

Any person with acute renal failure and at least one of the following two:

- Microangiopathic haemolytic anaemia
- Thrombocytopenia

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following three:

- Isolation of Shigatoxin/Verotoxin (STEC/VTEC) producing E. coli
- Detection of stx1 or stx2 gene(s) nucleic acid
- Detection of free shigatoxins.

Only for HUS the following can be used as laboratory criterion to confirm STEC/VTEC:

- E. coli serogroups specific antibody response

Isolation and additional characterisation by serotype, phage type, eae genes, and subtypes of stx1/stx2 should be performed if possible

Case classification

Possible case of STEC-associated HUS

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria for HUS

Probable case of STEC/VTEC

• Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link or a laboratory confirmed case without clinical criteria

Confirmed case of STEC/VTEC

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

1. Detection of E. coli O157 (most prominent serotype in HUS cases):

- Bacteriology: Isolation of O157 colonies on Sorbitol-MacConkey agar after incubation for 24 hours at 37 °C. O157 is confirmed via the E. coli O157 Latex Test.

- Serology: This method is constantly used at the German HUS-"Konsiliarlabor"; anti-O157 antibodies of IgG and IgM types can be distinguished.

2. Detection of Verotoxin (VTEC)-producing strains (used at the National Reference Center for EHEC/VTEC/STEC in Innsbruck): Stools are enriched overnight in a medium containing mitomycin C (EHEC Direct Medium, Heipha, Heidelberg, Germany). Enriched cultures are investigated for

presence of Shiga toxins by commercial EIA (e.g. Premier, Novitec). Isolate identification is further confirmed by conventional biochemical tests (API 20 E, bioMerieux, Marcy-l'Etoile, France). Enrichments are plated on Sorbitol-MacConkey agar and incubated for 24 hours at 37 °C. Detection of stx1 and stx2 genes and of the genes encoding EHEC hemolysin (hlyA) and intimin (eae) is done by PCR (Gerber et al. (2002) J Infect Dis 186:493-500).

All EHEC/STEC/VTEC isolates obtained in Austria are to be sent to the National Reference Center for confirmation, subtyping and comparison. All Shiga toxin producing E. coli are serotyped with E. coli antisera (E. coli antisera, Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark). Comparison of the isolates is done by Pulsed-Field-Gel-Electrophoresis and Ribotyping.

Notification system in place

Notification of VTEC according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

See History of the disease

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease

Relevance as a zoonotic disease

HUS is a rare complication of E. coli infection; however EHECs themselves are not rare, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, most of which are currently unknown. Although raw or undercooked meat and unpasteurised dairy products are likely candidates to transfer the bacterium to humans, the actual source of infection often remains unclear. The importance of hand hygiene after animal contact should be always considered.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria.

Annual Report of the National Reference Laboratory for VTEC 2010:

http://bmg.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/2/9/2/CH1305/CMS1299590882763/jb_vtec_2010_endguel tig.pdf (as of 9.05.2011)

Provisionally yearly report published on the Website of the MOH

Table 60 Verocytotoxic Escherichia coli infections in human - species/serotype distribution, 2010

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases
HUS	11*	0,13	n.a.	n.a.
- clinical cases	11*	0,13	n.a.	n.a.
- lab. confirmed cases	10	0,12	n.a.	n.a.
- caused by O157 (VT+)	2	0,02	n.a.	n.a.
- caused by other VTEC	8	0,10	n.a.	n.a.
E.coli infect. (except HUS)	77	0,93	n.a.	n.a.
- clinical cases	77	0,93	n.a.	n.a.
- laboratory confirmed	77	0,93	n.a.	n.a.

* in one patient's stool only the stx2 gene was detected, culture was negative, serology was negative

Data source: Epidemiological Reporting System, National Reference Laboratory as 13th May 2011

Table 61 Verocytotoxic *Escherichia coli* infections in human - age distribution, 2010

Age group	HUS			<i>E. coli</i> infections (except HUS)		
	all	male	female	all	male	female
< 1 year	2	1*	1	11	4	7
1 to 4 years	4	2	2	32	13	19
5 to 14 years	1	0	1	18	13	5
15 to 24 years	0	0	0	1	0	1
25 to 44 years	0	0	0	7	5	2
45 to 64 years	2	1	1	5	1	4
65 years and older	2	1	1	3	2	1
Age unknown	0	0	0	0	0	0
All age groups	11	5	6	77	38	39

* in one patient's stool only the stx2 gene was detected, culture was negative, serology was negative

Data source: Epidemiological Reporting System, National Reference Laboratory as 13th May 2011

4.4.3. Pathogenic *Escherichia coli* in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2009 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2008“ (BMGFJ – 75500/0332-IV/B/7/2008) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2007-2010) according to Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2010, approximately 35,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 75 % of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2010, seven food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2010 BMG-75500/0246-II/B/7/2009). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

25 g of the sample is pre-enriched using modified tryptic soy broth containing novobiocin (mTSB + n) for 24h at 37 °C. Subsequently about 1 microliter is plated on trypton-bile-glucuronid (TBX) for 24h at 37 °C. 5 colonies per plate are identified as *E. coli* (indole positive, glucuronidase positive or using

enterotube. E. coli are tested in a multiplex PCR for stx1 and stx2 (Brian et al, 1992. Polymerase chain reaction for diagnosis of enterohemorrhagic Escherichia coli infection and haemolytic-uremic syndrome. J Clin Microbiol 30, 1801-06).

The typing for virulence factors as the eae-gene and serotyping is carried out by the National Reference Laboratory for VTEC in the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-802-10: VTEC in food - Meat - mixed meat – meat products – fermented sausages - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: November – December

Type of specimen taken

Mixed meat products – fermented sausages

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of VTEC in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

66 samples tested, VTEC: 1-times positive (non-O157)

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Salmonella spp. and Listeria monocytogenes

Campaign A-803-10: VTEC in food - Meat from farmed game – land mammals fresh chilled - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: September - November

Type of specimen taken

Meat from farmed game – land mammals fresh chilled

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of VTEC in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

30 samples tested, VTEC: 2-times positive (ONT:H30, Orough-H28)

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Salmonella spp., Campylobacter and Clostridium difficile

Table 62 Verocytotoxic Escherichia coli in food, 2010

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for VTEC	VTEC O100:HNM; stx1-, stx2+, eae-, Ehly-	VTEC O69:HNM; stx1-, stx2+, eae-	VTEC O157:H7; stx1-, stx2+, eae-	VTEC non-O157	VTEC O157:H7; stx1-, stx2+, eae-	VTEC O157:H7; stx1-, stx2+, eae-
Cheeses made from cows' milk - curd	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	1							
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	1							
		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2							
Cheeses made from goats' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	1							
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	1							
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	1							
		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	1							
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	1							
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
Fishery products, unspecified	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
Meat from bovine animals - fresh	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	3	1		1				
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	4							
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	3							
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2							
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
Meat from deer (venison) - meat preparation	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	8							
	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
Meat from deer (venison) - meat products	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
	at game handling establishment	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2							
Meat from farmed game - land mammals fresh chilled (campaign A-803-10)	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	4							
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	30	2				1	1	
Meat from other animal species or not specified	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	3							
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	3							
Meat from sheep - fresh	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
Meat from sheep - meat preparation	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	5							
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	33							
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	66	1				1		
Meat, mixed meat - meat products - fermented sausages (campaign A-802-10)	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	4	1	1					
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	8							
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos)	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2							
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2							
	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos)	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	16							
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	16							

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for VTEC	VTEC O100:HNM; stx1-, stx2+, eae-, Ehly-	VTEC O69:HNM; stx1-, stx2+, eae-	VTEC OMT:HNT; stx1-, stx2+, eae-	VTEC non-O157	VTEC OMT:H30; stx1-, stx2+, eae-	VTEC Orough:H28; stx1-, stx2+, eae-
meat products - fermented sausages	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	4							
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	11,09g	1							
		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	24	1			1			
	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	3							
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - raw	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2							
Milk, cows' - raw	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
	at farm	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	3							
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2							
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2							
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
	at farm	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	7							
	at retail	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
Milk, goats' - raw	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	3							
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
Milk, sheep's - raw	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1							
Other processed food products and prepared dishes	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	1							
		Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2							

4.4.4. Pathogenic Escherichia coli in animals

A. Verotoxigenic Escherichia coli in cattle (bovine animals)

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

The monitoring program on the prevalence of VTEC in slaughtered cattle was continued. The sampling was stratified based on the number of processed animals per abattoir in Austria. The date of sampling was randomized over the year 2010. Sampling was performed in the 37 abattoirs which processed more than 80 % of Austria's cattle in 2009.

Frequency of the sampling

Animals at slaughter

The sampling was distributed randomly over the period of the study from January to December 2010.

Type of specimen taken

Animals at slaughter

A part of the intestine containing rectum and anus.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Animals at slaughter

The sampling is performed by qualified veterinarians who carry out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration, a part of rectum and anus was sampled. After cooling down to 4 °C, the sample had been sent to the AGES Institute of Veterinary Diseases Control (IVET) in Graz the same day, in a hobbox or polystyrene box along with cooling packs. In the laboratory, a swab from the rectum-anal mucosa was incubated in a broth.

Case definition

Animals at slaughter

An animal is considered to be infected with VTEC following the isolation of VTEC (verotoxin producing E. coli irrespective of intimin) from its recto-anal mucosa.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Animals at slaughter

In a first step the samples were screened for presence of verotoxins by ELISA, secondly the positive samples were processed for VTEC isolation.

At first the swab was pre-enriched using modified tryptic soy broth containing novobiocin (mTSB + n) for 5 hours at 37 °C on a shaker. Then 1 ml of each pre-enrichment was inoculated into mTSB + n containing mitomycin C for 18-20 hours at 37 °C on a shaker too. The process was followed by testing the enrichment for the occurrence of verotoxin in an enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA, Premier TM EHEC). Positive enrichments were plated on MacConkey (MAC) -, on cefixime tellurite sorbitol MAC (CTSMAC) - and on enterohemolysin agar and incubated for 24 hours at 37 °C. 2-4 colonies from each of the plates were subcultured on MAC as well as on CTSMAC. Afterwards the genomes of subcultured E. coli were investigated in a real time PCR for harboring the genes for Verotoxin 1, Verotoxin 2, Intimin and Enterohemolysin (Reischl U. et al. 2002: Real-Time Fluorescence PCR Assays for Detection and Characterization of Shiga Toxin, Intim and Enterohemolysin Genes from Shiga Toxin-Producing Escherichia coli. Journ of Clin Microb, 40, p 2555-2565).

The serotyping was carried out by the National Reference Center for VTEC in the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Harmonization of methods with regard to all possible VTEC serotypes.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen

Notification system in place

No notification system in place at this time.

Results of the investigation

Verotoxin was detected in 64 of 127 samples, VTEC (verotoxin producing E. coli) could be isolated from 37 verotoxin-positive samples, showing a prevalence of VTEC of 29 %; 2 x O157 (1 x VTEC O157:H- - eae positiv vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv, 1 x VTEC O157:H7 - eae positiv vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv. In several samples more than one VTEC serotype was identified.

According to the EFSA definition of VTEC ("a VTEC positive sample is considered to be any sample, from which at least one E. coli strain containing vtx and eae has been isolated. Both gene-groups must be present in the isolated E. coli strain, for a sample to be positive") only in 8 samples VTEC were isolated, showing a prevalence of 6 %.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The prevalence of isolated VTEC from bovine remained high; we hypothesize that this is due to a high sensitivity of the ELISA, the sampling material (recto-anal swabs) and the improvement in the VTEC isolation techniques especially the use of the enterohemolysin-agar.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance of findings of VTEC in faeces seems to be low because VTEC are found only in a very low prevalence on meat samples from bovines.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. Verotoxigenic E. coli (VTEC) in animal - Sheep

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Monitoring program on the prevalence of VTEC in sheep at farm:

The monitoring in 2010 was directed towards sheep at farms. 112 sheep (out of 112 different farms) had to be tested, calculated on a population of sheep of 350,000 in Austria in 2010. The sampling had been stratified on the number and size of sheep holdings in Austrian provinces.

Frequency of the sampling

Animals at farm:

The sampling was done after blood sampling in course of the Brucella melitensis control program.

Type of specimen taken

Animals at farm:

Recto-anal swabs

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Animals at farm:

The swab was sent in transport medium cooled down to 4 °C and the fleece in a separate plastic bag in a hobbock or polystyrene box after adding cooling units to the AGES Institute of Veterinary Diseases Control (IVET) in Graz. In the laboratory, the swab and fleece were inoculated into separate broths.

Case definition

Animals at farm

An animal is considered to be infected with VTEC following the isolation of VTEC (verotoxin producing E. coli irrespective of intimin) from one of the samples tested.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Animals at farm

In a first step the samples were screened for presence of verotoxins by ELISA, secondly the positive samples were processed for VTEC isolation, see chapter above.

The serotyping was carried out by the National Reference Laboratory for VTEC in the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Harmonization of methods with regard to all possible VTEC serotypes.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen

Notification system in place

No notification

Results of the investigation

Verotoxin was detected in 89 of 112 swab samples. VTEC could be isolated from 73 verotoxin-positive swab samples, showing a prevalence for VTEC of 65 %; none of them O157, all eae negative. In several samples more than one VTEC serotype was identified.

According to the EFSA definition of VTEC ("a VTEC positive sample is considered to be any sample, from which at least one E. coli strain containing vtx and eae has been isolated. Both gene-groups must be present in the isolated E. coli strain, for a sample to be positive") no VTEC was isolated from sheep, showing a prevalence of 0 %.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The prevalence of isolated VTEC from sheep remained high but we hypothesize that this is due to a higher sensitivity of the new ELISA, the sampling material (recto-anal swabs) and the improvement in the VTEC isolation techniques especially the use of the enterohemolysin-agar.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance of findings of VTEC in/on sheep seems to be low because sheep meat is consumed well-done.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 63 Escherichia coli containing vtx and eae in animals, 2010

animal species	sampling context	Sampling stage	Source of information	Sampling unit	units tested	units with VTEC isolated	VTEC O 157	VTEC non O 157	VTEC O103:H2 - vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ eae positiv	VTEC O103:HNT - vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ eae positiv	VTEC O156:H - vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv eae positiv	VTEC O157:H - vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv eae positiv	VTEC O157:H7 - vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv eae positiv	VTEC O177:H - vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv eae positiv	VTEC O84:H - vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ eae positiv	VTEC ONT:H - vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv eae positiv
Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal)	IVET Graz	Animal	6	0	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cattle (bovine animals) - meat production animals - young cattle (1-2 years)	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal)	IVET Graz	Animal	37	4	1	3	1	-	1	-	1	-	1	-
Cattle (bovine animals) - adult cattle over 2 years	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal)	IVET Graz	Animal	84	4	1	3	-	1	-	1	-	1	-	1
Sheep	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at farm - animal sample - mucosal swab	IVET Graz	Animal	112	0	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 64 Verotoxin producing Escherichia coli in animals (all VTEC isolated), 2010

animal species		sampling context	Sampling stage	Source of information	Sampling unit	units tested	units positive (ELISA)	units with VTEC isolated	VTEC O 157	VTEC non O 157	VTEC O rough:H19 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O103:H2 - eae positiv vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O103:HNT - eae positiv vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O107:H28 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O112ab:H2 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O113:H18 - eae negativ vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC O113:H4 - eae negativ vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC O113:HNT - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O116:H - eae negativ vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC O116:H - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O116:H21 - eae negativ vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC O116:HNT - eae negativ vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC O117:H - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O122ab:H2 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O125a,b,c:H21 - eae negativ vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC O125abc:Hrough - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O128abc:HNT - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O132:H18 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O142:H16 - eae negativ vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC O145:H8 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O146:H - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O146:H21 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O146:H21 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O146:H32 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O146:HNT - eae negativ vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC O149:HNT - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O153:H25 - eae negativ vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC O156:H - eae positiv vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O157:H - eae positiv vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O157:H7 - eae positiv vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC O166:H28 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O166:HNT - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O168:H7 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ		
cattle, unspecified	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal)	IVET Graz	Animal	127	64	37	2	44	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	1	1	1	0	0	0		
Sheep	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at farm - animal sample - mucosal swab	IVET Graz	Animal	112	89	77	0	87	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	3	1	5	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	4	1	2

Verotoxin Escherichia coli

animal species	sampling context	Sampling stage	Source of information	Sampling unit	units tested	units positive (ELISA)	units with VTEC isolated	VTEC O 157	VTEC non O 157	VTEC O168:H8 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O174:H8 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O175:H21 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O176:H - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O176:H - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O176:HNT - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O177:H - eae positiv vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC O178:H - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O178:H19 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O178:H7 - eae negativ vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC O178:HNT - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O179:H8 - eae negativ vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC O22:H11 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O22:H8 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O22:Hrough - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O38:H21 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O5:H - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O5:H - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O70:H - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O70:HNT - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O75:H8 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O75:HNT - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O76:H - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O76:H19 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O76:HNT - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O8:H - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O8.1:H21 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O8.2:H8 - eae negativ vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC O8.4:H - eae positiv vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O8.7:H - eae negativ vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC O8.7:H10 - eae negativ vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC O8.7:H16 - eae negativ vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC O9.1:H21 - eae negativ vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv		
cattle, unspecified	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal)	IVET Graz	Animal	127	64	37	2	44	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	2	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	2
Sheep	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at farm - animal sample - mucosal swab	IVET Graz	Animal	112	89	77	0	87	0	2	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	12	1	1	5	1	2	1	3	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	4	0

animal species	sampling context	Sampling stage	Source of information	Sampling unit	units tested	units positive (ELISA)	units with VTEC isolated	VTEC O 157	VTEC non O 157	VTEC O91:H21 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O91:H21 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O91:HNT - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC OMT :H- - eae negativ vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC OMT :H- - eae positiv vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC OMT :H10 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC OMT :H19 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC OMT :H2 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC OMT :H5 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC OMT :H8 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC OMT :H8 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC OMT :HNT - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC Orough:H- - eae negativ vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC Orough:H- - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC Orough:H18 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC Orough:H21 - eae negativ vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC Orough:H8 - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC Orough:HNT - eae negativ vtx1 negativ vtx2 positiv	VTEC Orough:HNT - eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC O5:H- eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 positiv	VTEC O112ab:H2 eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ	VTEC Orough:H2 eae negativ vtx1 positiv vtx2 negativ
cattle, unspecified	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal)	IVET Graz	Animal	127	64	37	2	44	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Sheep	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at farm - animal sample - mucosal swab	IVET Graz	Animal	112	89	77	0	87	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1

4.5. Tuberculosis

4.5.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Human tuberculosis has steadily declined during the last decades. Commission Decision 1999/467/EC of 15 July 1999 declared bovine herds of Austria officially tuberculosis-free.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Bovine tuberculosis poses no public health problem in Austria. Sheep, goats and pigs are free of bovine tuberculosis. Although in spring 2008 infective lung tuberculosis caused by *M. caprae* was diagnosed in one slaughtered cattle. All cattle of that holding were culled following an intra cutan testing showing several positive reactors. Two more cattle holdings with several reagents were culled and some single reactors in contact holdings. In 21 cattle out of 14 holdings *M. caprae* was isolated in 2008. In 2009 again 6 cattle out of 3 holdings were bacteriologically confirmed and in 2010 eight cattle were identified as infected with *M. caprae*. Since several years a reservoir of *M. caprae* in red deer in an Austrian region has been confirmed and cattle are exposed to the bacteria in the summertime grazing on contaminated pastures in the Alps.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

No findings of *M. bovis* in animals, although *M. caprae* was detected.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A new national regulation has been implemented due to the finding of *M. caprae* in cattle from a certain region (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 2008/322). This regulation obliges the intracutan testings (using simultaneously bovine and avium tuberculin) of all cattle and goats that are kept together with cattle in given districts due to the epidemiological situation.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Continuation of the existing control programs

Additional information

Nil

4.5.2. Tuberculosis in humans

A. Tuberculosis due to *Mycobacterium bovis* in humans

Case definition

Definite: A case with isolation of *M. tuberculosis* complex (except *M. bovis* BCG) from any clinical specimen.

Other than definite: A case that meets the clinical criteria above but does not meet the laboratory criteria of a definite case.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Definite: Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen, Auramin-Rhodamin stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material
- Culture: After decontamination of the homogenised sample material in NALC-NaOH and centrifugation, the sample material is transferred in parallel on Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing glycerol and PACT and Stonebrink agar containing PACT and MGITmedium.
The media are incubated at 37 °C for up to 8 weeks.
Confirmation of the species by Amplicor (Roche)
- Other than definite: A skin test and an X-Ray of the thorax are performed.

Notification system in place

The person who diagnoses (laboratory/hospital/general practitioner) has to notify definite (*M. tuberculosis* and *M. bovis*) and other than definite cases (this excludes radiologists) to the local health authority (Federal Law BGBl. 127/1968: Tuberkulosegesetz, as amended; Epidemiegesetz 1950, as amended). *M. bovis* is notifiable since 2004 (National Regulation BGBl. Nr. 254/2004: Anzeigepflichtige übertragbare Krankheiten 2004).

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The National Reference Center for Tuberculosis (NRC-T) has been nominated since 1995. Since 1998 all data are compiled in a national database.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Preliminary *M. bovis* was isolated from four cases and *M. caprae* was identified in three cases.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

The relevance is inconsiderable; in 2010 four out of 680 preliminary human tuberculosis cases were caused by *M. bovis* and three by *M. caprae*.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Annual report of the National Reference Center from 2009 (2010 not available yet):

http://www.bmg.gv.at/cms/site/attachments/8/1/9/CH0954/CMS1253785411621/tb_jb2009kuoscd24092010.pdf (as of 9.05.2011).

Table 65 Tuberculosis in humans - species/serotype distribution, 2010

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases
Tuberculosis	680	8,12	unknown	unknown
microbiological confirmed	324	3,87	unknown	unknown
<i>M. bovis</i>	4	0,05	4	0
<i>M. caprae</i>	3	0,04	3	0

Data source: National Reference Center for Tuberculosis as of April 27, 2011

Table 66 Tuberculosis in humans - age distribution, 2010

Age group	Tuberculosis due to <i>M. bovis</i>			Tuberculosis due to <i>M. caprae</i>		
	all	male	female	all	male	female
< 1 year	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	0	0	0	1	0	1
5 to 14 years	0	0	0	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	1	0	1	0	0	0
25 to 44 years	1	0	1	0	0	0
45 to 64 years	1	1	0	0	0	0
65 years and older	1	1	0	2	1	1
Age unknown	0	0	0	0	0	0
All age groups	4	2	2	3	1	2

Data source: National Reference Center for Tuberculosis as of April 27, 2011

4.5.3. Mycobacterium spp. in animals

A. Mycobacterium bovis in bovine animals

Status as officially free of bovine tuberculosis during the reporting year

The entire country free: Yes

Additional information

According to Council Directive 64/432/EWG from June 26, 1964, Austria has the status Officially Tuberculosis Free Member State declared in the Commission Decision 1999/467/EC from July 15th, 1999, replaced by Commission Decision 2003/467/EC from June 23rd, 2003. The monitoring programme is based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection in which all cattle and goats originating from an official tuberculosis free holding have to be tested for tuberculous alterations.

A national Regulation has been implemented due to the finding of *M. caprae* in cattle from a certain region (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008). This Regulation includes provisions which apply for all Mycobacteria belonging to the Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex; therefore also a compulsory notification exists.

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Specimens are taken from carcasses with macroscopically observable alterations, characteristic for tuberculosis. They are sampled in slaughterhouses and sent to the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals.

All cattle in holdings of designated regions given in annex 2 of the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 2008/322) were subjected to simultaneous intracutan testing.

Frequency of the sampling

Continuous post-mortem inspections of each slaughtered bovine and caprine animal.

Intracutan testing: All cattle in holdings of designated regions given in annex 2 of the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 322/2008).

Type of specimen taken

Organs/tissues: Tissues that are macroscopically altered due to tuberculosis, inclusive lymph nodes (according to Annex 4 of the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008).

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The alterations and lymph nodes are excised and sent to the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals.

Case definition

According to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 2008/322 -- Tuberculosis: Infection with Mycobacteria of the Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex. Results of the intracutan test: A reactor is each animal which is not negative (either doubtful or positive). Doubtful and positive reactions are defined (see Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 2008/322).

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Intracutan testing (simultaneous testing using bovine and avium tuberculin): The test is performed according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964, as amended and the national Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 322/2008).

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material.

Culture: After decontamination of the homogenised sample material in NALC and centrifugation, the sample material is transferred in parallel on Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing glycerol and PACT and Stonebrink agar containing PACT and Middlebrook medium. The media are incubated at 37 °C for up to 8 weeks.

Confirmation of the Mycobacterium species by PCR (De los Monteros et al. 1998: Journal of Clinical Microbiology 36: 239-242) in the National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals.

Vaccination policy

Due to the importance of the intracutan tests for diagnostic purposes, vaccinations are prohibited.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all slaughtered bovine and caprine carcasses originating from official tuberculosis free holding and intracutan tests in animals of given regions according to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

The control programs are based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all slaughtered bovine and caprine carcasses originating from an official tuberculosis free holding.

Intracutan tests are performed in animals in holdings of given regions according to the epidemiological situation, defined in the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A new national Regulation has been implemented due to the finding of *M. caprae* in cattle from a certain region (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008). This Regulation includes provisions which apply for all mycobacteria belonging to the Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex; therefore also a compulsory notification exists.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The carcass is condemned.

Loss of the status OTF for the holding from which the animal was originated and for contact holdings. It is prohibited to bring bovines and goats in and out of the holding. Slaughtering of cows and goats can only be allowed by the official veterinarian and has to be performed using a special testing and slaughtering frame. Epidemiological investigations have to be done.

Prohibition of keeping these animals together with animals from OTF-holdings on pastures or market places etc.

Regaining the status OTF:

There must be no animals in the holding showing signs of clinical tuberculosis

All animals are recruited from an OTF-holding

Animals have to be tested according to the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 322/2008).

No reactors are identified after two intradermal testings of all animals in the holding older than 6 months examined earliest 60 days (first tuberculin test) and earliest 4 months (second tuberculin test) but latest 12 months after elimination of the last reactor.

Notification system in place

A suspected case of tuberculosis must be notified.

Results of the investigation

No findings of *M. bovis* in cattle.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No findings of *M. bovis* in cattle. Due to the fact that *M. caprae* is endemic in wildlife deer in Western parts of Austria (and South-Western parts of Germany), cattle in this areas has been observed with higher sensitivity. The National Regulation concerning Bovine Tuberculosis has been revised and set into force on 1. September 2008 (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 2008/322, BGBl II 2008/384, BGBl II 2009/381).

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

M. caprae is differentiated in Austria.

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. *Mycobacterium bovis* in farmed deer

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Due to the identification of *M. caprae* in several cattle holdings new control programmes have been developed and implemented in 2009.

Frequency of the sampling

Every shot farmed deer that is foreseen to be used as a food is subjected to pre and post-mortem inspection. Pre-mortem inspection can be performed by the livestock owner if the owner is trained in this special inspection and if the veterinarian has assured himself of the physical health of the animal within the last month prior to slaughtering.

Type of specimen taken

Other: Macroscopically tuberculous alterations and lymph nodes

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The alterations and lymph nodes are excised and sent to the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals.

Case definition

Tubercles pathognomically for tuberculosis detected in course of the post-mortem inspection or *Mycobacterium bovis* or *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* isolated from suspected material

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stain is performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material

Culture: After decontamination of the homogenised sample material in NALC and centrifugation, the sample material is transferred in parallel on Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing glycerol and PACT and Stonebrink agar containing PACT and Middlebrook medium. The media are incubated at 37 °C up to 8 weeks.

Confirmation of the *Mycobacterium* species by PCR (De los Monteros et al. 1998: Journal of Clinical Microbiology 36: 239-242) in the National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is prohibited.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

The control programs are based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all slaughtered carcasses originating from an official tuberculosis free holding

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A new national Regulation has been implemented due to the finding of *M. caprae* in cattle from a certain region (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008). This Regulation includes provisions which apply for all *Mycobacteria* belonging to the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex; therefore also a compulsory notification exists.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The carcass is condemned. Further measures according to Tierseuchengesetz RGBL. 1909/177 as amended.

Notification system in place

The suspicion and finding of tuberculosis is notifiable.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No cases of *M. bovis* in 2010.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

No cases of *M. bovis* in 2010.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

C. Mycobacterium spp. in animal - all animals - at slaughter – Control programme - mandatory - official sampling (all slaughtered animals except those mentioned above)

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Samples from suspected swine are taken in slaughterhouses. Sampling is performed when tissue of slaughtered animals is visibly altered, seen by the unaided eye.

Goats in defined regions that are kept together with cattle are subjected to intracutan testing (see chapter Mycobacterium bovis bovine animals; Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BgBL II 2008/322).

Frequency of the sampling

Continuous post-mortem inspections of each slaughtered animal

Type of specimen taken

Other: Macroscopic tuberculous alterations and lymphnodes

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The altered tissue and lymph nodes are excised and sent to the laboratory

Case definition

Tubercles pathognomically for tuberculosis detected in course of the post-mortem inspection or Mycobacterium bovis or Mycobacterium tuberculosis or Mycobacterium avium isolated from suspected material

Tuberculosis (for bovines and goats which are kept together with bovines): Infection with Mycobacteria of the Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex.

Results of the intracutan test: A reactor is each animal which is not negative (either doubtful or positive).

Reactions are defined (see Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BgBL II 2008/322)

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material

Culture: After decontamination of the homogenised sample material in NALC and centrifugation, the sample material is transferred in parallel on Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing glycerol and PACT and Stonebrink agar containing PACT and Middlebrook medium. The media are incubated at 37°C up to 8 weeks.

Confirmation of the Mycobacterium species by PCR (De los Monteros et al. 1998: Journal of Clinical Microbiology 36: 239-242) in the National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is prohibited.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

See other chapters.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

The control programs are based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all slaughtered carcasses originating from an official tuberculosis free holding

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No need at the moment

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The carcass is condemned. Further measures are performed according to Tierseuchengesetz RGBI. 1909/177, as amended.

Notification system in place

The detection of tuberculosis is notifiable.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No cases in Austria in 2010.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

No cases in Austria in 2010.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 67 Bovine tuberculosis in countries and regions that do not receive Community co-financing for eradication programme, 2010

Member State: Austria..... Date of the report: 23.05.2011..... Year: 2010.....											
The official post-mortem examination for all slaughtered bovine animals is implemented: Yes											
Region (1)	Total number of existing bovine		Officially free herds		Infected herds * all M. caprae		Routine tuberculin testing		Number of tuberculin tests carried out before the introduction into the herds (Annex A(I)(2)(c) third indent (1) of Directive 64/432/EEC)	Number of animals with suspicious lesions of tuberculosis examined and submitted to histopathological and bacteriological examinations	Number of animals detected positive in bacteriological examination *all M. caprae
	Herds	Animals	Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Interval between routine tuberculin tests (2)	Number of animals tested			
Austria	71563	2013281	71555	99.989	8	0.011	(a) and (g)	7633	15	40	8
Total	71563	2013281	71555	99.989	8	0.011	(a) and (g)	7633	15	40	8

* all identified cases due to M. caprae; national control measures identical to the detection of M. bovis

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Use the following letter codes: (a) no routine tests; (b) tests once a year; (c) tests every two years; (d) tests every three years concerning 24 month-old animals; (f) tests every 4 years; (g) others (please give details) Sonderuntersuchungs- bzw. überwachungsgebiet.

Table 68 Tuberculosis in other animals, 2010

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Mycobacteriaspp.</i>
Sheep	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante- mortem and post- mortem inspection	Stat. AT	animal	122,053	0
Goats	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante- mortem and post- mortem inspection	Stat. AT	animal	5,301	0
Pigs	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante- mortem and post- mortem inspection	Stat AT	animal	5,577,579	0

Stat. AT: Statistics Austria

4.6. Brucellosis

4.6.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In Austria, human brucellosis cases are considered to be an imported infectious disease. The Austrian cattle, sheep and goat population bears the status Officially Brucellosis Free (OBF) and Officially Brucella melitensis free (OBmF).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Three human cases were identified in 2010; two cases were imported, for the third case the infectious vehicle is unknown.

The number of Brucellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of cases reported to the Epidemiological Reporting System and the National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, n = 3.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

No findings in Austria, OBF and OBmF

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A new national regulation has been implemented concerning the examination of milk- and bloodsamples in cattle (Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305).

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Continuation of the existing control programs

Additional information

If zoonotic agents, which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.6.2. Brucellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The National Reference Center provides a yearly report for the Ministry of Health.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with fever

AND at least one of following seven symptoms:

- Sweating (profuse, malodorous, specially nocturnal)
- Chills
- Arthralgia
- Weakness
- Depression
- Headache
- Anorexia

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following two:

- Isolation of *Brucella* spp. from a clinical specimen
- *Brucella* specific antibody response (Standard Agglutination Test, Complement Fixation, ELISA)

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Serological examination: Serum samples are tested in the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) with reference standard antisera from CVL-Weybridge. Participation in international ring trials: Brucellosis European Ring Trial 2000 and 2002 (VLA Weybridge) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and SAT.

- Bacteriological: Multiple blood samples are inoculated in blood culture broth over several consecutive days. The incubation lasted 4 to 6 weeks, once per week medium is transferred on brucella agar and incubated 5-10 % CO₂ atmosphere (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123- 126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 56).

- The genus is identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using brucella serum. The species is identified by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific sera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.)

Notification system in place

Notification of Brucellosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Austria is OBF and OBmF. All cases reported in Austria are epidemiologically linked to travel in endemic countries or to foreign workers from endemic countries; for one case this is suspected.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

This zoonosis has no relevance in Austria.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria.

Provisionally yearly report published on the Website of the MOH

Table 69 Brucellosis in humans - species/serotype distribution, 2010

	Cases	Notification rate/100.000	Autochtone cases	Imported cases	Unknown status
Brucellosis	3	<0.4	0	2	1
<i>B. abortus</i>	0	0	0	0	0
<i>B. melitensis</i>	3	<0.4	0	2	1
<i>B. suis</i>	0	0	0	0	0

Data source: EMS and National Reference Laboratory as of May 13, 2011

Table 70 Brucellosis in humans - age distribution, 2010

Age group	<i>Brucellosis</i>			<i>B. melitensis</i>		
	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	-	-	-	-	-	-
1 to 4 years	-	-	-	-	-	-
5 to 14 years	-	-	-	-	-	-
15 to 24 years	-	-	-	-	-	-
25 to 44 years	2	2	-	2	2	-
45 to 64 years	1	1	-	1	1	-
65 years and older	-	-	-	-	-	-
Age unknown	-	-	-	-	-	-
All age groups	3	3	-	3	3	-

Data source: EMS and National Reference Laboratory as of May 13, 2011

4.6.3. Brucella in foodstuffs

Due to the fact that Austria is OBF and OBmF, food is not investigated for Brucella spp.

4.6.4. Brucella spp. in animals

A. *Brucella abortus* in Bovine Animals

Status as officially free of bovine brucellosis during the reporting year

The entire country free: Yes

Additional information

Upon the request of the Commission Decision of July 15th 1999, CD 1999/466/EC, as amended, by the Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964, Austria achieved the status: officially brucellosis-free for bovine herds.

A new national regulation has been implemented concerning the examination of milk- and bloodsamples in cattle (Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305). This means that in the case of dairy herds, the examination of milk samples in accordance with Annex C of Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964 can be performed.

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Nationwide all bovine milk producing holdings were subjected to bulk milk testing.

In non-milk producing holdings a risk based sampling plan was performed.

Abortion or premature birth: Abortive material and blood of the cow is sampled

Frequency of the sampling

Bulk milk sampling: All milk producing holdings had been sampled minimum once per year according to the regulation (§6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBL II 2007/305). In case of not-negative bulk milk samples, blood samples in the affected holding were investigated.

Holdings without milk production: A risk based sampling plan has been calculated stratified according to the different provinces (§6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBL II 2007/305). If blood serology does not show a definitive negative result diagnostic slaughtering of the affected animal has to be carried out.

- Abortion or premature birth: Tissue and blood from the cow is sampled immediately post abortion. If the result of the first serological examination was negative, a second blood sample was taken 2 weeks post abortion for serological testing. If this result was negative again, sampling and testing was repeated after two weeks.

Type of specimen taken

Bulk milk

Blood samples

Diagnostic slaughtering: organs and lymph nodes of the genital tract; udder and accessory lymph nodes; fetus (stomach, lungs); retropharyngeal lymph node.

Abortion or premature birth: Tissue and blood samples from the animal that had an abortion.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Bulk milk sampling: §6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBL II 2007/305.

Holdings without milk production: According to the sampling plan individual blood samples are taken in the holdings and sent to the laboratories (§6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBL II 2007/305).

Diagnostic slaughtering: §6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBL II 2007/305.

Abortion or premature birth: Aborted tissue and blood samples sent to a veterinary laboratory.

Case definition

An animal is considered to be positive for *Brucella abortus*, in case of positive blood-serological test result and the epidemiological situation of the herd indicates the possibility that a brucella infection has been introduced to the herd or in case of bacteriological isolation. If a single animal reactor is detected in the holding, tracing back is an important tool to get more information about the animal.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bulk milk: Testings according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and the manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals of the OIE.

Blood samples: Testings according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and the manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals of the OIE: Routinely single serum samples or serum pools (5 sera in one pool) were tested in the Indirect-ELISA (I-ELISA) using the three OIE ELISA *Brucella* Standard Sera (OIE ELISAwSS, OIE ELISAspSS, OIE ELISAnSS) and the OIE *Brucella abortus* Positive International Standard Antiserum (OIEISS) to calibrate the method (Commission Regulation 535/2002/EC of 21 March 2002 amending Annex C to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and amending Decision 2000/330/EC). Following a positive or suspected test result in the IELISA single serum samples were also tested in the Complement Fixation Test (CFT), Rose Bengal test (RBT) and Competitive ELISA (C-ELISA).

Participation in international ring trials: Participation in international ring trials (Weybridge, AFSSA and other) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and Serum Agglutination Test (SAT). The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all Veterinary Institutes.

Abortion or premature birth: Aborted material was tested bacteriologically and serologically as described above.

Bacteriology: Smears of the samples are stained by Stableforth's method. Brucella agar and Columbia agar (Merck) containing selective additives were used (Oxoid). After inoculation the media were incubated for 4-10 days at 37°C in an atmosphere containing 10% CO₂. The genus was identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using brucella serum. The species was differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific sera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not allowed (BGBl. 1957/147, Bangseuchengesetz, § 13 Impfung)

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Control programme according to the National Regulation (Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305). Abortion or premature birth: Compulsory notification according BGBl 1957/147, Bangseuchengesetz, as amended, §11 Anzeigepflicht;

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No actions, because OBF

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to BGBl 1957/147, Bangseuchengesetz, as amended, and BGBl 1909/177, Tierseuchengesetz, as amended

Notification system in place

Abortion or premature birth: Notification of abortions: The livestock owner has to notify each abortion within 24 hours to the mayor (Gemeinde). The mayor has to forward the notification to the local authority (Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde) (BGBl. 1957/147, Bangseuchengesetz, § 11 Anzeigepflicht). If the cow is being treated by a veterinarian or the veterinarian has been informed about the abortion, then the veterinarian has to notify to the official authority (Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde).

Results of the investigation

See tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

OBF

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. *Brucella melitensis* in Sheep and Goats

Status as officially free of ovine brucellosis during the reporting year

The entire country free: Yes

Additional information

According to Commission Decision Nr. 93/52/EWG, as amended, Austria has the status officially brucellosis (*B. melitensis*) free (ObmF).

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

To maintain the status officially brucellosis (*B. melitensis*) free, according to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002) a representative number of samples were examined with a confidence level of 95 % to detect infected holdings at a target prevalence of 0.2 %. Sampling was performed by the competent authority or under its supervision, by bodies to which it had delegated this responsibility. Samples were taken in the holdings. Aborted material and blood samples from the animal were also investigated.

Frequency of the sampling

Principally the sampling was performed during the cold season, between November and May when the animals were kept in the stables.

Type of specimen taken

- Monitoring: Blood samples according to a sampling plan.
- Clinical cases: Aborted material and blood samples from the affected animal.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Individual blood samples and aborted material are taken within the holdings and sent to the laboratories.

Case definition

An animal is considered to be infected with *B. melitensis* in case of bacteriological isolation or positive serological test result.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Routinely single serum samples were tested in the Indirect ELISA. Confirmation of suspected or positive results was performed by the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) with reference standard antisera from CVL-Weybridge. Participation in international ring trials on Brucellosis (Weybridge and other) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and SAT. The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all national Veterinary Institutes.

Bacteriology: Smears of the samples were stained by Stableforth's method.

Brucella agar and Columbia agar (Merck) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media are incubated for 4 - 10 days at 37 °C in an atmosphere containing 10 % CO₂. The

genus was identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using brucella serum. The species were differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific sera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

According to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002, §4, Impfverbot) vaccination is not allowed.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Monitoring program and investigation of abortions

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

To maintain the status officially brucellosis (*B. melitensis*) free, according to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002) a representative number of samples have to be examined with a confidence level of 95 % to detect infected holdings at a prevalence of 0.2 %. Sampling is performed by the appropriate authority or under its supervision, by bodies to which it has delegated this responsibility. Samples are taken in the holdings.

Notification and clarification of each clinical case by bacteriology and serology.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

ObmF

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002, §3, Ausmerzung von Reagenten) reactors have to be culled, the carcasses have to be incinerated in an incineration plant.

Notification system in place

Notification of brucellosis or a suspicion of brucellosis according to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002).

Results of the investigation

See tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

ObmF

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

D. *Brucella suis* in animal – Pigs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

According to Guideline 64/432/EEC as amended.

Frequency of the sampling

Targeted, following abortion and in positive cases contact holdings.

Type of specimen taken

- Monitoring: Blood samples;
- Clinical cases: Abortion material and blood samples from the affected animal; tissues: according to decree 74700/0132-IV/B/5/2008

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Individual blood samples and abortion material are taken from animals in the holdings and sent to the laboratories.

Case definition

An animal is considered to be serologically positive for brucellosis following one/more positive CFT Complement Fixation Test (CFT) and RBT Rose Bengal test (RBT) results (*B. abortus* used antigen). A bacteriological isolation may also be possible as in the case of *B. suis*.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Due to the fact that a *Brucella suis* antigen is not available, the *B. abortus* antigen is used for the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) and the Rose Bengal test (RBT) because *B. abortus* shows cross reactions with *B. suis* antibodies.
 - ELISA and CFT is not available, the *B. abortus* ELISA and CFT are used because these tests show cross reactions with *B. suis* antibodies.
 - Participation in international ring trials: Brucellosis European Ring Trial 2000 and 2002 (VLA Weybridge) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and Serum Agglutination Test (SAT). The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all Veterinary Institutes.
- Bacteriology: Quality control: Laboratory strains
- Smears of the samples are stained by Stableforth's method
 - *Brucella* agar and Columbia agar (Merck) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media are incubated for 4-10 days at 37 °C in an atmosphere containing 10 % CO₂. The genus was identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using brucella serum. The species were differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific sera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No mandatory measures but notification is required.

Notification system in place

B. suis has been a notifiable disease since 1993 according to BGBl 1993/756, Tierseuchen-Anzeigepflichtverordnung, as amended.

Results of the investigation

There was one case of Brucella suis in 2010 (serologically positive).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Due to the results of the passive monitoring in pigs we conclude that there is no need for an active monitoring program.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 71 Bovine Brucellosis data from countries and regions that do not receive Community co-financing (non co-financed), 2010

Member State: Austria Date of report: 23.05.2011..... Year: 2010.....																					
Region ⁽¹⁾	Total number of existing bovine		Officially free herds		Infected herds		Surveillance ⁽²⁾						Investigations of suspect cases								
	Herds	Animals	Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Serological tests			Examination of bulk milk samples			Information on abortions			Epidemiological investigation					
							Number of bovine herds tested	Number of animals tested	Number of infected herds	Number of bovine herds tested	Number of animals or pools tested	Number of infected herds	Number of notified abortions whatever cause	Number of isolations of <i>Brucella</i> infection	Number of abortions due to <i>Brucella abortus</i>	Number of animals tested with serological blood tests	Number of suspended herds	Number of positive animals		Number of animals examined microbiologically	Number of animals positive microbiologically
																	Serologically	BST			
Austria	71,563	2,013,281	71,563	100	0	0	3,781	30,210	0	35,374	35,427	0	825	0	0	2003	60	0	0	2	0
Total	71,563	2,013,281	71,563	100	0	0	3,781	30,210	0	35,374	35,427	0	825	0	0	2003	60	0	0	2	0

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Please give details.

Table 72 Ovine and caprine brucellosis - data from countries that do not receive co-financing for control or eradication programme, 2010

Member State: Austria..... Date of report: 26.05.2011..... Year: 2010.....														
Region (1)	Total number of existing ovine/caprine		Officially free herds		Infected herds		Surveillance (2)			Investigations of suspect cases				
	Herds	Animals	Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Number of herds tested	Number of animals tested	Number of infected herds	Number of animals tested with serological blood tests	Number of animals positive serologically	Number of animals examined microbiologically	Number of animals positive microbiologically	Number of suspended herds
Austria	27,208	503,674	27,208	100	0	0	1,669	19,907	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	27,208	503,674	27,208	100	0	0	1,669	19,907	0	0	0	0	0	0

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services, Provincial Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Please give details.

4.7. Yersiniosis

4.7.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Yersiniosis is not considered a major food borne illness in Austria. The incidence of human disease is low when compared to salmonellosis or campylobacteriosis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of Yersiniosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of cases reported to the Epidemiological Reporting System and the National Reference Laboratory for Yersiniosis, n = 84. The sources of infections are unclear. Neither studies on sporadic cases nor scientific outbreak investigations were performed in Austria so far.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

If zoonotic agents, which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.7.2. Yersiniosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The National Reference Center provides a yearly report for the Ministry of Health.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following five symptoms:

- Fever
- Diarrhoea
- Vomiting
- Abdominal pain (pseudoappendicitis)
- Tenesmus

Laboratory criteria

- Isolation of human pathogenic *Yersinia enterocolitica* or *Yersinia pseudotuberculosis* from a clinical specimen

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Faecal (*Yersinia enterocolitica*) or resection (*Y. pseudotuberculosis*) sample material is plated directly on cefsulodin-irgasan-novobiocin (CIN) agar and incubated for 18 hours at 30 °C. Suspicious colonies are identified in an Api 20 E reaction and API 50 CHE reaction. *Y. enterocolitica* is agglutinated with sera against serogroups O:3, O:5, O:9 and O:8. Biovar and pathogenicity are defined.

Notification system in place

Notification of Yersiniosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Yersiniosis is the third most bacterial food borne pathogen in Austria although compared to salmonellosis and campylobacteriosis, the number of notified cases are much lower.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of human cases has been similar in the last years.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Yersiniosis is the third most bacterial food borne pathogen in Austria although compared to salmonellosis and campylobacteriosis, the number of notified cases are much lower.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. Annual report of the National Reference Centre

http://bmg.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/8/6/3/CH1305/CMS1299586684574/jb_yersinien_2010_v4.pdf (as of 9.05.2011).

Provisionally yearly report published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 73 Yersiniosis in human - species/serotype distribution, 2010

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population
Yersiniosis	84	1.00
<i>Y. enterocolitica</i>	83	0.99
<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:3	70	0.84
<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:9	12	0.14
<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> sv indeterminate	1	0.01
<i>Y. pseudotuberculosis</i>	1	0.01

Data source: EMS and National Reference Laboratory as of May 13, 2011

Table 74 Yersiniosis in humans - age distribution, 2010

Age group	Yersiniosis			<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:3			<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:9			<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> sv indeterminate			<i>Y. pseudotuberculosis</i>		
	all	male	female	all	male	female	all	male	female	all	male	female	all	male	female
< 1 year	3	0	3	3	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	19	7	12	16	4	12	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	15	7	8	13	6	7	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
15 to 24 years	17	12	5	17	12	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25 to 44 years	16	8	8	10	5	5	6	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
45 to 64 years	9	6	3	7	4	3	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
65 years and older	5	3	2	4	3	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
All age groups	84	43	41	70	34	36	12	8	4	1	1	0	1	0	1

Data source: EMS and National Reference Laboratory as of May 13, 2011

Table 75 Yersiniosis in humans - seasonal distribution, 2010

Month	Yersiniosis	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:3	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:9	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> sv indeterminate	<i>Y. pseudotuberculosis</i>
	Cases	Cases	Cases	Cases	Cases
January	4	3	1	-	-
February	10	9	-	1	-
March	2	2	-	-	-
April	6	6	-	-	-
May	7	7	-	-	-
June	4	3	1	-	-
July	4	4	-	-	-
August	13	10	3	-	-
September	6	5	1	-	-
October	11	9	2	-	-
November	4	3	1	-	-
December	4	3	1	-	-
Unkown	9	6	2	-	1
Total	84	70	12	1	1

Data source: EMS and National Reference Laboratory as of May 13, 2011

4.7.3. Yersinia in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2008 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2008“ (BMGFJ – 75500/0332-IV/B/7/2008) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2007-2010) according to Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2010, approximately 35,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 75 % of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-dept information. In 2010, seven food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2010 BMG-75500/0246-II/B/7/2009). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Enrichment of 25 g sample in ITC-broth and incubation at 25°C for 48 hours and enrichment in PSB-broth at 22-25°C for 5 days; plating on CIN-agar and SSDC-agar and incubation at 30°C for 48 hours.

Results of the investigation

Table 76 Yersiniosis in food, 2010

Food	Sampling Context	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Yersinia</i>	<i>Y. frederiksenii</i>	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> biovar 1A
Fishery products, unspecified	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0		
Meat from other animal species or not specified	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0		
Meat from pig - fresh	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0		
Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	1		1
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	1	1	

4.7.4. Yersinia spp. in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not relevant in Austria therefore no testing.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination.

Other preventative measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

EU wide harmonized monitoring program.

Notification system in place:

Findings of Yersinia are not notifiable in animals.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No changes in recent years.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance has not been investigated.

Additional information

Nil

4.8. Trichinellosis

4.8.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

No documented autochton human infestations since several years.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of Trichinellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of cases reported to the Epidemiological Reporting System and the National Reference Laboratory for Trichinellosis, n = 5.

No documented autochtone human infestations in 2010.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Two documented infestations in food-animals (wild boars).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No new measures implemented

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Reconsider the necessity of routine trichinella meat inspection in pig carcasses

Additional information

If zoonotic agents, which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.8.2. Trichinellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The National Reference Center provides a yearly report the Ministry of Health.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least three of the following six symptoms:

- Fever
- Muscle soreness and pain
- Diarrhoea
- Facial oedema
- Eosinophilia
- Subconjunctival, subungual and retinal haemorrhages

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following two:

- Demonstration of Trichinella larvae in tissue obtained by muscle biopsy
- Trichinella specific antibody response (IFA test, ELISA or Western Blot)

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

ELISA and Westernblot

Notification system in place

Notification of Trichinellosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The last autochthonous cases have been reported in 1970

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance as zoonotic disease

No relevance in Austria

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria.

Provisionally yearly report published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 77 Trichinellosis in human - species/serotype distribution, 2010

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Imported cases	Unkown
Trichinellosis	5	0.06	2	3
Trichinella spiralis	3	0.04	2	1
unspecified	2	0.02	-	2

Data source: Epidemiological Reporting System, National Reference Laboratory as 13th May 2011

Table 78 Trichinellosis in human - age distribution, 2010

Age group	<i>Trichinellosis</i>			<i>Trichinella spiralis</i>			<i>Trichinella unspecified</i>		
	all	male	female	all	male	female	all	male	female
< 1 year	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25 to 44 years	2	2	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
45 to 64 years	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
65 years and older	2	2	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
All age groups	5	5	0	3	3	0	2	2	0

Data source: Epidemiological Reporting System, National Reference Laboratory as 13th May 2011

4.8.3. Trichinella in animals

A. Trichinella spp. in pigs

Number of officially recognised Trichinella-free holdings

Categories of holdings officially recognised Trichinella-free

Officially recognised regions with negligible Trichinella risk

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

General

Targeted sampling of all slaughtered pigs except pigs slaughtered by the farmer for his own consumption; the sampling is performed by competent authorities; the samples are taken at slaughterhouses; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme.

Frequency of the sampling

General

Other: Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered pig

Type of specimen taken

General

Muscles: Diaphragm (crus), tongue, masseter and abdominal muscles.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

General

Appropriate muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Case definition

General

When trichinellosis is detected with one of the given methods

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2075/2005

Vaccination policy

Nil

Preventive measures in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004, as amended.

The contingency plan in place

Notification system in place

Results of the investigation including description of the positive cases and the verification of the *Trichinella* species

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. *Trichinella* spp. in horses

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Targeted sampling of all slaughtered horses; the sampling is performed by competent authorities; the samples are taken at slaughterhouses; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme

Frequency of the sampling

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered horse

Type of specimen taken

Muscles from tongue, masseter, diaphragm and neck.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Appropriate muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Case definition

When trichinellosis is detected with one of the given methods.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2075/2005

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

Results of the investigation

No findings in horses.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

C. *Trichinella* spp. in animal - Wildlife - wild boars

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Sampling of all hunted or harvested wild boars; the sampling is performed by hunters with special knowledge about trichinella investigation or by competent authorities; the sampling is stratified by geographical regions depending to the habitats of wild boar in Austria; samples are taken either immediately after shooting the animal or at the cold storage depots; the sampling is part of a monitoring scheme.

Frequency of the sampling

All farmed wild boars are controlled for trichinella.

Type of specimen taken

Diaphragm muscles (crus), tongue, masseter and abdominal muscles.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Appropriate muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Case definition

When trichinellosis is detected with one of the given methods.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2075/2005

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2 samples Trichinella was detected

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 79 *Trichinella* spp. in animals, 2010

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Trichinella</i> spp.
Pigs							
fattening pigs raised under controlled housing conditions in integrated system							
fattening pigs not raised under controlled housing conditions in integrated system	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling		CVS	animal	5,577,579	0
breeding animals -unspecified - sows and boars							
Domestic solipeds							
horses	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling			animal	520	0
Wild boars							
Farmed	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling			animal	25,480	2
wild							
Foxes							
Badger					animal	17	0
Bears							
Rodents							
Rats							

CVS: Central Veterinary Services

4.9. Echinococcosis

4.9.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Austria is a low risk country for both forms of echinococcosis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of echinococcosis cases presented in this report (table 2) reflects the number of cases reported to the Epidemiological Reporting System and the National Reference Laboratory for Echinococcosis, n = 21.

We expect the future prevalence to be low.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Alveolar echinococcosis: Due to the infestation rates of red foxes in Austria (0-40 %) there is a relatively elevated risk for hunters, cat owners and farmers.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Tools for preventive serological screening of hunters (and also other persons) have been established to detect *Echinococcus multilocularis* infections in an early stage. The early detection of the infection is the prerequisite for a successful curative treatment.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

If zoonotic agents, which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.9.2. Echinococcosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The National Reference Center provides a yearly report for the Ministry of Health.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Not relevant for surveillance purposes

Diagnostic criteria

At least one of the following five findings:

- Histopathology or parasitology compatible with *Echinococcus multilocularis* or *granulosus* (e.g. direct isvisualisation of the protoscolex in cyst fluid)
- Detection of *Echinococcus granulosus* pathognomonic macroscopic morphology of cyst(s) in surgical specimens
- Typical organ lesions detected by imaging techniques (e.g.: computerised tomography, sonography, MRI) AND confirmed by a serological test

- Echinococcus spp. specific serum antibodies by high-sensitivity serological test AND confirmed by a high specificity serological test
- Detection of Echinococcus multilocularis or granulosus nucleic acid in a clinical specimen

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- NA

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the diagnostic criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

ELISA and Westernblot technique, participant of the UK National External Quality Assessment Service for Microbiology, National Reference Laboratory for Echinococcosis.

Notification system in place

Notification of echinococcosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

- Alveolar echinococcosis has been known in Austria since 1897; annual incidence (1897- 2004): 0-6 cases, mean incidence: 2.4 cases/year (only autochthonous cases); geographic distribution in Austria: mainly in the western provinces (Vorarlberg, Tyrol, Salzburg), but cases have been reported in every province; outbreaks are not known.
- Cystic echinococcosis has been known in Austria at least since 1819; Cases of cystic echinococcosis have been registered in the Clinical Institute of Hygiene and Medical Microbiology (Medical University Vienna) regularly since the beginning of the 1980ies. Annual incidence (1984 - 2006): 20 - 60 cases; mean incidence: 31 cases per year, one third of patients are of Austrian origin; two thirds are from abroad. Geographic distribution in Austria is unknown; a few autochthonous infections could be observed mainly in the eastern and southern provinces (Lower Austria, Burgenland, and Styria); outbreaks are not known.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

- Alveolar echinococcosis: We expect the future incidence to be low; sources of infestation: fox faeces (contaminated hands and fingers, vegetables, water).
- Cystic echinococcosis: We expect the future incidence to be low; sources of infestation: dog faeces, presumably in a very few foci (in or around farmers houses)

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Low incidence of both forms of echinococcosis

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria.

Provisionally yearly report published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 80 Echinococcosis in humans - species/serotype distribution, 2010

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	autochtone cases	imported cases	unknown
Echinococcosis	21	0.26	5	4	12
<i>E. granulosus</i>	18	0.22	5	3	10
<i>E. multilocularis</i>	3	0.04		1	2

Data source: Epidemiological Reporting System, National Reference Laboratory as 13th May 2011

Table 81 Echinococcosis in humans - age distribution, 2010

Age group	<i>Echinococcus</i>			<i>E. granulosus</i>			<i>E. multilocularis</i>		
	all	male	female	all	male	female	all	male	female
< 1 year	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	2	2	0	2	1	1	1	1	0
25 to 44 years	6	1	5	7	1	6	1	0	1
45 to 64 years	4	3	1	7	3	4	0	0	0
65 years and older	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
All age groups	14	7	7	18	7	11	3	1	2

Data source: Epidemiological Reporting System, National Reference Laboratory as 13th May 2011

4.9.3. Echinococcus in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Targeted sampling of all in abattoirs slaughtered animals; the sampling is performed by competent authorities in course of the post-mortem meat inspection; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme.

Frequency of the sampling

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered animal

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

All organs and muscles that were used for human consumption

Case definition

Each carcass in which cysts, cystic or alveolar hydatids are detected in muscles or organs

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Other: All organs and muscles that were used for human consumption were visually inspected, palpated and cuttings were performed

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Post-mortem meat inspection act according to BGBl. 1982/522, Fleischuntersuchungsgesetz, as amended

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Cystic or alveolar echinococcosis in animals that are used for food production do not play a role for the infection of humans; it is primarily a hygienic problem.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 82 Echinococcus sp. in animals, 2010

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for Echinococcus spp.	<i>E. multilocularis</i>	<i>E. granulosus</i>	<i>Echinococcus</i> spp., unspecified
Cattle	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	624,859	195			
Sheep	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	265,568	622			
Goats	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	45,159	0			
Pigs	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	5,632,643	0			

All detected cysts are reported but not differentiated

x: Central Veterinary Services, Statistics Austria

4.10. Toxoplasmosis

4.10.1. General evaluation of the national situation

No data available.

4.10.2. Toxoplasma in humans

Not notifiable in Austria.

4.10.3. Toxoplasma in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

There is no official surveillance for *Toxoplasma* spp. in animals. Sampling of cattle, sheep, goats or pigs is performed depending on clinical suspicion of toxoplasmosis and if ordered by the sender in cases after abortion. Other animal species are also occasionally sampled.

Frequency of the sampling

In case of clinical suspicion and abortion and if ordered.

Type of specimen taken

Blood, organ, faeces

Case definition

A case is defined as an animal that tested positive serologically ($\geq 1:40$) or if the pathogen is detected microscopically. The animal is the epidemiological unit.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The diagnostic methods used for serology is the microagglutination test.

Vaccination policy:

No vaccination

Other preventative measures than vaccination in place:

Control programme/ mechanisms:

The control programmes/ strategies in place

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases:**Notification system in place:**

Toxoplasmosis is not notifiable in animals.

Results of the investigation

No valid data available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection:

Nil

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection):**Additional information**

Nil

Table 83 Toxoplasmosis in animals, 2010

animal species	sampling context	sampling details	sampling unit	Source of information	Units tested	Total units positive for Toxoplasma
dog	clinical investigation	feces	animal	AGES IVET	1	0
dog	clinical investigation	organs	animal	AGES IVET	1	0
cat	clinical investigation	blood	animal	AGES IVET	1	0
cattle	clinical investigation	blood	animal	AGES IVET	10	0
cattle	clinical investigation	organs	animal	AGES IVET	1	0
sheep	clinical investigation	blood	animal	AGES IVET	27	16
sheep	clinical investigation	organs	animal	AGES IVET	12	0
goat	clinical investigation	blood	animal	AGES IVET	29	6

4.11. Rabies

4.11.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Rabies in humans was a major public health issue in the 1960s.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2010, there was no case of rabies detected in animals in Austria.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

In 2010, vaccination programmes were carried out in fox populations in areas of higher risk.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

Nil

4.11.2. Rabies in humans

Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with an acute encephalomyelitis

AND

At least two of the following seven symptoms:

- Sensory changes referred to the site of a preceding animal bite
- Paresis or paralysis
- Spasms of swallowing muscles
- Hydrophobia
- Delirium
- Convulsions
- Anxiety

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following four:

- Isolation of Lyssa virus from a clinical specimen
- Detection of Lyssa virus nucleic acid in a clinical specimen (e.g. saliva or brain tissue)
- Detection of viral antigens by a DFA in a clinical specimen
- Lyssa virus specific antibody response by virus isneutralisation assay in serum or CSF

Laboratory results need to be interpreted according to the vaccination or immunisation status

Case classification

Possible case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Liquor, smears from pharynx, swab from conjunctivae biopsy at the nape of the neck and serum were examined in the fluorescent antibody test (FAT), immunohistochemistry and RT-PCR (Ito M., Itou T., Sakai T., et al. (2001). Detection of Rabies Virus RNA isolated from several species of animals in Brazil by RT-PCR. Journal of Veterinary medicine Science 63(12): 1309-1313.).

Notification system in place

Notification of rabies according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Nil

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Nil

Table 84 Rabies in humans

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases
Rabies	0	0	0	0
Human expose	0	0	0	0

4.11.3. Lyssavirus (rabies) in animals

A. Rabies virus in animal - Wildlife - foxes

Monitoring system**Sampling strategy**

According to GZ:39.642/14-VII/B/03: 8 foxes per 100 km² in rabies infected and rabies endangered areas, 4 foxes per 100 km² in not endangered and free areas (definition of areas: GZ 30.517/35-IV/12/03).

Frequency of the sampling

8 foxes per 100 km² in rabies infested and rabies endangered areas, 4 foxes per 100km² in not endangered and free areas.

Type of specimen taken

Other: Brain (brain stem or hippocampus)

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Whole animals or heads of the dead animals are sent to the laboratories; sometimes brain tissue (derived from other laboratories). Brain tissue (e.g. 1 cm²) is examined.

Case definition

An animal is considered positive if the fluorescent antibody test (FAT) shows a positive signal.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The routine test was the fluorescent antibody test (FAT).

RTCIT (rabies tissue culture infection test) was performed on mouse neuroblastoma cells.

MIT (mouse inoculation test) will be only performed on demand, not for routine confirmation

Vaccination policy

Delivery of vaccine containing baits in the southern part of East Tyrol; the requirement is 25 baits/km² in an area of approximately 854 km² (27 packets with 800 pieces each); additionally emergency vaccination from southern Tyrol to the Deferegger Alps (iG, Drautal) Lesachtal in Carinthia due to cases of rabies registered in North Italy since October 2008.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Fuchs-Tollwutbekämpfungsverordnung 2010 BGBl II 2010/329, Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42, Tierseuchengesetz-Durchführungsverordnung 1909/178 as amended: BGBl 1955/76 TSG-DVO zum IV. Abschnitt Wutkrankheiten

Control of vaccination: Detection of tetracycline in jaw bones of randomly chosen foxes from the vaccination area; additionally an ELISA is performed to proof seroconversion.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A helicopter was requested to delivery the baits; recommendation of vaccination for dogs and cats in the southern border area and public awareness through BMGs homepage.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Probably the reduction of the number of the animals (foxes) for investigation.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42, and vaccination of the fox population.

Notification system in place

According to Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Austria is declared as rabies free since 28.9.2008.

Note the additional emergency vaccination in Carinthia according GZ 74.100/0002-II/B/5/2010 and GZ. 74100/0091-II/B10/2010.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

B. Rabies virus in animal - all animals except foxes

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Sampling is targeted when animals are observed with central nerval symptoms or after biting a person. The suspicious animal is killed or euthanized and the carcass or head is sent to the laboratory.

Frequency of the sampling

If a case is suspected

Type of specimen taken

Other: Brain (hippocampus and brain stem)

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Routinely a sample will be taken from one site of the brain: a part from the hippocampus, brain stem or cerebellum. If an animal has bitten a person then 2 parts from the brain will be taken: hippocampus and brain stem.

Case definition

An animal is considered positive if the fluorescent antibody tests (FAT) or the rabies tissue culture infection test or the mouse inoculation test show a positive result.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The routine test was the fluorescent antibody test (FAT).

RTCIT (rabies tissue culture infection test) was performed on mouse neuroblastoma cells.

MIT (mouse inoculation test) will be only performed on demand, not for routine confirmation

Vaccination policy

Voluntary vaccination of pets.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42;

Tierseuchengesetz-Durchführungsverordnung 1909/178 as amended: BGBl 1955/76

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42. If a rabies suspicious pet bites a person, the person is treated.

Notification system in place

According to Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBI I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

On 28th of September 2008, Austria has been declared free of rabies.

Vaccination areas, rabies endangered and rabies free areas were redefined.

Table 85 Rabies in animals, 2010

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for Lyssa virus (rabies)	Classical rabies virus (serotype 1)	European Bat Lyssavirus 1 (ELB 1)	European Bat Lyssavirus 2 (ELB 2)	Rabies virus, unspecified
Cattle	at farm - animal sample organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES	Animal	6	0	0	0	0	0
Sheep	at farm - animal sample organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES	Animal	1	0	0	0	0	0
Goats			AGES	Animal	0	-	-	-	-	-
Pigs			AGES	Animal	0	-	-	-	-	-
Domestic solipeds	at farm - animal sample organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES	Animal	2	0	0	0	0	0
Dogs	at farm - animal sample organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES	Animal	57	0	0	0	0	0
Cats	at farm - animal sample organ/tissue	clinical investigation	AGES	Animal	52	0	0	0	0	0
Wildlife			AGES	Animal	2478					
Bats	found dead	monitoring - official sampling - selective sampling	AGES	Animal	80	0	0	0	0	0
Foxes- wild	from hunting or found dead	selective sampling - official sampling - monitoring programme	AGES	Animal	2358	0	0	0	0	0
Raccoon dog - wild			AGES	Animal	0	-	-	-	-	-
Raccoon - wild			AGES	Animal	0	-	-	-	-	-
Wolves - wild			AGES	Animal	0	-	-	-	-	-
Badgers - wild	from hunting or found dead	selective sampling - clinical suspects	AGES	Animal	11	0	0	0	0	0
Martens - wild	from hunting or found dead	selective sampling clinical suspects	AGES	Animal	26	0	0	0	0	0
Wild boars - wild			AGES	Animal	0	-	-	-	-	-
Deer - wild			AGES	Animal	0	-	-	-	-	-
roe deer - wild	from hunting		AGES	Animal	3	0	0	0	0	0
red deer - wild			AGES	Animal	0	-	-	-	-	-
fallow deer - wild			AGES	Animal	0	-	-	-	-	-
Other farm, wild or pet animals (please add the relevant species)			AGES	Animal	17					
Other mustelidae	from hunting or found death	selective sampling-clinical suspects	AGES	Animal	7	0	0	0	0	0
Other wild animals	from hunting	selective sampling-clinical suspects	AGES	Animal	10	0	0	0	0	0

Data source: NRL Rabies as of 10.05.2011

4.12. Q-Fever

4.12.1. General evaluation of the situation

No information

4.12.2. Q-fever in humans

Not notifiable in Austria, therefore no data available

4.12.3. Coxiella burnetii in animals

Not notifiable in Austria

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

There is no official surveillance for Coxiella burnetii in animals.

Frequency of the sampling

Type of specimen taken

Case definition

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The diagnostic method is the complement fixation reaction, detecting phase 1 and phase 2 antigens. Organs and swabs are tested by real time PCR.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination.

Other preventative measures than vaccination in place:

Nil

Control programme/ mechanisms

The control programmes/ strategies in place

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Notification system in place

Q-fever in animals is not a notifiable disease

Results of the investigation

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Q-fever in humans is not a notifiable disease. In Austria the number of sheep per holding is low (3.9 animals per holding in average) compared to countries that have a problem with Q-fever; therefore no change of the epidemiological situation in Austria is expected.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

Nil

Table 86 Q-fever in animals, 2010

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Coxiella burnetii</i>
Cattle	clinical investigations	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	Coxiella burnetii	AGES IVET	animal	6	0
Cattle	clinical investigations	at farm - animal sample - blood	Coxiella burnetii Ak	AGES IVET	animal	582	12
Sheep	clinical investigations	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	Coxiella burnetii	AGES IVET	animal	30	12
Sheep	clinical investigations	at farm - animal sample - blood	Coxiella burnetii Ak	AGES IVET	animal	135	28
Goats	clinical investigations	at farm - animal sample - milk	Coxiella burnetii Ak	AGES IVET	animal	20	2
Goats	clinical investigations	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	Coxiella burnetii	AGES IVET	animal	5	2
Goats	clinical investigations	at farm - animal sample - blood	Coxiella burnetii Ak	AGES IVET	animal	109	20

4.13. MRSA

4.13.1. MRSA in food

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Food samples were collected according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. In the AGES ILMUs in Graz, Wien and Linz those samples were tested for coagulase-positive staphylococci according to EN ISO 6888. All coagulase-positive staphylococci were sent to the national reference laboratory for antimicrobial resistance in the IMED Graz to test for the *mecA* gene.

Frequency of the sampling

All over the year.

Type of specimen taken

All different food categories

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 1 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *mecA* gene in coagulase positive staphylococci

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

Out of 4,447 samples 169 coagulase-positive staphylococci were isolated. None of the typed staphylococci was a MRSA.

Additional information

no

Table 87 MRSA in food, 2010

Food	Sampling Context	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Staphylococcus</i>	Total units positive for <i>S. aureus</i> , methicillin resistant (MRSA)
Bakery products	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	2	0	0
Bakery products - cakes	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	77	1	0
Bakery products - pastry	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	114	1	0
Bakery produkts	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	34	1	0
Beverages, non-alcoholic	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1ml	1	0	0
cereals and meals	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	35	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - curd	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	33	3	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	38	2	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	5	1	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	18	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	16	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	209	2	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	27	11	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	18	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	30	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	6	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	4	1	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	2	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	18	2	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	11	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	7	1	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	5	5	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	2	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	2	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - unspecified	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	1	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	10	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	8	3	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	3	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	1	1	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	19	1	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	5	2	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	7	1	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - curd	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	7	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - fresh	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	3	0	0
Chocolate	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	9	0	0
Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	3	0	0
	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1ml	5	0	0
Crustaceans	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	17	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses)	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	15	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	16	0	0
	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1ml	29	0	0

Food	Sampling Context	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Staphylococcus</i>	Total units positive for <i>S. aureus</i> , methicillin resistant (MRSA)
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	1	0	0
	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1ml	15	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	559	9	0
Fish - raw	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	76	1	0
Fishery products, unspecified	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	43	1	0
Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	3	0	0
Fruits	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	1	0	0
Fruits - products	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	32	0	0
Infant formula	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	26	0	0
	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1ml	1	0	0
Juice - fruit juice	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	1	0	0
Juice - fruit juice - unpasteurised	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1ml	112	0	0
	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1ml	14	0	0
Juice - mixed juice	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1ml	13	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - fresh	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	40	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	16	1	0
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	21	2	0
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	63	11	0
Meat from deer (venison) - fresh	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	32	5	0
Meat from deer (venison) - meat preparation	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	2	1	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	17	0	0
Meat from pig - fresh	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	63	2	0
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	121	8	0
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	48	1	0
Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	2	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	4	0	0
Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	3	0	0
Meat from pig - offal	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	2	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	8	1	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	83	22	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	1	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	25	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	1	0	0
Meat from rabbit - fresh	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	3	0	0
Meat from sheep - fresh	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	5	0	0
Meat from sheep - meat preparation	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	5	0	0
Meat from turkey - fresh	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	24	1	0
Meat from wild boar - fresh	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	8	0	0
Meat from wild game - birds - fresh	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	3	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	76	7	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos)	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	31	4	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	196	4	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	8	0	0

Food	Sampling Context	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Staphylococcus</i>	Total units positive for <i>S. aureus</i> , methicillin resistant (MRSA)
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	3	0	0
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - raw	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1ml	2	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1ml	9	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1ml	14	0	0
Milk, goats' - raw	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1ml	2	0	0
Milk, sheep's - raw	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1ml	2	0	0
Mushrooms	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	11	0	0
Nuts and nut products	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	33	0	0
Other food	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	74	1	0
Other food of non-animal origin	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	18	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	1g	1222	30	0
	Surveillance official control objective sampling		1ml	6	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta	Surveillance official control objective sampling		1g	138	17	0
Ready-to-eat salads	Surveillance official control objective sampling		1g	111	1	0
Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise	Surveillance official control objective sampling		1g	4	0	0
Sauces and dressings	Surveillance official control objective sampling		1g	4	0	0
	Surveillance official control objective sampling		1ml	1	0	0
Seeds, dried	Surveillance official control objective sampling		1g	33	0	0
Soups	Surveillance official control objective sampling		1g	2	0	0
Spices and herbs	Surveillance official control objective sampling		1g	15	0	0
Sweets	Surveillance official control objective sampling		1g	1	0	0
Vegetables	Surveillance official control objective sampling		1g	35	0	0
Vegetables - products	Surveillance official control objective sampling		1g	25	0	0

4.14. Clostridium difficile

4.14.1. Clostridium difficile in food

Campaign A-803-10: Clostridium difficile in food - Meat from farmed game – land mammals fresh chilled - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: September - November

Type of specimen taken

Meat from farmed game – land mammals fresh chilled

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Clostridium difficile in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

30 samples tested for Clostridium difficile: 0-times positive

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Campylobacter, VTEC and Salmonella spp.

Table 88 Clostridium difficile in food, 2010

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling unit	Sampling weight	Units tested	Total units positive for Clostridium difficile
Meat from farmed game - land mammals - fresh, chilled (Campaign A-803-10)	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	single	25g	30	0

4.14.2. Clostridium difficile in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

All feces samples or intestines collected in the slaughterhouses in course of the zoonoses monitoring program from cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches were forwarded to the national reference laboratory for Clostridium difficile (NRL CD) in the IMED Vienna (AGES) to be tested for Clostridium difficile.

Frequency of the sampling

Animals at slaughter:

The sampling was distributed by randomization over the whole year 2010.

Type of specimen taken

Animals at slaughter: Caecum content of cattle and pigs and intestinal content of 10 chicks per slaughter batch.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The sampling was performed by official veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration a part of the colon (cattle, pigs) or the whole intestines (broiler) were ligated and wrapped in a sterile plastic bag. After cooling down to 4 °C the sample was sent in a hobbox or polystyrene box after adding cooling units to the Institute of Veterinary Diseases Control (IVET) in Graz. Remaining feces/intestinal content after their analyses were collected and sent twice a week to the NRL CD.

Case definition

A sample is defined positive after isolation of Clostridium difficile.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The material was directly plated on selective cycloserine-cefoxitine agar plates (C. difficile agar; bioMérieux, Marcy l'Etoile, France), with and without alcohol-shock pre-treatment as described by Borriello and Honour (Borriello SP, Honour P (1981). Simplified procedure for the routine isolation of Clostridium difficile from faeces. J Clin Pathol 34: 1124–1127). Media were incubated anaerobically at 35 ± 2°C for 48 h. In addition, 3–4 g of fecal material was incubated at 35 ± 2°C for 12 days in thioglycolate bouillon (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) and then subcultured by plating onto C. difficile agar, after alcohol shock, and incubated as described above. Colonies suspicious for C. difficile (based on morphological criteria, Gram stain results and odor) were tested for the common antigen of C. difficile using a latex slide-agglutination test (C. difficile Agglutination Test Kit; Oxoid, Basingstoke, UK). Strains were stored at –80°C in Cryobank tubes (Mast Diagnostics, Bootle, UK) until further testing.

Toxin detection and PCR ribotyping were performed as described by Indra et al. (Indra A, Lassnig H, Baliko N, Much P, Fiedler A, Huhulescu S, Allerberger F (2009) Clostridium difficile: a new zoonotic agent? Wien Klin Wochenschr (2009) 121: 91–95).

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not performed in Austria

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

None

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None

Notification system in place

Findings of Clostridium difficile in animals are not required to be reported to authorities in Austria.

Results of the investigation

See respective tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In Austria, C. difficile is found in animals at very low levels and is not found in food samples.
Therefore the risk of zoonotic transmission for humans seems to be low.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

Nil

Table 89 Clostridium difficile in animals, 2010

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive
Broiler flocks	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	10 intestines per slaughter batch	IMED Vienna	slaughter batch	379	1
Cattle (bovine animals) - adult cattle over 2 years	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling		IMED Vienna	animal	501	17
Cattle (bovine animals) - meat production animals - calves (under 1 year)	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling		IMED Vienna	animal	15	1
Cattle (bovine animals) - meat production animals - young cattle (1-2 years)	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling		IMED Vienna	animal	211	5
fattening pigs	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling		IMED Vienna	animal	342	4

4.15. Hepatitis Virus

4.15.1. Hepatitis Virus in food

Campaign A-017-10: Hepatitis-A virus in food – vegetable products dried (half-dried tomatoes) - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: March

Type of specimen taken

Vegetable products dried (half-dried tomatoes)

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 5 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Hepatitis-A virus in 5 g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

41 samples tested, 0-time positive for Hepatitis-A virus

Additional information

None

Campaign A-022-10: Hepatitis-A virus in food – Live bivalve molluscs – oysters non-depurated - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: April - July

Type of specimen taken

Live bivalve molluscs – oysters non-depurated

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 5 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Hepatitis-A virus in 5 g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

25 samples tested, 0-time positive for Hepatitis-A virus

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Norovirus

Table 90 Hepatitis-A Virus in food, 2010

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling unit	Sampling weight	Units tested	Total units positive for Hepatitis-A virus
Live bivalve molluscs, oysters non-depurated (Campaign A-022-10)	at retail - imported	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	single	5g	25	0
Vegetables - products - dried (half-dried tomatoes Campaign A-017-10)	at retail - imported	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	single	5g	41	0

4.16. Calicivirus

4.16.1. Calicivirus in food

Campaign A-022-10: Norovirus in food – Live bivalve molluscs – oysters non-depurated - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: April - July

Type of specimen taken

Live bivalve molluscs – oysters non-depurated

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 5 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Norovirus in 5 g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

25 samples tested, 0-time positive for Norovirus

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Hepatitis-A virus

Table 91 Norovirus in food, 2010

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling unit	Sampling weight	Units tested	Total units positive for Norovirus
Live bivalve molluscus, oysters non-depurated (Campaign A-022-10)	at retail - imported	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	single	5g	25	0

5. Information on Specific Indicators of Antimicrobial Resistance

5.1. E. coli Indicators

5.1.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Resistance monitoring of faeces isolates from slaughtered animals was started in Austria in 2004 and has been continued annually.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The Austrian wide monitoring program on the trends of antimicrobial resistance of E. coli in broiler slaughter batches, bovine animals and pigs has been implemented according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 17 November 2003 in the National Order Überwachungsprogramme-Verordnung (as amended). The sampling was carried out from January to December 2010 in slaughterhouses.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Europe wide harmonized standards for antimicrobial resistance monitoring are be highly welcome.

Additional information

The results are published annually in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

5.1.2. Antimicrobial resistance in Escherichia coli isolates

A. Antimicrobial resistance of E. coli in animal - All animals - farmed - at slaughterhouse - Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

A sampling plan was created according to the federal monitoring program „ Durchführungserlass Zoonosenmonitoring 2010 - Überwachung ausgewählter Zoonosen und Antibiotikaresistenzen (BMG-74600/0262-II/B/5/2009)“. The sampling plan for E. coli included cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches.

Type of specimen taken

E. coli was isolated from the caecum of slaughtered cattle, pigs and broiler. 170 E. coli strains were tested for their antimicrobial susceptibility. The caecum from one cow or pig or the whole intestines from ten slaughtered broilers within a single slaughter batch at each slaughterhouse were collected.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The intestines were refrigerated to 4 °C and samples were sent to the Institute of Veterinary Disease Control (IVET) in Graz, where each pathogen was isolated and further characterized. The national Reference Lab for antimicrobial resistance in the Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz performed the antimicrobial susceptibility testing for all strains.

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

The number of samples was calculated by experts of the Division for Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment of the AGES based on the expected prevalence of E. coli among the different animal species (cattle, pigs, broiler flocks). All isolated strains of E. coli were sent to the IMED Graz for antimicrobial susceptibility testing.

Methods used for collecting data

All information concerning the tested animals and the sampled slaughterhouses were recorded in a questionnaire. In the laboratory, the data were entered into a database and later analysed in Microsoft® Excel tables.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The intestinal contents are streaked onto the MacConkey-agar plates (Merck Nr. 1.05465) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. The process is repeated for colonies which are suspected for E. coli. These colonies are streaked onto a blood-agar (Oxoid Nr. CM0055, 5% Sheep blood) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. The confirmation of the identification of E. coli is done with an oxidase- (Merck Nr. 1.13300.0001) and spot indol test (Firma Biomedica, Nr. 1069).

Laboratory used for detection for resistance

Antimicrobials included in monitoring

E. coli samples isolated from cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches are tested for antimicrobial susceptibility against gentamicin, kanamycin, streptomycin, ceftotaxim, sulfamethoxazol, trimethoprim, ciprofloxacin, nalidixic acid, ampicillin, chloramphenicol and tetracycline.

Breakpoints used in testing

See respective tables

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

None

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None

Notification system in place

None

Results of the investigation

See respective tables.

National evaluation of the recent situation

Trends and sources of infection are not available yet; a census on the use of antimicrobials in veterinary medicine is planned.

Additional information

Table 92 Breakpoints used for antibiotic resistance testing of E. coli in animals

Test method used	Number of reporting laboratory
Disc diffusion	
E-test	
Agar dilution	
Broth dilution	x

Standards used for testing	The methods are used for investigation of isolates from
CLSI	Feedingstuff
other	Animals
EN ISO 20776-1	Food
	Humans

<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Standard for breakpoint (NCCLS,...)	Dilution method		
		Breakpoint	Range tested concentration (µg/ml)	
			Resistant >	lowest
Aminoglykosid AB				
Gentamicin	EFSA	> 2	0,25	32
Streptomycin	EFSA	> 16	2	256
Carbapeneme				
Imipenem	EFSA	> 0.5	0.125	32
Cephalosporine				
Cefotaxim	EFSA	> 0,25	0,06	128
Folsäureinhibitoren				
Sulfamethoxazol	EFSA	> 256	8	1024
Trimethoprim	EFSA	> 2	0,25	16
Quinolone and Quinoxalin				
Ciprofloxacin	EFSA	> 0,032	0,008	8
Nalidixinsäure	EFSA	> 16	2	256
Penicilline				
Ampicillin	EFSA	> 8	0,5	64
Phenicole				
Chloramphenicol	EFSA	> 16	2	256
Tetracycline				
Tetracyclin	EFSA	> 8	0,5	64

Table 93 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in animals (qualitative tables), 2010

	<i>E.coli</i>								
	Gallus Gallus			Cattle			Pigs		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory									
Antimicrobials:	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
Aminoglykosid AB									
Gentamicin	171	4,1	7	181	0,0	0	169	1,2	2
Streptomycin	171	37,4	64	181	7,7	14	169	56,8	96
Carbapeneme									
Imipenem									
Cephalosporine									
Cefotaxim	171	0,6	1	181	0,0	0	169	1,2	2
Folsäureinhibitoren									
Sulfamethoxazol	171	39,8	68	181	7,2	13	169	32,0	54
Trimethoprim	171	24,0	41	181	1,1	2	169	14,8	25
Quinolone and Quinoxalin									
Ciprofloxacin	171	80,1	137	181	2,2	4	169	4,7	8
Nalidixinsäure	171	78,9	135	181	0,6	1	169	5,3	9
Penicilline									
Ampicillin	171	32,7	56	181	2,2	4	169	17,2	29
Phenicole									
Chloramphenicol	171	7,0	12	181	1,1	2	169	5,9	10
Tetracycline									
Tetracyclin	171	28,1	48	181	8,8	16	169	57,4	97
Number of multiresistant isolates									
fully sensitive	171	9,9	17	181	87,9	159	169	29,6	50
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	171	27,5	47	181	4,4	8	169	16,6	28
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	171	23,4	40	181	1,7	3	169	21,3	36
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	171	18,7	32	181	3,9	7	169	18,3	31
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	171	7,6	13	181	1,1	2	169	8,9	15
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	171	12,9	22	181	1,1	2	169	5,3	9

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For E. coli this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazol

Table 94 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in Cattle (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2010

				<i>E.coli</i>																			
				CATTLE																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	≤< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
Aminoglykosid AB	N	%R	n	n																			
Gentamicin	181	0	0						82	93	5	1											
Streptomycin	181	7,735	14									6	129	30	2	7	5		1	1			
Carbapeneme																							
Imipenem																							
Cephalosporine																							
Cefotaxim	181	0	0				157	23	1														
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
Sulfamethoxazol	181	7,182	13											32	40	43	43	8	2			13	
Trimethoprim	181	1,105	2						60	97	22					2							
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
Ciprofloxacin	181	2,21	4	19	150	8	2	2															
Nalidixinsäure	181	0,552	1									139	38	3			1						
Penicilline																							
Ampicillin	181	2,21	4								8	58	103	8	1			3					
Phenicole																							
Chloramphenicol	181	1,105	2									3	54	112	10				2				
Tetracycline																							
Tetracyclin	181	8,84	16								32	124	8	1		1	5	10					

Table 95 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in broiler - at slaughter - monitoring programme – active monitoring (slaughter batch) - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2010

		<i>E.coli</i>																						
		GALLUS GALLUS																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																							
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																						
Antimicrobials:				≤< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
Aminoglykosid AB																								
	Gentamicin	171	4,094	7					60	98	6		1		1	2	3							
	Streptomycin	171	37,43	64								1	60	32	14	19	16	17	11	1				
Carbapeneme																								
	Imipenem																							
Cephalosporine																								
	Cefotaxim	171	0,585	1			119	45	6					1										
Folsäureinhibitoren																								
	Sulfamethoxazol	171	39,77	68										16	33	42	9	3		1		67		
	Trimethoprim	171	23,98	41					48	71	11					41								
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																								
	Ciprofloxacin	171	80,12	137	12	20	2	3	19	51	26	10	1	5	19	3								
	Nalidixinsäure	171	78,95	135									30	5		1	1	27	47	13	47			
Penicilline																								
	Ampicillin	171	32,75	56								4	44	60	7		1	1	54					
Phenicole																								
	Chloramphenicol	171	7,018	12									1	33	107	18	3	2	2	5				
Tetracycline																								
	Tetracyclin	171	28,07	48								10	100	13				15	33					

Table 96 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in Pigs - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2010

		<i>E. coli</i> PIGS																					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
Aminoglykosid AB				n																			
Gentamicin	169	1,183	2						56	99	11	1				2							
Streptomycin	169	56,8	96									1	40	22	10	20	43	25	8				
Carbapeneme																							
Imipenem																							
Cephalosporine																							
Cefotaxim	169	1,183	2				142	25								1	1						
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
Sulfamethoxazol	169	31,95	54											18	32	36	20	7	2			2	52
Trimethoprim	169	14,79	25					39	92	12	1					25							
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
Ciprofloxacin	169	4,734	8	22	123	16		2	4	1				1									
Nalidixinsäure	169	5,325	9									103	54	3		1	3	1	3	1			
Penicilline																							
Ampicillin	169	17,16	29								7	68	61	4		1	2	26					
Phenicol																							
Chloramphenicol	169	5,917	10									1	34	111	13	4	2	1	3				
Tetracycline																							
Tetracyclin	169	57,4	97								5	55	10	2	1	7	29	60					

5.2. Enterococcus Indicators

5.2.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Resistance monitoring of faeces isolates from slaughtered animals was started in Austria in 2004 and continued in 2010.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The Austrian wide monitoring program on the trends of antimicrobial resistance of Enterococcus in broiler slaughter batches, bovine animals and pigs has been implemented according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 17 November 2003 in the National Order Überwachungsprogramme-Verordnung (as amended). The sampling was carried out from January to December 2010 in slaughterhouses.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Europe wide harmonized standards for antimicrobial resistance monitoring would be highly welcome.

Additional information

5.2.2. Antimicrobial resistance in Enterococcus spp. isolates

A. Antimicrobial resistance of Enterococcus spp. in animal - All animals - farmed - at slaughterhouse - Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

A sampling plan was created according to the federal monitoring program „Durchführungserlass Zoonosenmonitoring 2010 - Überwachung ausgewählter Zoonosen und Antibiotikaresistenzen (BMG-74600/0262-II/B/5/2009)“. The sampling plan for enterococci includes cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches.

Type of specimen taken

Enterococci are isolated from the caecum of slaughtered cattle, pigs and broiler. 170 E. faecalis or E. faecium strains per animal species are tested for their antimicrobial susceptibility. The caecum from one cow or pig or the whole intestines from ten slaughtered broilers within a single slaughter batch at each slaughterhouse are collected.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The intestines were refrigerated to 4 °C and samples were sent to the Institute of Veterinary Disease Control (IVET) in Graz, where each pathogen was isolated and further characterized. The Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz performed the antimicrobial susceptibility testing for all strains.

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

The number of samples was calculated by experts of the Division for Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment of the AGES based on the expected prevalence of *Enterococcus faecalis* and *E. faecium* in the different animal species (cattle, pigs, broiler flocks). From each sample up to five enterococci were differentiated. Only *E. faecalis* and *E. faecium* strains were sent to the IMED Graz for antimicrobial susceptibility testing.

Methods used for collecting data

All information concerning the tested animals and the sampled slaughterhouses were recorded in a questionnaire. In the laboratory, the data were entered into a database and later analysed in Microsoft® Excel tables.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The samples are injected into the Citrate Azide Tween Carbonate Agar (CATC-AGAR, Merck Art.Nr. 1.10279) and incubated at $37\text{ °C} \pm 1\text{ °C}$ for 24 h. Then, the medium is left at room temperature for another 24 hrs. Potential colonies are subcultivated on blood agar (Oxoid Nr. CM0055, 5% Sheep blood) for 24 h at $37 \pm 1\text{ °C}$ which results in the differentiation of *E. faecalis* and *E. faecium* through Gram's method, Catalase Test, Arabinose- and Pyruvate-breakdown.

Laboratory used for detection for resistance

Antimicrobials included in monitoring

E. faecalis/faecium samples isolated from cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches are tested for antimicrobial resistance against gentamicin, streptomycin, vancomycin, ciprofloxacin, erythromycin, linezolid, ampicillin, chloramphenicol, synergid, tetracycline, tigecycline and daptomycin.

Breakpoints used in testing

See respective tables

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

None

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None

Notification system in place

None

Results of the investigation

See respective tables. National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection are not available yet; a census on the use of antimicrobials in veterinary medicine is planned.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not yet available

Additional information

Nil

Table 97 Breakpoints used for antibiotic resistance testing of *Enterococcus faecalis* in animals

Test method used	Number of reporting laboratory
Disc diffusion	
E-test	
Agar dilution	
Broth dilution	x

Standards used for testing	The methods are used for investigation of isolates f
CLSI	Feedingstuff
other	Animals x
EN ISO 20776-1	Food
	Humans

<i>E. faecalis</i>	Standard for breakpoint (NCCLS,...)	Dilution method		
		Breakpoint	Range tested concentration (µg/ml)	
		Resistant >	lowest	highest
Aminoglykosid AB				
Gentamicin	EFSA	> 32	4	2048
Streptomycin	EFSA	> 512	16	2048
Glycopeptide				
Vancomycin	EFSA	> 4	1	64
Quinolone and Quinoxalin				
Ciprofloxacin	EUCAST	> 4	0,25	32
Makrolide				
Erythromycin	EFSA	> 4	0,5	64
Oxacolidinone				
Linezolid	EFSA	> 4	0.5	32
Penicilline				
Ampicillin	EFSA	> 4	0.25	32
Phenicole				
Chloramphenicol	EFSA	> 32	4	256
Streptogramine				
Synercid	EFSA	> 32	0.5	128
Tetracydine				
Tetracyclin	EUCAST	> 4	0.5	64
Tigecyclin	EUCAST	> 0.25	0.032	1
Cyclic Lipopeptides				
Daptomycin	EUCAST	> 4	0.125	16

Table 98 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecalis* in animals (qualitative tables), 2010

	<i>E. faecalis</i>								
	Gallus Gallus			Cattle			Pigs		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory									
Antimicrobials:	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
Aminoglykosid AB									
Gentamicin	172	0,0	0	112	0,0	0	131	4,6	6
Streptomycin	172	25,0	43	112	2,7	3	131	23,7	31
Glycopeptide									
Vancomycin	172	1,2	2	112	0,0	0	131	0,0	0
Quinolone and Quinoxalin									
Ciprofloxacin	172	0,0	0	112	0,0	0	131	0,8	1
Makrolide									
Erythromycin	172	57,0	98	112	6,3	7	131	30,5	40
Oxacolidinone									
Linezolid	172	0,0	0	112	0,0	0	131	0,0	0
Penicilline									
Ampicillin	172	0,0	0	112	0,0	0	131	0,0	0
Phenicole									
Chloramphenicol	172	6,4	11	112	2,7	3	131	10,7	14
Streptogramine									
Synercid	172	0,0	0	112	0,0	0	131	0,0	0
Tetracycline									
Tetracyclin	172	58,7	101	112	18,8	21	131	61,8	81
Tigecyclin									
Cyclic Lipopeptides									
Daptomycin	172	0,6	1	112	0,0	0	131	0,0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates									
fully sensitive	172	26,7	46	112	81,3	91	131	36,6	48
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	172	28,5	49	112	12,5	14	131	29,0	38
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	172	20,9	36	112	3,6	4	131	10,7	14
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	172	17,4	30	112			131	15,3	20
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	172	6,4	11	112	2,7	3	131	6,9	9
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	172			112			131	1,5	2

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For enterococci this includes resistance to streptomycin, gentamicin, chloramphenicol, ampicillin, vancomycin, erythromycin, synercid, tetracycline

Table 99 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecalis* in Cattle (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2010

		<i>E. faecalis</i> CATTLE																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Aminoglykosid AB				n																		
Gentamicin	112	0,0	0									17	92	3								
Streptomycin	112	2,7	3												9	90	9	1				3
Glycopeptide																						
Vancomycin	112	0,0	0						68	42	2											
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	112	0,0	0				2	19	74	17												
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	112	6,3	7					29	26	27	23	1				6						
Oxacolidinone																						
Linezolid	112	0,0	0					1	33	78												
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	112	0,0	0				2	4	74	32												
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	112	2,7	3								37	71	1		2	1						
Streptogramine																						
Synercid	112	0,0	0				3	1	2	5	83	17	1									
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	112	18,8	21				82	6	3			1	3	8	9							
Tigecyclin																						
Cyclic Lipopeptides																						
Daptomycin	112	0,0	0			1		18	75	18												

Table 100 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecalis* in Pigs - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2010

<i>E. faecalis</i> PIGS		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		n																		
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n																	
Aminoglykosid AB																				
Gentamicin	131	4,6							2	11	106	6							4	2
Streptomycin	131	23,7											6	79	15					31
Glycopeptide																				
Vancomycin	131	0,0					91	39	1											
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																				
Ciprofloxacin	131	0,8			1	20	96	12	1			1								
Makrolide																				
Erythromycin	131	30,5				20	24	30	17	2		2	4	32						
Oxacolidinone																				
Linezolid	131	0,0					48	82	1											
Penicilline																				
Ampicillin	131	0,0			2	7	82	40												
Phenicole																				
Chloramphenicol	131	10,7							38	67	8	4	4	10						
Streptogramine																				
Synercid	131	0,0					1	2	4	93	30	1								
Tetracycline																				
Tetracyclin	131	61,8				45	4	1		1			34	46						
Tigecyclin																				
Cyclic Lipopeptides																				
Daptomycin	131	0,0				4	96	28	3											

Table 101 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecalis* in broiler - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2010

<i>E. faecalis</i> GALLUS GALLUS																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Aminoglykosid AB				n																		
Gentamicin	172	0,0	0								1	23	143	5								
Streptomycin	172	25,0	43												9	109	11					43
Glycopeptide																						
Vancomycin	172	1,2	2						68	97	5	2										
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	172	0,0	0					42	126	4												
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	172	57,0	98					23	21	22	8	25	6	4	4	59						
Oxacolidinone																						
Linezolid	172	0,0	0						118	54												
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	172	0,0	0				1	11	133	27												
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	172	6,4	11								80	78		3	10	1						
Streptogramine																						
Synercid	172	0,0	0					3		1	6	127	32	3								
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	172	58,7	101					66	5			2	1	20	35	43						
Tigecyclin																						
Cyclic Lipopeptides																						
Daptomycin	172	0,6	1			1	1	32	126	10	1	1										

Table 102 Breakpoints used for antibiotic resistance testing of *Enterococcus faecium* in animals

Test method used		Number of reporting laboratory	1
Disc diffusion			
E-test			
Agar dilution			
Broth dilution	x		

Standards used for testing		The methods are used for investigation of isolates from	
CLSI		Feedingstuff	
other		Animals	x
		Food	x
		Humans	x

<i>E. faecium</i>	Standard for breakpoint (NCCLS,...)	Dilution method		
		Breakpoint	Range tested	
			concentration (µg/ml)	
		Resistant >	lowest	highest
Aminoglykosid AB				
Gentamicin	EFSA	> 32	4	2048
Streptomycin	EFSA	> 128	16	2048
Glycopeptide				
Vancomycin	EFSA	> 4	1	64
Quinolone and Quinoxalin				
Ciprofloxacin	EUCAST	> 4	0,25	32
Makrolide				
Erythromycin	EFSA	> 4	0,5	64
Oxacolidinone				
Linezolid	EFSA	> 4	0.5	32
Penicilline				
Ampicillin	EFSA	> 4	0.25	32
Phenicol				
Chloramphenicol	EFSA	> 32	4	256
Streptogramine				
Synercid	EFSA	> 1	0.5	128
Tetracycline				
Tetracyclin	EUCAST	> 4	0.5	64
Tigecyclin	EUCAST	> 0,25	0.032	1
Cyclic Lipopeptides				
Daptomycin	EUCAST	> 4	0.125	16

Table 103 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecium* in animals (qualitative tables), 2010

	<i>E. faecium</i>		
	Gallus Gallus	Cattle	Pigs
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes	yes	yes
Number of isolates available in the laboratory			

Antimicrobials:	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
Aminoglykosid AB									
Gentamicin	15	0	0	57	0	0	77	0	0
Streptomycin	15	40	6	57	1,754	1	77	3,896	3
Glycopeptide									
Vancomycin	15	0	0	57	0	0	77	0	0
Quinolone and Quinoxalin									
Ciprofloxacin	15	6,667	1	57	12,28	7	77	5,195	4
Makrolide									
Erythromycin	15	53,33	8	57	8,772	5	77	49,35	38
Oxacolidinone									
Linezolid	15	0	0	57	0	0	77	0	0
Penicilline									
Ampicillin	15	6,667	1	57	0	0	77	0	0
Phenicole									
Chloramphenicol	15	0	0	57	0	0	77	0	0
Streptogramine									
Synercid	15	66,67	10	57	54,39	31	77	89,61	69
Tetracycline									
Tetracyclin	15	73,33	11	57	3,509	2	77	16,88	13
Tigecyclin									
Cyclic Lipopeptides									
Daptomycin	15	0	0	57	0	0	77	0	0

Number of multiresistant isolates									
fully sensitive	15	13,33	2	57	43,86	25	77	7,79	6
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	15	20	3	57	45,61	26	77	32,47	25
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	15	13,33	2	57	8,77	5	77	54,55	42
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	15	20	3	57	1,75	1	77	2,6	2
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	15	33,33	5	57			77	2,6	2
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	15			57			77		

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For enterococci this includes resistance to streptomycin, gentamicin, chloramphenicol, ampicillin, vancomycin, erythromycin, synercid, tetracyclin

Table 104 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecium* in Cattle (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2010

		<i>E. faecium</i> CATTLE																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Aminoglykosid AB				n																		
Gentamicin	57	0,0	0								10	28	19									
Streptomycin	57	1,8	1										4	4	37	11	1					
Glycopeptide																						
Vancomycin	57	0,0	0						44	7	6											
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	57	12,3	7				1	5	13	9	22	7										
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	57	8,8	5					9	2	9	32	5										
Oxacolidinone																						
Linezolid	57	0,0	0						1	52	4											
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	57	0,0	0				1	9	23	22	2											
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	57	0,0	0								12	43	2									
Streptogramine																						
Synercid	57	54,4	31					19	7	9	19	3										
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	57	3,5	2					43	8	4						1	1					
Tigecyclin																						
Cyclic Lipopeptides																						
Daptomycin	57	0,0	0					6	3	17	31											

Table 105 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecium* in Pigs - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2010

<i>E. faecium</i>		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																	
PIGS		<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory																			
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	n															
Aminoglykosid AB																			
Gentamicin	77	0,0	0						1	48	28								
Streptomycin	77	3,9	3										42	32			1		2
Glycopeptide																			
Vancomycin	77	0,0	0				69	8											
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																			
Ciprofloxacin	77	5,2	4			1	13	47	4	8	4								
Makrolide																			
Erythromycin	77	49,4	38			5	5	3	26	35	2			1					
Oxacolidinone																			
Linezolid	77	0,0	0				4	72	1										
Penicilline																			
Ampicillin	77	0,0	0			3	3	22	48	1									
Phenicole																			
Chloramphenicol	77	0,0	0						37	37	2	1							
Streptogramine																			
Synercid	77	89,6	69			4	4	12	46	11									
Tetracycline																			
Tetracyclin	77	16,9	13			59	2	3			1		4	8					
Tigecyclin																			
Cyclic Lipopeptides																			
Daptomycin	77	0,0	0			1	6	22	48										

Table 106 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecium* in broiler - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2010

		<i>E. faecium</i>																				
		GALLUS GALLUS																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Aminoglykosid AB				n																		
Gentamicin	15	0,0	0								2	9	4									
Streptomycin	15	40,0	6												1	4	4	1				5
Glycopeptide																						
Vancomycin	15	0,0	0						11	4												
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	15	6,7	1						3	3	8	1										
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	15	53,3	8						1	1	5				1		7					
Oxacolidinone																						
Linezolid	15	0,0	0						7	8												
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	15	6,7	1				1	2	2	7	2	1										
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	15	0,0	0								9	3	1	2								
Streptogramine																						
Synercid	15	66,7	10					4	1		6	4										
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	15	73,3	11					4						2		4	5					
Tigecyclin																						
Cyclic Lipopeptides																						
Daptomycin	15	0,0	0			1			7	5	2											

6. Foodborne outbreaks

Foodborne outbreaks are defined as two or more human cases of the same disease or infection where the cases are linked or are probably linked to the same food source. A situation in which the observed human cases exceed the expected number of cases and where a same food source is suspected, is also indicative of a foodborne outbreak.

A. Foodborne outbreaks

System in place for identification, epidemiological investigations and reporting of food borne outbreaks

Presently, every district (Austria = 98 + Vienna) is responsible for outbreak investigation. However, food borne outbreaks affecting more than one district or even more than one province (Austria = 9 provinces) are regulated by the Federal Zoonoses Act (Zoonosengesetz, BGBl. I, 128/2005 entered into force on 1. January 2006). The Federal Zoonoses Commission was founded to advise the Federal Minister to survey and combat the zoonoses in Austria. One target of the Zoonoses Act is to ensure that food-borne outbreaks receive proper epidemiological investigation. It regulates, in case of food borne outbreaks affecting more than one province that the governors of the affected provinces provide operative units to investigate possible or confirmed food borne outbreaks. Data concerning epidemiological criteria, potential implicated food items and the source of an outbreak must be collected and adequate epidemiological and microbiological examinations must be conducted. Short reports summarize each outbreak and must be communicated to the Federal Commission for Zoonoses and to AGES.

Description of the types of outbreaks covered by the reporting:

Since there has not been a coordinated approach for outbreak investigation in most provinces, the large majority (162 of 193) of food borne outbreaks are classified as household outbreaks. Coordinated investigation of outbreaks affecting more than one province - unhampered by district limits - will drastically decrease the total number of outbreaks.

National evaluation of the reported outbreaks in the country:

In 2010, 193 food borne outbreaks affecting 838 persons were reported. 155 persons were hospitalized and 2 persons died. The total number of foodborne outbreaks decreased by 45% compared to 2009. The number of cases affected by an outbreak was 4.3 persons. 17 % (10% in 2009) of the reported outbreaks were acquired abroad. 43 % of all foodborne outbreaks acquired in Austria were caused by *Campylobacter* spp. (n=82), 51 % by *Salmonella* spp. (n=98) and 69 % thereof by serotype Enteritidis (n=68).

Relevance of the different causative agents, food categories and the agent/food category combinations

Salmonella and *Campylobacter* pose the most important agents causing 93 % of all foodborne outbreaks. The data quality does presently not allow conclusions on the relevance of different food categories.

Relevance of the different type of places of food production and preparation in outbreaks

The data quality does presently not allow conclusions on the relevance of different food categories.

Evaluation of the severity and clinical picture of the human cases

Hospitalized cases or cases that result in death are presently not ascertained in a valid way: Nevertheless, in 2010, 19 % of patients affected by these foodborne outbreaks were reported as hospitalized (17 % in 2009); there were 2 lethal cases this year (in 2009: 6 lethal cases).

Control measures or other actions taken to improve the situation

Improvement due to the implementation of the Federal Zoonoses Act e.g. the chain of command in terms of investigation of foodborne outbreaks affecting more than one province was implemented.

Table 107 Foodborne outbreaks in humans, 2010

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Evidence	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
C. jejuni	1	household		2	2	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Bakery products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Mobile retailer/market/street vendor	Transport of food	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	2	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household	Spain	3	0	0	Tap water including well-water	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Restaurant/Bar/Hotel	Catering/Restaurant	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household	Morocco	2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Other foods	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	general		4	1	0		Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Restaurant/Bar/Hotel	Other	Unknown	Unprocessed contaminated ingredient
C. jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Other or mixed red meat and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Take-away/Fast food Restaurant	Take-away or fast food outlet	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	general		2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Retail sale outlet	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	general		2	1	0	Turkey meat and	Laboratory detection	Low	Restaurant/Bar	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Evidence	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
							products thereof	in human cases		r/Hotel			
C. jejuni	1	household	Moldova	2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Travel abroad	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		4	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		3	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Turkey meat and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Retail sale outlet	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	general		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Restaurant/Bar/Hotel	Catering/Restaurant	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household	Georgia	2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	general		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Hospital/medical care facility	Processing plant	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		3	1	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Fish and fish products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Other

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Evidence	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
C. jejuni	1	household		2	0	0		Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Other	Farm (primary production)	Domestic market	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household	Morocco	2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Imported from outside EU	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	general	Indonesia	2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household	Spain	2	0	0	Mixed or buffet meals	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Other	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	0	0			Low	Restaurant/Bar/Hotel	Catering/Restaurant	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	general		3	0	0		Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Other	Farm (primary production)	Domestic market	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		4	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
C. jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection	Low	Household/do	Household/d	Unknown	Unknown

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Evidence	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
								in human cases		mestic kitchen	omestic kitchen		
C. jejuni	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		4	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Pig meat and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic	Unknown	Unknown

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Evidence	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
											kitchen		
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		4	1	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Mobile retailer/market/street vendor	Take-away or fast food outlet	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Other, mixed or unspecified poultry meat and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Fish and fish products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household	Hungary	2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Evidence	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
Campylobacter spp.	1	household	Iran	2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	2	0	Other foods	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
EHEC O174:H2	1	general		7	2	0	Vegetables and juices and other products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
EHEC O181:H49	1	household		3	1	0	Milk	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Farm (primary production)	Domestic market	Unknown
EHEC O26:H31	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Hepatitis-A virus	1	household	Italy	2	0	0	Mixed or buffet meals	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Restaurant/Bar/Hotel	Travel abroad	Unknown	Unknown
Listeria monocytogenes 1/2a	1	household		3	1	0	Dairy products (other than cheeses)	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Norovirus	1	general		69	0	0	Mixed or buffet meals	Laboratory detection in human cases	Strong	Canteen or workplace catering	Catering/Restaurant	Unknown	Infected food handler
Norovirus	1	general		4	0	0	Unknown		Low	Restaurant/Bar/Hotel	Catering/Restaurant	Unknown	Unknown
Norovirus	1	general		6	1	0	Mixed or buffet meals	Analytical epidemiological evidence	Strong	Other	Transport of food	Domestic market	Infected food handler
Paratyphi B var. L(+) tartrate+ (variant Java)	1	household	India	2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Paratyphi B var. L(+) tartrate+ (variant Java)	1	general	Montenegro	2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
RDNC	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Evidence	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
S. Abony	1	household	Serbia	2	2	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Travel abroad	Unknown	Unknown
S. Bardo	1	household	Greece	2	2	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Travel abroad	Unknown	Unknown
S. Branderup	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Coeln	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis	1	household	Croatia	3	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Travel abroad	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis	1	general	Turkey	2	2	0	Mixed or buffet meals	Analytical epidemiological evidence	Low	Restaurant/Bar/Hotel	Travel abroad	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT RDNC	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT RDNC	1	household	Romania	2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Travel abroad	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT1	1	household		3	0	0	Eggs and egg products	Laboratory characterisation of isolates from food and human samples	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Retail sale outlet	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT1	1	household		4	0	0		Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Retail sale outlet	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT1	1	household	Ukraine	2	2	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Other	Farm (primary production)	Imported from outside EU	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT13	1	household		2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT13	1	household		2	0	0		Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT13a	1	household	Slovakia	2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Intra EU trade	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT14b	1	household	Italy	2	1	0	Eggs and egg products		Low	Unknown	Catering/Restaurant	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT14b	1	general		74	3	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Residential institution	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Evidence	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
										(nursing home, prison, boarding schools)			
S. Enteritidis PT14b	1	household		2	1	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT2	1	general	Hungary	2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Canteen or workplace catering	Travel abroad	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT35	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	1	0	Eggs and egg products	Descriptive epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food chain or its environment, Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	Strong	Household/domestic kitchen	Farm (primary production)	Domestic market	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	1	0	Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	general		3	0	0	Mixed or buffet meals	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Other	Travel abroad	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	general		5	5	1	Eggs and egg products	Descriptive epidemiological evidence, Detection	Strong	Other	Farm (primary)	Domestic market	Unprocessed contaminate

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Evidence	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
								of causative agent in food vehicle or its component, Detection of causative agent in food chain or its environment, Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans			production)		d ingredient
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	general		7	1	0	Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	general		33	2	0	Eggs and egg products	Analytical epidemiological evidence	Strong	Restaurant/Bar/Hotel	Catering/Restaurant	Domestic market	Unprocessed contaminated ingredient
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	general		2	0	0	Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		3	2	0	Turkey meat and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Intra EU trade	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household	Italy	2	0	0	Crustaceans, shellfish, molluscs and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Restaurant/Bar/Hotel	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	general		7	0	0	Eggs and egg products	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Strong	Household/domestic kitchen	Farm (primary production)	Intra EU trade	Storage time/temperature abuse
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	general		13	2	0	Bakery products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Strong	Other	Household/domestic kitchen	Intra EU trade	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	general		4	3	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Retail sale outlet	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	general		14	2	0	Mixed or buffet	Analytical	Strong	Household/do	Other	Intra EU	Cross-

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Evidence	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
							meals	epidemiological evidence		mestic kitchen		trade	contamination
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	general	Switzerland	13	6	0	Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Restaurant/Bar/Hotel	Travel abroad	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household	Croatia	2	0	0	Dairy products (other than cheeses)	Laboratory characterisation of isolates from food and human samples	Low	Mobile retailer/market/street vendor	Travel abroad	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	general		5	3	0	Unknown		Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	1	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Domestic market	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT4b	1	household		2	0	0			Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	household		5	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	household		2	0	0	Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unprocessed contaminated ingredient
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	household		2	1	0	Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	household		6	0	0	Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Domestic market	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	household		5	3	0	Dairy products (other than cheeses)		Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	household		4	0	0	Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Intra EU trade	Inadequate heat treatment
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	general		2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Domestic market	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	0	0	Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Evidence	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	2	0	Bovine meat and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Restaurant/Bar/Hotel	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	general		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	2	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	1	0	Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Domestic market	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	general		9	4	0	Bakery products	Analytical epidemiological evidence	Strong	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		5	2	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Restaurant/Bar/Hotel	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	2	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	1	0	Eggs and egg products		Low	Restaurant/Bar/Hotel	Catering/Restaurant	Intra EU trade	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		3	0	0	Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Retail sale outlet	Domestic market	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	2	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Evidence	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	2	0		Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
S. Infantis	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Java	1	household		2	0	0	Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
S. Kentucky	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Manhattan	1	household		2	0	0	Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Mbandaka	1	general		159	31	0	Eggs and egg products	Descriptive epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component, Detection of causative agent in food chain or its environment, Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	Strong	Household/domestic kitchen	Farm (primary production)	Domestic market	contaminated feeding stuffs
S. Oranienburg	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Saintpaul	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Saintpaul	1	household	Egypt	2	0	0	Unknown		Low	Restaurant/Bar/Hotel	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Saintpaul	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
S. Stanley	1	household	unknown	2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Restaurant/Bar/Hotel	Travel abroad	Unknown	Unknown

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Evidence	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
S. Thompson	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Typhimurium	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Typhimurium DT104	1	household	Tunisia	2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Restaurant/Bar/Hotel	Travel abroad	Unknown	Unknown
S. Typhimurium DT104	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Typhimurium DT120	1	household	Hungary	2	1	0	Pig meat and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Aircraft/ship/train	Travel abroad	Intra EU trade	Unknown
S. Typhimurium DT120	1	household		2	2	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Typhimurium DT141	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Typhimurium DT24	1	household	Mauritius	2	0	0	Fish and fish products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Restaurant/Bar/Hotel	Travel abroad	Unknown	Unknown
S. Typhimurium DT27	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Typhimurium monophasic DT 193	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
S. Typhimurium U277	1	household		3	1	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
S. Typhimurium U310	1	household		2	2	1	Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Domestic market	Unknown
Salmonella spp.	1	general	Egypt	2	0	0	Fish and fish products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Restaurant/Bar/Hotel	Travel abroad	Unknown	Unknown
Shigella flexneri	1	household		2	2	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Shigella sonnei	1	household		3	1	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Analytical epidemiological evidence	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown
Shigella sonnei	1	household	Turkey	6	0	0	Unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Household/domestic kitchen	Imported from outside EU	Unknown
Trichinella spiralis	1	household	Bosnia-Herzegovina	3	2	0	Pig meat and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Slaughterhouse	Imported from	Unknown

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Evidence	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
												outside EU	
Yersinia enterocolitica O:9	1	household		2	0	0	Pig meat and products thereof	Laboratory detection in human cases	Low	Household/domestic kitchen	Retail sale outlet	Unknown	Unknown
Total	193			838	155	2							

7. Information on specific microbiological agents

7.1. Staphylococcal Enterotoxins

7.1.1. Staphylococcal enterotoxins general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Not available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Additional information

Not available

7.1.2. Staphylococcal enterotoxins in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Not available

Type of specimen taken

Not available

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Not available

Definition of positive finding

Not available

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Not available

Preventive measures in place

Not available

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the hazard

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Not available

Notification system in place

Not available

Results of the investigation

See table below

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

Table 108 Staphylococcal enterotoxins in food

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for Staph. enterotoxins
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at farm	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single		1	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single		2	1
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single		1	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single		1	1
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single		1	0
Fishery products, unspecified	at retail - imported	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single		1	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single		1	0
Meat, mixed meat - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked chilled	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single		2	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single		3	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified ready-to-eat foods chilled	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single		3	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified ready-to-eat foods chilled	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0
Cereals and meals	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	1	0
Vegetable products cooked chilled	at catering	Surveillance official control objective sampling	single	25g	2	0

7.2. Enterobacter sakazakii

7.2.1. Enterobacter sakazakii in foodstuff

Table 109 Enterobacter sakazakii in food

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for E. sakazakii
Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses	at retail - domestic production	single		1	0

7.3. Histamine

7.3.1. Histamine general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Not available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Additional information

Not available

7.3.2. Histamine in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Not available

Type of specimen taken

Not available

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Not available

Definition of positive finding

Not available

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Not available

Preventive measures in place

Not available

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the hazard

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Not available

Notification system in place

Not available

Results of the investigation

See table below

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

Table 110 Histamine in food, 2010

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units in non-conformity	<= 100 mg/kg	>100 - <= 200 mg/kg	>200 - <= 400 mg/kg	>400 mg/kg
Fish - raw	at retail	single		7	0	7			
	at retail - imported	single		8	0	8			
Fish raw frozen		single	10g	1	0	1			
Fishery products, unspecified	at processing plant - domestic production	single		4	0	4			
	at retail	single		2	0	2			
	at retail - domestic production	single		7	0	7			
	at retail - imported	single		38	0	37	1		
Fishery products, unspecified ready-to-eat chilled		single	10g	2	0	2			
Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine* - not enzyme matured	at retail - imported	single	5g	21	0	1			
		single	25g	244	8	5	3		
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail - domestic production	single		1	0	1			
Cheeses made from cows' milk curd		single	10g	2	0	2			
Cheeses made from cows' milk hard made from pasteurised milk		single	5g	4	0	2	1	1	

*Particularly the fish species from *Scombridae*, *Clupeidae*, *Engraulidae*, *Coryfenidae*, *Pomatomidae*, *Scombresosidae*

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